

STUDIES IN SCURVY

BY

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*This work has been carried out by aid of
grants from the Karolinska Institutet and
the Swedish Society for Medical Research.*

UPPSALA 1924

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Vol. III. Supplementum

17: V. 1924

To

Professors Axel Holst and Theodor Frölich

This work is respectfully inscribed by

THE AUTHOR

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94 microphotograms.
33 curves in the text.
6 colored plates.

Preface.

The work which is here presented was begun in July, 1922. It would have been impracticable to fulfil it without the possibilities of technical aid offered by clinical laboratories. To Professors F. HENSCHEN and G. HÄGGQUIST, who have allowed me to avail myself of these possibilities and to whom I am also indebted for much helpful advice, I beg to express my gratitude. My thanks are also due to Professors I. JUNDÉLL and U. QUENSEL, to Assistant Professor Dr. C. KLING, Doctors R. NORDGREN, G. VESTBECK, H. DAVIDE, A. WASSÉN, S. SIVE, A. WALLGREN, Å. ÅKERLUND, the Dental Surgeon Dr. G. WESTIN, and others, for various reasons, some of which I have mentioned more particularly in my book. Special thanks are due to Doctor F. WAHLGREN and Fil. Doctor L. G. ROMÉLL who have kindly read the proofs.

My late father, the historian NILS J. HÖJER, who during all his life, beside his practical activity as a teacher, devoted himself to scientific work for science's sake, has been my model. My wife, SIGNE HÖJER, has been my helper.

I have allowed myself as a respectful token of admiration to inscribe my work to Professors AXEL HOLST and THEODOR FRÖLICH in Christiania, the first investigators in the field of experimental scurvy, whose work still remains unrivalled. Even though the exaggeration is evident in Funk's utterance (1922): »Since the experiments of Holst and Frölich, no real progress has been made (in experimental scurvy), in spite of the numerous publications that have appeared», yet his words show how high Holst and Frölich's works rank among all the rest.

Hagalund, Sweden. February 1924.

J. Axel Höjer.

PART V.

Records of cases belonging to Part I.

Extracts.

Guinea-pigs No. 1—96, Series 1—23.

Series I.

Animals 1—8. Basal diet from July 11 (No. 1—4) or August 5 (No. 5—8). Weight charts, Fig. 95.

No. 1. For this a more detailed extract from the record is given as a specimen.

♂. Black—brown—white. (The colours are mentioned in the order in which they dominate.)

²²/₇ The left hind-leg sometimes lifted in scurvy position. Frequent and deep breathing. Drinks but little milk. Cries out at palpation of left knee. ²⁵/₇ Bad appetite. Skin dry. Coat rough. Priapism. ²⁶/₇ Scurvy position of left hind-leg permanent. The upper epiphysis of left tibia fractured. Sits brooding. ¹/₈ Getting weaker and weaker. ²/₈ Drags the hind quarters; falling. ³/₈ Mors. ⁴/₈ *Post-mortem* examination: Hair easily loosening in tufts. Body very lean. At the stripping off of the skin, *fractures* in the upper epiphyseal lines of right tibia and both humeri. Also diaphyses of the long bones more easily broken than normally. *Upper jaw* brittle (a blunt pincette easily pierces this bone as well as the bottom of the cranium). The molars of the lower jaw somewhat loose. Different joints, especially knee-joints, swollen. The swelling is localized to the adjacent epiphyses. The costochondral junctions swollen, forming a distinct rosary, most marked from the inside, partly due to an angular bend («bayonet position») between cartilage and bone. *Hemorrhages* numerous in subcutis and muscles. Sometimes they appear in the neighbourhood of fractures (left knee, many ribs), otherwise near the muscle connections around knees, ankles and elbows, and are numerous under pleura and pericardium viscerae. The *adipose tissue*, which is very sparse, is deeply yellow with a brownish tinge. The *heart auricles* are highly dilated. The section surface of the *liver* shows the central veins filled with blood. Otherwise nothing abnormal was remarked at the ocular examination. Microscopical examination was made of 22 ribs (Fig. 44), elbows, wrists, knees, ankles (Fig. 47), lower jaw (Fig. 34), teeth (Fig. 14, 34) muscles and liver. The staining has been hematoxylin, for the different lobes of the liver also sudan, for the ribs also methylene-blue. The description of sections from different organs forms the basis of the exposition in Part I and will not be printed here.

Diagnosis: Scorbut gravior manifestus

No. 2.

♀. Black—white—brown.

Clinical progress and macroscopical findings very like those of No. 1.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{5}{8}$ s. Not examined microscopically.*Diagnosis:* Scorbut gravior manifestus.

Fig. 95. Series I. No antiscorbutic.

No. 3.

♂. Brown—white—black.

Clinical progress and macroscopical findings of a nature very like the preceding numbers, though of a more pronounced degree (lifetime 38 days).

Teeth very loose both in upper and lower jaw, can easily be removed with the pincette. Hemorrhages in all rib interstices, around knees and elbows.

Microscopical examination of the same organs as in No. 1. Tooth, Fig. 31. Musculature, Fig. 57.*Diagnosis:* Scorbut gravior manifestus.

No. 4.

♂. White—brown—black.

Clinical progress and macroscopical findings as in No. 3. Teeth looser still, almost falling out.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{10}{8}$ s. Not examined microscopically.*Diagnosis:* Scorbut gravior manifestus.

No. 5.

♂. Black—brown—white.

The scurvy symptoms (joint-lesions, hemorrhages) in this case seemed still after a month comparatively little developed, but the animal was exceedingly emaciated and died $10/9$. Autopsied the same day: no hemorrhages. Submental lymph-glands swollen. One of them suppurated, forming an abscess large as a good-sized pea. Teeth can easily be removed. The costochondral junctions enlarged, those of the upper seven pairs show distinctly the white or yellowish white line. Otherwise as No. 1. Histological examination of the same organs as No. 1, and besides of the spleen.

Diagnosis: Scorbut gravior manifestus.

No. 6.

♂. Black—light brown.

$25/9$ Walks with difficulty. Dead $4/9$, autopsied $5/9$. Histological examination as in No. 5. Diaphyses of slightly increased fragility, epiphyses easily broken. Hemorrhages only in a few rib interstices. The liver contains plenty of fat. No swelling of lymph-glands. The rest as No. 5.

Diagnosis: Scorbut gravior manifestus.

No. 7.

♀. Grey—white.

Dead and autopsied $3/9$. Histological examination as in No. 5; spleen also stained with Giemsa. The macroscopic changes are similar to those of No. 1, only in this case there are no visceral hemorrhages and the teeth can easily be removed.

Diagnosis: Scorbut gravior manifestus.

No. 8.

♂. Grey—yellow.

Dead $1/9$, autopsied $2/9$. Hemorrhages around caput humeri dx (fracture), both scapulae, both knees and in the upper six rib interstices. The epiphyses of the long bones are easily broken, the diaphyses not. All teeth very loose. The rest as No. 1. Histological examination of the same organs as in No. 5. Besides staining of ribs with Giemsa.

Diagnosis: Scorbut gravior manifestus.

Conclusion for Series I: No antiscorbutic can be perceived in the basal diet.

Series II.

Animals 9—12, and 33 (partly). Controls on complete dietary from July 22 to December 11 (No. 9—11). September 8 to December 11 (No. 12), July 22 to October 28 (No. 33). Weight charts Fig. 96.

No. 9.

♂. Black—brown—white.

Healthy till it was chloroformed $11/12$. Autopsied $14/12$. Histological examination as in No. 7. Everywhere normal conditions.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 10.

♀. Black—white.

Pregnancy stated $26/11$. At the *post-mortem* examination a fetus was found in one of the uterine horns, 5 cm. from vertex to coccyx. (Fig. 32, 48). Plenty of fat peripherally in the liver acini. The rest as No. 9.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 11.

♀. White—black—brown.

Looked sound the whole time. Delivered $\frac{8}{9}$ of a lively young (No. 12). Progress, examination and findings for the rest as in No. 9. Muscle, Fig. 52; liver, Fig. 71; spleen, Fig. 79, 82.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

Fig. 96. Series II. > 1 m. pr. d.

No. 12.

♂. Black—brown—white.

Progress, examination and findings as in No. 9 (spleen not examined histologically).

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

Conclusion for Series II: The controls have shown perfect health. No signs of scurvy, either clinically or at the patho-anatomical examination.

Series III.

Animals 13—19. Normal dietary. Were injected $\frac{29}{7}$ with tubercle bacilli, stock No. 80, received in a homogeneous emulsion from the Public Medical Institute. The absolute doses varied from 0.0000005 to 0.0025 grams of bacilli. The injection was made into the adductors of the right thigh. All the animals survived and were killed after 135 days, on $\frac{11}{12}$.

Weight charts Fig. 97. At the *post-mortem* examination no sign of another infection could be discovered, nor any sign of scurvy. Histological examination was made, besides of liver, spleen and lungs, also of a number of 11—17 ribs, knees, ankles, elbows, wrists, and lower jaw. No. 16 and 18, which had not increased in weight during the last two months, showed symptoms of scurvy at this examination. The rest showed normal bone pictures.

No. 13.

♂. Black—brown—white.

$\frac{29}{7}$ injection with 0.000005 grams of tubercle bacilli.

Diagnosis: Tuberculosis loc. prim., lymphogland. regional., paratracheal. et submaxill., lienis. Cirrhosis hepatis initialis. No scurvy.

Fig. 97. Series III. > 1 m. pr. d.

No. 14.

♀. Light brown—black—white.

$\frac{29}{7}$ injection with 0.000005 grams of tubercle bacilli. $\frac{8}{9}$ Pregnant.

$\frac{7}{10}$ delivered of two sturdy young ones (No. 92 and 94), that she suckled for two weeks.

Diagnosis: Tuberculosis loc. prim., lymphogland. regional., lienis. Cirrhosis hepatis initialis. No scurvy.

No. 15.

♂. Brown—black—white.

$\frac{29}{7}$ injection with 0.000025 grams of tubercle bacilli.

Diagnosis: Tuberculosis loc. prim., lymphogland. regional., lienis. Cirrhosis hepatis initialis. No scurvy.

No. 16.

♂. Light brown—white—black.

$\frac{29}{7}$ injection with 0.00005 grams of tubercle bacilli.

At the histological examination the root incisor shows a disordered odontoblast layer, the predentin is amorphously calcified and there is a beginning formation of pulpa bone.

Diagnosis: Tuberculosis loc. prim.; lymphogland. region.; lienis, pulmonum. Cirrhosis hepatis initialis. Scorbut mitior latens levior.

No. 17.

♂. Brown—black—white.

³⁰/₇ injection with 0.0025 grams of tubercle bacilli.

Diagnosis: Tuberculosis loc. prim., lymphogland. region., lienis. Cirrhosis hepatis initialis. No scurvy.

No. 18.

♂. White—black—brown.

²⁹/₇ injection with 0.0005 grams of tubercle bacilli.

At the histological examination the same changes are seen in the incisor root as in No. 16. In the costochondral junction the cartilage columns are seen in disorder.

Diagnosis: Tuberculosis loc. prim.; lymphogland. region.; lienis, hepatis, pulmonum, testium. Scorbut mitior latens extensus.

No. 19.

♂. White—light brown.

²⁹/₇ injection with 0.0025 grams of tubercle bacilli.

At the *post-mortem* examination the incisors of the lower jaw are found to be somewhat loose. Histological examination of these shows a normal picture.

Diagnosis: Tuberculosis loc. prim., lymphogland. region., lienis, hepatis, pulmon. No scurvy.

Conclusion for Series III: The consequence of an injection of tubercle bacilli has been a tuberculosis which, when the animals were killed after 135 days, has left distinct marks in the local focus, lymphglands, spleen and liver, with higher dosage also in other organs. The liver changes with the smaller dosages consist of an interacinous increase of the connective tissue. With the higher dosages this connective tissue in some places assumes the character of tuberculous granulation tissue. The three animals which showed general tuberculosis (No. 16, 18, 19) did not increase in weight during the last month. In any case the virulence of the bacilli must be indicated as rather weak. One animal (No. 14) even went through a delivery followed by three weeks' suckling of twins, and afterwards went on well.

Series IV.

Animals 20—23. From August 8 basal diet + 1 ccm. of red whortleberry juice bought at grocer's. Weight charts, Fig. 98.

All four proceeded as cases of typical scurvy to death after 26 to 30 days and showed, at the *post-mortem* examination (teeth that were easily removed, extensive hemorrhages, swollen joints, enlarged costochondral junctions with white lines, fragile epiphyses and, to a smaller degree, diaphyses, etc.) as well as at the histological examination of the same organs as in No. 5, the typical signs of scurvy. (No. 22 not microscopically examined.)

No. 20.

♂. White—black.

Dead and autopsied ⁵/₀.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 21.

♀. White (albino).

Dead $\frac{2}{9}$, autopsied $\frac{3}{9}$. Spleen also stained with Giemsa.*Diagnosis*: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 22.

♂. Light brown—white.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{5}{9}$.*Diagnosis*: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 23.

♀. White—light brown—black.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{1}{9}$. Tooth, Fig. 17; muscles, Fig. 54.*Diagnosis*: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Fig. 98. Series IV. No antiscorbutic.

Conclusion for Series IV: The dosage administered (1 ccm.) of red whortleberry juice with the origin mentioned has not had any perceptible antiscorbutic effect.

Series V.

Animals 24—27. From August 8, basal diet and besides 5 ccm. each of the same red whortleberry juice as in Series 4. Weight charts, Fig. 99.

All four proceeded as typical cases of scurvy to death in 24 to 27 days. At the *post-mortem* examination they all showed extensive hemorrhages in the intercostal musculature, in the muscles round the knees, ankles, elbows and scapulae; No. 24 also extensive hemorrhages subcutaneously and under the tongue epithelium. The picture for the rest like that shown in Series IV, also at the histological examination of organs mentioned there.

No. 24.

♀. White—black—light brown.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{5}{9}$.*Diagnosis*: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 25.

♂. Black—light brown.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{5}{9}$. Tooth, Fig. 9.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 26.

♂. Light brown.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{6}{9}$. The marrow of the ribs also stained with Giemsa.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Fig. 99. Series V. No antiscorbutic.

No. 27.

♀. White—greyish brown.

Dead $\frac{4}{9}$, autopsied $\frac{5}{9}$. After $\frac{19}{8}$ the animal had a slight cough. The spleen picture confirms the surmise that an infection has been present. The marrow of the ribs also stained with Giemsa.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. Infectio.

Conclusion for Series V: The dosage administered (5 ccm.) of red whortleberry juice with the origin mentioned has not had any perceptible antiscorbutic effect.

Series VI.

Animals 28—33. They got from different dates basal diet and besides 10 ccm. of the same juice that had been given in the two preceding series. Weight charts, Fig. 100.

No. 28.

♀. Black—white.

The animal was put $\frac{11}{7}$ on solely basal diet and with this diet developed scurvy symptoms. $\frac{17}{7}$ keeping still. $\frac{22}{7}$ tenderness of right knee. $\frac{24}{7}$ lame; does not finish its milk. $\frac{20}{7}$ very dishevelled; swallows its faeces; pronounced oliguria. $\frac{29}{7}$ 10 ccm. of the above-mentioned juice was

given. $^{30}/_7$ scurvy position of left hind-leg. $^1/_8$ less dishevelled, somewhat livelier movements. $^6/_8$ oliguria lessened. $^{12}/_8$ mors. Autopsied $^{14}/_8$, the examination showed very marked scorbutic changes, like those in Series IV and V, likewise the histological examination of all ribs, knees, ankles, elbows, wrists, jaw and liver. Musculature, Fig. 53. Nowhere an effect of the antiscorbutic can be traced. The clinically observable changes which set in with the administering of the juice — the animal became livelier, passed a larger quantity of urine and had a less dishevelled coat — is not necessarily owing to an antiscorbutic effect. The animal died 32 days after the first alteration of the diet, a fortnight after it had the whortleberry juice.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Fig. 100. Series VI. No antiscorbutic.

No. 29.

♀. Light brown—white.

$^8/_8$ put on basal diet with an addition of 10 ccm. of red whortleberry juice. On that date the animal had decreased in weight for a week back (infection). It died after 12 days, $^{20}/_8$, and was autopsied the same day. Teeth firm, no signs of scurvy. The animal was fairly fat and generally showed normal conditions. The right lung adhered to the chest wall through

a fibropurulent exudate. In the left pleura a sparse hemorrhagic exudate. On the pericardium a film of fibrin. In both lungs numerous small pneumoniae, partly forming abscesses. Spleen somewhat enlarged. At the histological examination of the epiphyseal ends of the long bones, the bone columns are found to be somewhat thin, the bone marrow rather bright. Root of a tooth, Fig. 5. Hemorrhages in the rib musculature, otherwise none. Hyperplasia of the spleen. Liver: diffuse fat, all over staining badly.

Diagnosis: Scorbut latens gravior, bronchopneumoniae bilaterales c. pleurit., pericarditis.

No. 30.

♀. White—light brown—black.

Put on basal diet $\frac{8}{8}$, with an addition of 10 ccm. red whortleberry juice. On that date the animal had remained at the same weight a week. $\frac{21}{8}$ conjunctivitis purulenta. $\frac{22}{8}$ dead, a fortnight after beginning with the diet. *Post-mortem* examination the same day. No adipose tissue except around the kidneys. Purulent exudate in the conjunctiva. Pea-sized abscesses in the submaxillary lymph-glands. Hyperemia in the lungs, diminished air content. Irregular sore in the mucous membrane of the caecum in its most oral part with necrotic bottom, passing over to the adjacent part of the small intestine. The corresponding part of the serosa has a purulent film; hyperemia in the mesentery. Possibly some swelling of the upper epiphyseal line of the tibia. The epiphyseal ends of the long bones are more easily broken than normally. The upper back molar on the right rather loose.

Diagnosis: Scorbut latens gravior; septicemia.

No. 31.

♂. Black—white.

$\frac{8}{8}$ put on basal diet with an addition of 10 ccm. of whortleberry juice. Typical progress of scurvy. $\frac{1}{9}$ diarrhea. $\frac{7}{9}$ died and was autopsied. Macro- and microscopical examination as in Series V. Liver enormously fatty.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior; infectio.

No. 32.

♂. White—black—brown.

$\frac{28}{8}$ put on basal diet with an addition of 10 ccm. of whortleberry juice. Showing the picture of uncomplicated scurvy it proceeded to death after 31 days, $\frac{25}{9}$, and was autopsied the same day. The *post-mortem* examination could not be concluded.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 33.

♀. At first fed during 160 days on complete diet (weight chart, Fig. 96). During this time she was delivered of twins (No. 91 and 93), and showed every sign of health. Put on basal diet $\frac{28}{10}$ with 10 ccm. of the whortleberry juice. Had scurvy symptoms and died after 32 days, $\frac{2}{12}$. Autopsied the same day, showing the same picture as the animals in Series V. No histological examination.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Conclusion for Series VI: The dosage administered (10 ccm.) of red whortleberry juice with the origin mentioned has had no perceptible anti-scorbutic effect.

Series VII.

Animals 34—37. The animals had from August 31 5 cem. raw fresh juice, immediately before the feeding pressed from red whortleberries bought in the market-place. Progress, findings at *post-mortem* examination, histological picture similar to those in Series V. Weight charts, Fig. 101.

No. 34.

♀. Yellow—black—white.

Died $\frac{7}{10}$, autopsied $\frac{8}{10}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Fig. 101. Series VII. No antiscorbutic.

No. 35.

♂. Yellow—black—white.

Died and was autopsied $\frac{5}{10}$. Musculature, Fig. 62; liver, Fig. 73.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 36.

♂. Yellow—black—white.

Died and was autopsied $\frac{12}{20}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 37.

Brown—white—black.

Died $\frac{30}{3}$. Autopsied $\frac{1}{10}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Conclusion for Series VII: The animals have lived on an average 37 days, which is rather a long lifetime for animals on scurvy diet. It ought

to be observed that the animals in this series were heavier than the rest. No marked antiscorbutic effect of the fresh, raw juice of red whortleberries could be perceived.

Series VIII.

Animals 38—41. The animals got basal diet from August 8, and besides each 2 ccm. of the juice from red whortleberries which had been bottled nearly a year in water. The juice was pressed out of the berries immediately before the feeding. Histological examination of the same organs as in Series V. Weight charts, Fig. 102.

Fig. 102. Series VIII. No antiscorbutic.

No. 38.

♀. Black—light brown.

Kept in the same cage as No. 64, which died $12/8$ of acute infection. Died and was autopsied $16/8$. No sign of scurvy was seen macroscopically. In the small intestine highly injected vessels and ulcerations of the mucous membrane, corresponding to the localization of faecal lumps. Histological examination: root of a tooth, Fig. 4. The liver shows to a large extent the picture of acute necrosis.

Diagnosis: Scorbut latens gravior.

No. 39.

♂. Black—white—brown.

Progress, examination and findings similar to those in Series V. Died $4/8$, autopsied $9/8$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 40.

♂. Brown—black—white.

Progress, examination and findings similar to those of Series V. Died $5/8$, autopsied $8/8$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 41.

♀. Black—brown—white.

Progress, examination and findings similar to those of Series V. Died $14/9$, autopsied $15/9$. Liver, Fig. 72, also stained for iron. Spleen, Fig. 81, 83; stained according to Giemsa and on amyloid.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Conclusion for Series VIII: No antiscorbutic effect was observed from 2 cm. of the juice pressed in 1922 from berries preserved in water since 1921.

Fig. 103. Series IX. No antiscorbutic.

Series IX.

Animals 42—45. The animals had basal diet from August 8, with an addition of 7 cm. of the same juice as Series VIII. Weight charts, Fig. 103. Progress, examination and findings similar to those in Series V.

No. 42.

♂. White—black—yellow.

Dead and autopsied $6/9$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 43.

♂. Yellow—white—grey.

Dead and autopsied $2/9$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 44.

♂. Grey—white—brown.

Dead and autopsied $3/9$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 45.

♂. Black—white—brown.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{7}{9}$. Liver, Fig. 74. Adrenal examined on iron.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Conclusion for Series IX: In a dosage of 7 ccm., the whortleberry juice tested in Series VIII did not produce an antiscorbutic effect any more than in that series.

Series X.

Animals 46—49. Had basal diet from August 8, and besides 5 ccm. of a juice which at the beginning of the experiment was pressed from berries stirred raw, in the autumn of 1921, with the same quantity of sugar for an hour, and afterwards kept in a glazed jar, tied over with waxed paper. Weight charts, Fig. 104. These charts all show the form which appears when an animal with an acute infection is put on scurvy diet. The initial rising of the weight curve is missing.

Fig. 104. Series X. No antiscorbutic.

No. 46.

♂. Black—white—brown.

$\frac{25}{8}$ walks with difficulty; dishevelled. $\frac{29}{8}$ groaning, laborious breathing. Restless. $\frac{31}{8}$ dead. $\frac{1}{9}$ autopsied. Not very lean. A submaxillary lymph-gland forms an abscess. Right lung pneumonic, in the left lung an abscess, with a diameter of 5 mm. Three ulcerations in the large intestine. The epiphyses of the long bones easily breaking, the diaphyses not. The upper jaw brittle. Teeth loose; the upper molars are easily lifted out. Pyorrhoea around the dental sac of the upper, loosened incisors. No hemorrhages. Knee joints somewhat swollen.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. Septicemia.

No. 47.

♀. White—black—brown.

Progress and findings typically scorbutic, similar to Series V. No histological examination.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 48.

♀. White—black—yellow.

After a week less lively, grew gradually weaker and after 22 days was found one morning lying flattened underneath its fellows. *The post-mortem* examination on the same day showed multiple hemorrhages in the upper three rib interstices on the left side and around the left scapula. Fracture of one tibia in the upper epiphysis. Other epiphyses of the long bones easily broken, upper jaw brittle. Some of the teeth loose. Venous stasis in the thorax. Histological examination as in Series V. Musculature, Fig. 59.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. Infectio? Suffocatio.

No. 49.

♀. White—black.

Progress as in the preceding case. Dead $\frac{3}{9}$, autopsied the same day. Emaciated. Purulent submaxillary lymphadenitis. Fracture of one wrist, when taken out. For the rest only slightly increased fragility of the epiphyses of the long bones. Teeth loose. No hemorrhages. Hyperemia around the 5 upper anterior costochondral junctions on both sides. Lively hyperemia of the colon and its mesentery. The mucous membrane in this place swollen and reddened. Histological examination as in Series V.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. Lymphadenitis suppur. Colitis.

Conclusion for Series X. No antiscorbutic effect observed from 5 cem. of juice from red whortleberries a year old, stirred with sugar.

Fig. 105. Serier XI. No antiscorbutic.

Series XI.

Animals 50—53. Got basal diet from August 8, and besides the juice of fresh raw blue whortleberries, bought every two or three days in the market-place. Weight charts, Fig. 105. Progress, examination and findings similar to those in Series V.

No. 50.

♀. Brown—black—white.

Died and was autopsied $\frac{7}{9}$. In the seventh and eighth rib interstices

on the right side grains in the musculature of a granular, whitish yellow mass (calcium), in shape and size like a threepenny bit. Around this there were hemorrhages into the musculature. Tooth, Fig. 15, 16.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 51.

♀. Brown—white—black.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{6}{9}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 52.

♀. All white (albino).

Suffered from diarrhea during a couple of days from $\frac{1}{9}$. Died $\frac{6}{9}$, autopsied $\frac{7}{9}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 53.

♂. Greyish brown.

Died $\frac{5}{9}$, was autopsied $\frac{6}{9}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Conclusion for Series XI: No antiscorbutic effect has been observed from fresh blue whortleberry juice of the year 1922, in a dosage of 1 ccm.

Series XII.

Animals 54—57. Had basal diet from August 8, together with 5 ccm. of the juice from fresh blue whortleberries bought in the market. Weight charts, Fig. 106.

No. 54.

♀. White—black—brown.

Showed continuous emaciation and increasing difficulty of moving, till it was found $\frac{27}{9}$ flattened out beneath its fellows. The *post-mortem* examination the next day showed no hemorrhages. Swelling of the two uppermost pairs of the costochondral junctions and of the epiphyseal ends at the knees. The back molars in the lower jaw slightly loosened. Two lymph-glands in the mesentery of the large intestine somewhat swollen, lentil-sized. Venous stasis in the thorax. Histological examination of the same organs as in Series V.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. Infectio.

No. 55.

♀. White—brown—black.

Progressed to death in 35 days with typical scurvy symptoms. Dead $\frac{12}{9}$, autopsied $\frac{13}{9}$. Findings and histological examination similar to those in Series V.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. Infectio.

No. 56.

♀. Brown—black—white.

Dead $\frac{9}{9}$, autopsied $\frac{12}{9}$. Progress, findings at *post-mortem* and histological examination similar to those in Series V.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Fig. 106. Series XII. No antiscorbutic.

No. 57.

♀. Brown—black—white.

$\frac{31}{8}$ a rhinitis was observed. Dead the same day. Progress like that of Series V. At the *post-mortem* examination hundreds of small and large hemorrhages were seen in the periosteum, perinephrically, around the considerably enlarged costochondral junctions and the epiphyseal ends of the long bones which were very brittle, etc. Histological examination as in Series V. Tooth, Fig. 12 and 13.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. Rhinitis ac.

Conclusion for Series XII: No antiscorbutic effect could be stated of 5 ccm. of juice from fresh blue whortleberries of the year 1922.

Series XIII.

Animals 58—61. From August 8, they got juice from blue whortleberries, stewed for one hour in 1921 and then kept for a year in a glazed jar, tied over with waxed paper. Weight charts, Fig. 107. The animals reached the maximum weight after 23—26 days; displayed scurvy symptoms, though later than the animals in the preceding series, and died after 60, 52, 39, and 61 days, respectively.

No. 58.

♀. White—brown—black.

Dead $\frac{7}{10}$, autopsied $\frac{8}{10}$. Highly marked scurvy changes, teeth very loose, the epiphyses of the long bones very swollen and brittle, etc. At the costæ II, IV, VI, VIII sin., VI dx, about 1 cm. from the costochondral junction, lentil-sized grains of a dry whitish yellow mass (calcium) lying against the bared bone. Closer to the costochondral junction the intercostal musculature is locally swelled in several interstices, and pale. Histological examination as in Series V. Tooth, Fig. 8; muscle, Fig. 56, 58; spleen, Fig. 81. Spleen also stained on iron, amyloid, and according to Giemsa. Staining on iron also of knees and ribs.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

No. 59.

♂. White—yellow—black.

In dying condition killed with ether $29/9$. Autopsied immediately. Progress and findings very like No. 58. Around the enlarged costochondral junctions in the fifth to eighth interstices on the right side, the intercostal musculature was found to be swelled into exorbitant, pale greyish-pink masses, which to the width of about 1 mm. filled the space between the ribs. Histological examination as in No. 58.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

No. 60.

♀. White—yellow—black.

Progress, findings and histological examination similar to the two preceding numbers. Died $18/9$, autopsied $17/9$. Lymphoglandula submentalalis forms a pea-sized abscess. Around the sixth and seventh ribs on the right, fourth to eighth on the left side, enlargements similar to those described above lying in the intercostal musculature below the fascia, here they look like processes from the boundary line.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior. Lymphadenit. ac. purulenta submental.

No. 61.

♂. Grey—brown.

Dead $4/10$, autopsied $5/10$. Progress and findings similar to No. 58. Around the seven upper ribs on both sides, near the costochondral junctions, enlargements in the intercostal musculature looking like young connective tissue. No histological examination undertaken.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

Conclusion for Series XIII: The juice of blue whortleberry compote, a year old, in a dosage of 5 ccm. has proved to be of a certain antiscorbutic value (0.1 m. pr. d.).

Fig. 107. Series XIII. 0.1 m. pr. d.

Series XIV.

Animals 62—66. Got basal diet together with 10 ccm. of the same blue whortleberry juice as the animals in Series XIII; No. 62—65 from August 8, No. 66 from August 25. Weight charts, Fig. 108.

No. 62.

♂. Black—brown—white.

Got lean without showing signs of scurvy. Was found dead $18/8$, flattened out beneath its fellows, and was autopsied the same day. At the *post-mortem* examination there was no sign of scurvy or infection. Histological examination of teeth.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Infectio?

Fig. 108. Series XIV. 0.2 m. pr. d.

No. 63.

♀. Grey.

$25/8$ not very lively, dishevelled and dry. $26/8$ lymphogland. submental. as big as a good-sized pea, $27/8$ as a bean. Operated $27/8$ (ethyl chlorid): an attempt to extirpate the purulent gland entire did not succeed. Tamponade. $28/8$ improved; eats; walks about. $31/8$ lively. $3/9$ joints not swollen or tender. $6/9$ dead and autopsied. From the operation aperture upwards to the bottom of the mouth an abscess cavity, the size of an almond. Macroscopically the back molars in the lower jaw were found rather loose. Histological examination as in Series V shows marked scorbutic pictures. Musculature, Fig. 60.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Lymphadenitis submental. suppur.

No. 64.

♀. Brown—white.

Died already $^{12}/_8$, flattened against the floor. *Post-mortem* examination the same day showed a row of purulent lymph-glands on both sides of the neck. The mucous membrane in the larynx reddened. Histological examination of the same organs as in Series V, and besides of lungs.

Diagnosis: Scorbut initialis. Lymphadenit. supp. colli.

No. 65.

♀. Grey.

$^{25}/_8$ not very lively, coat dishevelled. $^{8}/_9$ the upper epiphyses of tibiae swollen, tender. Walks slowly and awkwardly. $^{8}/_{10}$ dead and autopsied: no sign of infection. Very strongly marked scurvy changes, hemorrhages around all ribs, knees and ankles; loose teeth, brittle bones, swollen joints and costochondral junctions etc. Histological examination as in Series V.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

No. 66.

♀. Brown—white—black.

Showed hardly distinct scurvy symptoms (a slight swelling of the knees) before death $^{20}/_9$. The *post-mortem* examination the same day showed small hemorrhages on the patellæ and in a couple of rib interstices, slightly swollen knees, rather strong enlargement of the costochondral junctions with the white line; teeth firm. Besides, sign of infection of the upper respiratory canal and bronchopneumonia. Histological examination as in Series V and also of lungs and different lymph-glands.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior. Bronchopneumoniae ac.

Conclusion for Series XIV: The slight degree of scurvy shown by No. 63, is remarkable. The juice of stewed blue whortleberries from 1921 has in this case, as well as in No. 66, had a certain antiscorbutic effect.

Series XV.

Animals 67—70. From August 8 basal diet together with a daily dose each of 5 ccm. of wood-strawberry juice. The first three weeks this juice was pressed from fresh strawberries, afterwards from berries that had been stirred early in August for one hour together with the same quantity of sugar, and had been kept in a glazed jar tied over with waxed paper. Already before three weeks had gone, the animals had become less lively. Soon after they developed distinct scurvy symptoms. Weight charts, Fig. 109.

No. 67.

♀. White—brown—black.

Dead $^{19}/_9$, autopsied $^{20}/_9$. Findings and histological examination similar to those in Series V. Eechymoses in the mucous membrane of the ventricle. At the ribs II sin. and IV—VI bilat., around the costochondral junctions there are seen rounded or cuneiform swellings of the intercostal musculature. Jaw, Fig. 33.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

No. 68.

♀. White—black—brown.

Dead and autopsied $^{23}/_9$. Progress, findings and histological examination as in No. 67. The change described around the costochondral junctions

is only seen around rib VI dx. No hemorrhages in internal organs. Spleen also stained according to Giemsa. Radiograms of the ribs, Fig. 42, a.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

No. 69.

♀. Yellow—grey.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{27}{10}$. Progress, findings and histological examination very similar to No. 63. Ribs, Fig. 41.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

Fig. 109. Series XV. 0.1 m. pr. d.

No. 70.

♀. Black—white—brown.

$\frac{25}{8}$ less lively. $\frac{12}{10}$ knees swollen. $\frac{20}{10}$ knees very swollen and tender. Dead and autopsied $\frac{2}{10}$. Hemorrhages around nearly all ribs, knees, elbows, subpleurally on both lungs; knees so brittle that they break into small pieces when taken out. No swelling of the intercostal musculature. Teeth easily lifted out, etc. Histological examination as in Series V.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

Conclusion for Series XV: The juice of wood-strawberries from the year 1922 has shown a certain antiscorbutic effect.

Series XVI.

Animals 71—74. From August 25, basal diet and besides a daily dose each of 5 ccm. of fir needle decoction (see p. 24). Weight charts, Fig. 110. Progress, findings and histological examination similar to Series V, yet a smaller number of bones have been examined.

No. 71.

♂. Black—brown—white.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{28}{10}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 72.

♀. Brown—grey—white.

Dead $^{26}/_9$, autopsied $^{37}/_9$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 73.

♂. White—black—brown.

Dead and autopsied $^{25}/_9$. Liver, Fig. 77. Also staining on iron of liver and spleen; spleen likewise on amyloid and, as also the marrow of the ribs, according to Giemsa.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Fig. 110. Series XVI. No antiscorbutic.

No. 74.

♂. Brown—white—black.

Dead $^{24}/_9$, autopsied $^{25}/_9$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Conclusion for Series XVI: The fir needle decoction in a dosage of 5 ccm. has shown no antiscorbutic effect.

Series XVII.

Animals 75—78. They got, from October 4 to October 29, a daily dose each of 1 ccm. of fresh juice from somewhat dry oranges; October 29 to November 18, 8 ccm. of preserved orange juice, after November 18 again fresh juice, now from juicy oranges (see p. 26). Weight charts, Fig. 111. After October 29, the weight of all the animals went down within a week. On November 18, they all showed pronounced signs of scurvy, which were more strongly marked in No. 75 than in the rest. This animal died $^{10}/_{11}$, whereas the others after a few days again seemed lively.

No. 75.

♂. Yellow—white—black.

Dead and autopsied ¹⁹/₁₁. Hemorrhages around a number of ribs. The costochondral junctions enlarged, except those of the lowest pairs. Pale connective-tissue formations around several ribs, most pronounced around VI dx. Teeth loose, except the anterior upper molars. Histological examination as in Series V. Teeth and ribs also stained according to Hansen, the ribs besides with Weigert's fibrin stain and on iron. Tooth, Fig. 18; ribs, Fig. 45, Plate II.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

Fig. 111. Series XVII. Varied antiscorbutic dose.

No. 76.

♂. White—light brown—grey.

Chloroformed ¹¹/₁₂ and autopsied the same day. Macroscopically no sign of scurvy. Histological examination as in No. 75. Tooth, Fig. 19, 20; ribs Fig. 46 a, Plate I.

Diagnosis: Healing scurvy.

No. 77.

♂. White—black—yellow.

Progress, findings and examination as in No. 76. Incisors rather brittle. Ribs, Fig. 46 b; musculature, Fig. 63, 64.

Diagnosis: Healing scurvy.

No. 78.

♂. White (albino).

Progress, findings and examination as in No. 76, but incisors somewhat loose. Tooth, Fig. 21.

Diagnosis: Healing scurvy.

Conclusion for Series XVII: No more than other products of the vegetable kingdom, oranges can be said to exercise a constant antiscorbutic effect. The antiscorbutic value evidently may vary.

Series XVIII.

Animals 76—82, They got a modified basal diet from October 12, the cod-liver oil being excluded. With this basal diet the animals had fresh orange juice, No. 79 and 80 2 ccm., No. 81 and 82 4 ccm. From October 29 to November 18, they had instead of the fresh juice 8 ccm. of preserved juice as in Series XVII. The two first animals died during this time, 30 and 19 days, respectively, after the starting of the experiment, of acute infections. After November 18, the two others again had fresh juice, in a dose of 4 ccm. Weight charts, Fig. 112.

Fig. 112. Series XVIII. Varied antiscorbutic dose.

No. 79.

♀. Black—white—brown.

Dead $^{11}/_{11}$, autopsied $^{12}/_{11}$. Abdomen considerably swollen. Intestine highly distended by gas. In the abdominal cavity some ccm. of turbid fluid. Peritoneum viscerale et parietale rose-coloured. Neither clinically nor at the *post-mortem* examination any scorbutic symptoms are seen, no more at the histological examination, undertaken as in Series V, except in the teeth.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Peritonitis diffusa.

No. 80.

♂. White—yellow—black.

Dead $^1/_{11}$, autopsied $^5/_{11}$. Altogether parallel with No. 79, the only

difference being that No. 80 has normal abdomen, a pneumonic right lung and cellular infiltration in the tongue musculature.

Diagnosis: Scorbut latens levior; glossitis; pneumonia ac.

No. 81.

♂. Grey—yellow—white.

Towards the end of the period when preserved juice was given, the animal decreased in weight and in liveliness. Grew livelier after the supply of fresh juice, but continued losing in weight. Chloroformed ¹¹/₁₂; autopsied ¹⁴/₁₂. Very lean but otherwise normal. No sign of infection, nor of scurvy. At the histological examination as in Series V, nothing was seen that recalled scurvy, except in the ribs. The odontoblast layer of the teeth completely in order. The dentin showed unequally bright strata, with uneven edge inwards; Tomes' canals somewhat widened. The epiphyses of the long bones without remark, except those of the ribs. Here the cartilage columns are short, the bone deposit sparse, in some places a bone plate is seen stretching transversely along the end of the cartilage.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 82.

♂. Yellow—white—black.

The same progress and findings as in No. 81.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

Conclusion for Series XVIII: The animals have for 30, 19, 60 and 60 days suffered from the want of A-vitamin. The first two animals that had an insufficient dose of antiscorbutic during the period immediately before death, showed scurvy changes in teeth, but normal picture of rib epiphyses. No. 81 and 82, on the other hand, showed certain changes in the teeth. These may be partly associated with the want of C-vitamin from which also these animals suffered for some time, and partly perhaps with the want of A-vitamin. The changes in the rib epiphyses resemble those found by DELF and TOZER with lack of A-vitamin in the food of guinea-pigs. The earlier period, during which the C-vitamin was insufficient, necessitates a certain caution in deciding the question about the cause of these rib changes.

Series XIX.

Animals 83—86. Got 3 ccm. of fresh tomato juice (see p. 25) from October 8. Weight charts, Fig. 113. After two weeks all the animals had reached the maximum weight, grew more quiet, and their coats became rough. Somewhat later the knees were swollen and tender. Died after 39 to 43 days. At the *post-mortem* examination which was undertaken immediately or one to two days after death, they all showed the typical picture of acute scurvy, with hemorrhages in numerous muscles, loose teeth that are easily removed, swollen joints, very brittle epiphyses. No. 83 and 86 showed the above-described connective-tissue formations in the upper six rib interstices around the costochondral junctions. Histological examination as in Series V.

No. 83.

♂. White—black.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

No. 84.

♂. White—black—brown.

Liver, Fig. 75.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

No. 85.

♂. White—black—light brown.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

Fig. 113. Series XIX. 0.1 m. pr. d.

No. 86.

♂. White—light brown—black.

Liver, Fig. 76, 78. Liver also stained on iron.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

Conclusion for Series XIX: 3 cem. of fresh juice from late-ripened tomatoes have shown a very inconsiderable antiscorbutic effect.

Series XX.

Animals 87—90. From October 4 they got, besides cereal and bran, unboiled milk, together 200 cem., which they consumed.¹ After two weeks the animals grew quiet, reached the maximum weight after 19—23 days and soon showed swollen, tender joints, scurvy position of the hind-legs etc. Weight charts, Fig. 114.

No. 87.

♀. White—black—light brown.

Dead ¹⁰/₁₁, autopsied ¹²/₁₁. Hemorrhages around the costochondral junctions of the upper five pairs of ribs, which are all enlarged, and around

¹ The milk had been heated at 66° C. for 20 minutes and was given to the animals 24 hours later.

the swollen knees. Along the caudal edge of the fifth, right rib a connective-tissue formation obliquely backwards from the costochondral junction. Teeth loose. Epiphyses fragile. Lymph-glands on the neck swollen.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior. Infectio ac.

No. 88.

♀. White—light brown—black.

Dead $\frac{2}{12}$, autopsied $\frac{4}{12}$. Changes similar to No. 87, but quantitatively more developed. Hemorrhages exceedingly numerous; epiphyses very brittle. Pale masses of connective tissue (Fig. 55, 61) fill up the 1st — 7th interstices on both sides between the costochondral junctions, which are swollen. Ribs stained with Weigert's fibrin stain, and besides, as also knees, spleen and liver, on iron. Jaw, Fig. 10, 11.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

Fig. 114. Series XX. 0.1 m. pr. d.

No. 89.

♀. Black—light brown—white.

Dead $\frac{10}{11}$, autopsied $\frac{12}{11}$. Progress and findings as in No. 87.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

No. 90.

♀. White—light brown—black.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{19}{11}$. A submaxillary lymph-gland forms a large abscess. Infectious spleen. Hemorrhages around the swollen knees and the enlarged costochondral junctions. Round these on the left side from the 4th to the 7th rib, swellings of the intercostal musculature, as described above. Histological examination as in Series V.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior; lymphadenitis suppur. submaxillar.

Conclusion for Series XX: In this series, where the animals have been able to consume at pleasure the substance which was to be tested, the lifetime has varied considerably. It is indicated that about 100 cem. of

milk are necessary for complete protection. The antiscorbutic value of milk, however, is highly variable, and the milk given in this experiment seems to have been relatively deficient in this respect.

Series XXI.

Animals 91, born $^{19}/_9$ of No. 33, and 92, born $^{7}/_{10}$ of No. 14. They got basal diet from October 28, and besides 5 ccm. of raspberry juice, bought at a pharmaceutical chemist's as »syrupus Rubi idaei 1922». The animals progressed as cases of absolute scurvy, with maximum weight after 15 and 18 days, to death in 28 and 27 days. Weight charts for Series XXI and XXII, Fig. 115.

Fig. 115. Series XXI—XXII. No antiscorbutic.

No. 91.

♀. Light brown—black.

Dead $^{28}/_{11}$, autopsied $^{27}/_{11}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 92.

♀. White—black—light brown.

Dead $^{24}/_{11}$, autopsied $^{27}/_{11}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

Conclusion for Series XXI: The preparation called raspberry juice has in two cases shown no antiscorbutic effect.

Series XXII.

Animals 93, born $\frac{9}{9}$ of No. 33, and 94, born $\frac{7}{10}$ of No. 14. They got from October 28 basal diet and besides 5 ccm. of black currant juice from the same pharmaceutical chemistry as the juice in Series XXI. No. 93 progressed as a case of absolute scurvy, with maximum weight after 19 days, to death in 37 days. Histological examination as in Series V. No. 94 died after six days $\frac{3}{11}$; the cause of death could not be established (overlying?)

No. 93.

♂. Light brown—black.

Dead $\frac{3}{12}$, autopsied $\frac{4}{12}$.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 94.

♀. White—black.

Dead $\frac{3}{7}$, autopsied $\frac{5}{11}$. The animal had been flattened against the floor of the cage by its fellows. Nothing pathological found in different organs except what was due to this circumstance.

Diagnosis: Scorbut latens gravior. Causa mortis incerta.

Conclusion for Series XXII: The preparation called black currant juice has in one case shown no antiscorbutic effect.

Series XXIII.

Animals 95 and 96. Healthy animals, which both at the first feeding with the red whortleberry juice given in Series 4 blew it out through the nose; all their muscles relaxed and they died, one after having staggered a few steps in the cage, the other almost immediately in the hand. The feeding was not managed slowly enough. The abdomen became rapidly and strongly distended, which at the post-mortem was shown to have been caused by the ventricle being filled with gas. Microscopical examination as in Series I.

No. 95.

♀. White (albino).

Dead and autopsied $\frac{2}{8}$.

Diagnosis: Reflex death?

No. 96.

♀. White—black.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{2}{8}$. Ribs, Fig. 36.

Diagnosis: Reflex death?

Records belonging to Part II, Chapter I.**Extracts.****Case I.**

Karl Albin P-n, No. 11181.

From the Hospital record: Born $\frac{6}{7}$ 1896, admitted that day.

Clinical diagnosis: $\frac{6}{7}$ 1896 conjunctivitis catarrhalis + macroglossia; $\frac{8}{9}$ icterus neonatorum; $\frac{18}{7}$ mastitis; $\frac{20}{8}$ lues suspecta; $\frac{9}{9}$ eczema faciei; $\frac{6}{11}$ gastroenterocolitis ac. + otitis med. pur.; $\frac{17}{11}$ erysipelas capitis; $\frac{22}{11}$ bronchitis bilat. ac. + otorrhoea bilat.; $\frac{24}{12}$ abscessus capitis; 1897, January: atrophía; bronchitis; $\frac{8}{2}$ morbus Barlow; $\frac{16}{3}$ mors.

Breast-fed for nearly 2 months. Then the weaning was begun and completed in 2 weeks; after that milk mixtures.

The weight increased steadily, from 3,600 grams at the birth on $\frac{6}{7}$ to 5,600 at the age of 3 months (then, $\frac{8}{10}$, dyspepsia). Then it sank uninterruptedly to 4,200 grams on $\frac{17}{12}$, and after that date rose again irregularly; during the last weeks it sank from 5,200 to 4,600 grams.

Daily records: $\frac{24}{10}$ nose-bleed; $\frac{22}{1}$ meatus audit. filled with bloody secretion; $\frac{28}{1}$ bloody discharge from nose; $\frac{29}{1}$ the gingiva over the incisors in the upper jaw imbibed with blood and swollen over each tooth not yet cut. $\frac{30}{1}$ Abundant discharge from the right ear of bloody secretion like that from the nose. $\frac{6}{2}$ Considerable edema in both legs. Bloody discharge from nose and left ear. Liver rather hard, reaches the navel plane; spleen reaches the front axillary line. Percussion area of heart from 1 cm to the left of the mammillary line to the middle of sternum. $\frac{8}{2}$ Lower parts of tibiae and fibulae considerably swelled and tender. $\frac{18}{2}$ Right thigh diffusely swollen. Complete immobility of both legs. No swelling of the arms which he moves a little, but slowly. Temp. about $37,5^{\circ}$ C. $\frac{22}{2}$ Hemorrhage on the left upper lid. $\frac{4}{3}$ Periosteal swellings, most pronounced in the lower part of the right femur, the upper and lower parts of the right fibula and tibia and the lower ends of the left fibula and tibia. $\frac{16}{3}$ Died with lung symptoms.

Post-mortem on $\frac{16}{3}$. *Patho-anatomical diagnosis:* Haemorrhagiae subperiostales, intramusculares et pulmonum + pneumonia ac. bilateralis + pachymeningitis haemorrhag. interna + hyperplasia lienis + otit. med. purul. sin.

From the post-mortem record: General complexion pale. In the tela subcutanea on the lower part of the left leg and foot a quite considerable edema. Ribs somewhat enlarged at costochondral junctions. At incision no sign of rickets is found. *Right thigh:* The musculature close to femur strongly infiltrated with blood and dark red. Periosteum raised all round by a layer of partly clotted blood, 1–5 mm. thick. Thus, a subperiosteal hemorrhage extends from the upper to the lower epiphysis. Both epiphyses had become loosened from the diaphyses. In the *right leg* mainly the same picture with fractures of both epiphyseal ends in *tibia* as well as *fibula*. A similar picture in the left thigh and leg; epiphyseal fracture is absent only in the upper part of the left fibula.

On the right and left side slight periosteal hemorrhage in *ulna* and *radius*. Joints and epiphyseal cartilages everywhere normal without any sign of rickets.

Lungs: The left upper lobe shows numerous miliary, dark red hemorrhages. Pneumonia in the whole of the left upper lobe and in smaller areas of the right upper lobe.

Liver: Slight fatty infiltration.

Microscopical examination: Left femur, lower epiphyseal line and the upper limit of right tibia display a marked picture of scurvy with low cartilage columns, »Gerüstmark» and »Trümmerfeldzone». (Detail Fig. 49 a). In the »Fugenwinkel» there is inferior bone in splinters (Fig. 49 b) and in bone columns higher up in the marrow homogeneous places (Fig. 49 c).

Epicrisis: Case of infantile scurvy, having displayed definite clinical changes in the seventh month and died of lung complication less than 2 months later. No rickets.

Case 2.

Gösta Reinhold Emanuel V.g, No. 11271.

From the Hospital record: Born $^{20}/_9$ 1896. Admitted $^9/_{10}$ 1896.

Clinical diagnosis: $^8/_{20}$ intertrigo, bronchitis: $^{31}/_{12}$ otorrhoea; $^{25}/_1$ 1897 abscessus retroaur. sin.; $^1/_4$ bronchitis; $^{28}/_4$ lymphadenitis; $^{28}/_4$ otit. med. pur.; $^{26}/_4$ pneumonia ac. dx.; $^{10}/_5$ excema capitis, $^{28}/_6$ bronchitis; $^{28}/_{10}$ rachitis; $^{11}/_{11}$ periostitis + perichondritis humeri et femoris; $^{19}/_{11}$ enterocolitis ac.; $^{22}/_{11}$ mors.

The infant was entirely breast-fed the first two months; from 4 months fed solely on cow's milk.

The weight increased for 5 months, till 5,700 grams. Loss in weight afterwards 1 kg. during 4 months; then again increase, $1\frac{1}{2}$ kg. in 3 months till 6,500 grams a month before death.

Daily records: $^{12}/_4$ (six months old): Craniotabes + rosary. $^{20}/_6$ Mellin's food, 8 tea-spoonfuls; $^{28}/_{10}$ very strongly developed rosary. Epiphyseal junctions of ankles and wrists enlarged. Occipital suture somewhat soft; $^1/_{11}$ tenderness of body. Crying out whenever turned over from dorsal position. Looks poorly and eats little; $^{11}/_{11}$ complexion dull, pale grey. Always lying on his back with his arms extended down his sides and his legs turned outwards, slightly bent in the hip-joints. Thighs somewhat swollen. At the slightest touching of the extremities and when moving passively, the patient moans a great deal; $^{12}/_{11}$ left arm from acromion down towards joint heavily swollen; considerable tenderness. $^{18}/_{11}$ quiet and still when left alone. The left forearm swollen at the epiphyseal junction above the wrist; tenderness. As the symptoms from the bone system increased, the patient grew steadily worse and died $^{22}/_{11}$, 14 months old. *Post-mortem* the same day.

Patho-anatomical diagnosis: Hemorrhagiæ subperiostales (morbus Barlow) + enterocolit. follicular. ac. + otit. med. bilat. + lymphadenit. chron. gland. mesenteric. + pachymeningit. hemorrh. interna + rachitis.

From the *post-mortem* record: Dura mater, of ordinary thickness, shows on the inside in patches a thin, mostly yellowish brown, sometimes pale, easily loosened membrane. In the lower lobe of the left lung immediately below the pleura dispersed miliary hemorrhages. Heart at ordinary size. Musculature pale. Spleen somewhat enlarged; Malpighian corpuscles somewhat enlarged. In large portions of colon transversum the solitary follicles, which are not swelled, are found to be of a dark red blood colour, darkest in the centre, lighter in the periphery. Between these portions there are others where the follicles generally are somewhat swelled, pale, and only some few show hemorrhages like those described above.

The left brachium swollen. Musculature in the upper half discoloured, pale yellowish or yellowish brown. Periosteum on left humerus loosened by a hemorrhage. The left upper humeral epiphysis separated from the diaphysis; a layer of yellow-tinged tissue, about 2 mm. thick, sticks to the epiphysis. The right femur only shows a somewhat looser connection between epiphysis and diaphysis in the upper part, while the left femur and right humerus show pictures similar to those of the left humerus (muscle discolouring, fracture of the diaphysis close to the upper epiphysis, subperiosteal hemorrhage). Hemorrhage like this is also seen on ulna and radius of both sides.

The ribs are considerably enlarged everywhere at the junction between cartilage and bone. At incision the cartilage proliferation zone is found to be a great deal wider than normally, generally 3—4 mm. wide. The calcification zone is exceedingly irregular. Adjoining this there is a yellowish

zone about 1 mm. wide of a soft tissue in which the bone is loosened from the cartilage. Under the periosteum, which evidently is slightly raised, a thin layer of dark red, not clotted blood extends 1—2 cm. from the junction of the cartilage and bone.

Microscopical examination. Cut sections were made of the lower left femoral epiphysis and a large number of ribs, *not decalcified*; the specimens were treated according to v. RECKLINGHAUSEN with carmalum and aluminated glycerin.

Left femur: The epiphysis has narrow bone columns, in the large majority normal injection. *In certain columns only the corpuscles injected, without canals.* In another series next to the epiphysis are seen 1) narrow columns with complete injection, 2) colourless columns with injection of corpuscles, but no canals, 3) colourless columns without any trace of injection, and 4) some few red-coloured columns without injection. In the marrow sparse cells and hemorrhages. (Note: When staining sections from the same place with hematoxylin and carmin, the majority of the columns are found to become blue-coloured, only a few tender columns red-coloured, in this manner proving that the bone columns are preavailingly calciferous, and only exceptionally osteoid.)

Rib. 1, not decalcified, treated according to v. Recklinghausen. In the parts next to the cartilage the bone columns are colourless, glossy, and there are no injected corpuscles or canaliculi to be seen in them, or else only small corpuscles without canaliculi. Farther away from the cartilage, however, injection of the bone column is found, in some places throughout the column, in other places there is injection in the central parts but round those a narrow zone, uncoloured and glossy, without injection of corpuscles or only of small, dwarfed ones without canaliculi. Other sections from the same rib show: 1) Next to the cartilage a narrow zone, in which there are numerous tender columns of a red-coloured tissue, which in some places seems to be quite homogeneous (remaining rests of the hyaline middle substance of the cartilage), but for the most part shows a structure of osteoid tissue *without* injection of corpuscles. In places there is in the centre a more deeply red-coloured tissue of hyaline nature and outside this a narrow zone of osteoid tissue (rest of hyaline cartilage surrounded by osteoid tissue). All these columns lie irregularly scattered, not parallel with the longitudinal axis of the bone. The bone marrow in this zone is fairly abundant in cells, and there have been both fresh and earlier hemorrhages. 2) Then a zone, in which the bone columns are very tender, not coloured, evidently calcified, but without injection of corpuscles. 3) Then again a zone with distinct injection of the bone canals.

Rib. 2. a. Cut section, hematoxylin-carmin.

The cartilage proliferation zone wider than normally. The calcification zone is narrow, and not seen in the most peripheral parts. Next to this is a zone of numerous small detached pieces of calcified cartilage tissue together with some columns of osteoid tissue (red-coloured) and some of calcified bone tissue (blue-coloured).

b. not decalcified, treated according to v. Recklinghausen.

In the zone next to the cartilage, scattered narrow, glossy columns, which are uncoloured and do not show any injection with carbon dioxid, or only of a few corpuscles without canaliculi. This zone evidently extends higher on the outward surface than on the pleural side.

Epicrisis. Case of infantile scurvy, dying at the age of 14 months, having displayed definite clinical symptoms during the last months. Rickets.

Case 3.

Fredrik Albert, born $\frac{9}{12}$ 1896. Admitted $\frac{9}{12}$ 1896.

The weaning began $\frac{1}{2}$ and was completed within 2 months. From $\frac{16}{2}$ Mellin's food was administered, 3 tea-spoonfuls, from $\frac{10}{5}$ raised to 8 tea-spoonfuls. The weight increased during the first 4 months to 5,000 grams but afterwards kept to about 5 kg. (4.6—5.4) until death at the age of 10 months.

Clinical diagnosis: $\frac{28}{12}$. 96 conjunctivitis catarrh. + dyspepsia; $\frac{1}{2}$. 97 otitis; $\frac{29}{8}$ bronchitis; $\frac{10}{5}$ gastroenteritis; $\frac{18}{6}$ otitis; $\frac{28}{8}$ pneumonia ac. sin.; $\frac{6}{10}$ pneumonia ac. sin.; $\frac{7}{10}$ mors.

The daily records have not been found. The clinical diagnosis was: pneumonia ac. + septicemia.

Post-mortem examination on $\frac{9}{10}$.

Patho-anatomical diagnosis: Pneumonia ac. bilat. + splenitis ac. levis + nephritis ac. parenchym. levis + colit. follicular. chron. et ac. + *hemorrhagia subperiostal. femor. ambor.* + otit. med. bilat.

From the post-mortem record: »The corpse is pale. In the upper side of the feet rather profuse edema. Both thighs quite considerably swollen. Musculature in the outer layers of pale flesh-colour, in the deeper ones discoloured, pale grey-red or of a dirty yellow, always having a gelatinous, transparent look. In a few small places in the musculature are seen slight hemorrhages. The periosteum on both sides raised from femur by a layer of blood, 1--5 cm. thick.» —

Microscopical examination. Series of sections from left femur, both from the two epiphysis ends and from different parts of the diaphysis. Staining: htx-eosin, htx-carmin and v. Gieson. Cut sections from the same places, prepared according to v. Recklinghausen.

By way of example some of the sections from the upper epiphysis end are here described.

1. Cut section, carmalum (v. R.).

Tender bone columns, the large majority showing complete injection. In a smaller number, incomplete or hardly any injection in the uncoloured columns. Some few columns are red-coloured and at the same time without injection (osteoid).

2. Cut section, same treatment.

Tender bone columns, generally showing injected bone corpuscles and bone canals throughout the column, but nearer the epiphysis not all the columns are found to be injected; sometimes merely scattered black corpuscles without canaliculi; sometimes a centre which is normal and outside that a narrow zone of white glossy colour *without* injected corpuscles.

3. Detail of section showing (Fig. 50) an old bone bridge, on the epiphyseal end of which there is an abundant layer of homogeneous, eosinophile bone, reaching the cartilage.

The sections in the upper, lower and middle parts of the left thigh show everywhere an exceedingly strong atrophy of the muscular fibres (Fig. 65 a and b).

Epicrisis. A 10 months' child, who since the age of 4 months was entirely fed on milk mixtures and during all this time has kept the same weight and in whom the *post-mortem* examination revealed pronounced scurvy.

Case 4.

Judit Teresia L-l., born $\frac{8}{6}$ 1899.

Admitted $\frac{10}{6}$ 1899.

Clinical diagnosis: $\frac{31}{8}$ Lues hereditaria; $\frac{8}{11}$ ulcus frenul. linguae; $\frac{13}{11}$ bronchitis; died $\frac{15}{11}$ 1899.

Was from her birth fed with cow's milk mixtures. Was given milk powder from $\frac{15}{8}$. Gained weight slowly from 2,920 grams on the day of admittance to 3,790 at 3 months, afterwards went down to 3,380 the day before her death, at the age of 5 months.

Treated with Hg per os after $\frac{1}{9}$.

The first of the daily records which is indicative of scurvy is of $\frac{14}{11}$ (the day before death) and says: Swellings on the thighs. The soft parts are firm to the touch and infiltrated. Swellings on the upper side of both feet. Eats very little, fretful and whimpering.

Died $\frac{15}{11}$, *post-mortem* examination $\frac{18}{11}$.

Patho-anatomical diagnosis: Hemorrhagiæ subperiostales (morbus Barlow) + pneumonia lobularis dx. + hyperplasia lienis.

Extracts from the post-mortem record: On the left thigh the musculature (mostly cruralis, but also vastus ext. et int.) is discoloured, of a greyish yellow, sometimes a little yellowish brown, and also shows small freshly occurred hemorrhages. Round the whole femur below the periosteum a layer of clotted blood, 1-3 mm. thick.

The lower right femoral epiphysis shows the cartilage proliferation zone about 2 mm. wide; the calcification zone is just above 1 mm. wide, greyish yellow, generally straight, but in some places uneven. The bone marrow next to this zone is changed into a dark red and muddy pulp.

Around the lower ends of both tibiæ and the right radius subperiosteal hemorrhages. The upper epiphyseal line of tibia is similar to the lower one of femur.

The ribs show on the pleural side, both at the posterior and anterior epiphyseal junctions, fresh hemorrhages below the periosteum. On the section at the junction of cartilage and bone, the cartilage proliferation zone is now 1 mm., now $\frac{1}{2}$ mm. wide, yellowish, on the whole even towards the cartilage but with small notches.

Microscopical examination. Staining: hematoxylin-eosin, alum. hematoxylin — v. Gieson, of the two femores, tibiæ and fibulæ, as well at the upper and lower epiphyseal lines as in the middle of the diaphysis; also the anterior and posterior epiphyseal junctions of two ribs.

The upper end of left femur: frame-work marrow 1 mm. high. Inferior bone covers the old bone bridges in the »Trümmerfeldzone». It shows bone canals but hardly any other structure.

The upper end of left fibula: no cartilage trabeculæ, the bone formation seems altogether arrested. In the musculature, which is highly atrophic, pictures of regeneration.

Ribs, posterior end: The bone columns, which are lying across in the frame-work marrow of 3 mm. width, are joined to the cartilage through a system of columns of more homogeneous bone. Round all the bone columns a thin zone of red tissue (osteoid) and spool-shaped osteoblasts (Fig. 5). In the »Fugenwinkel» hyaline bulky bone.

Epicrisis. Scurvy in a child of 5 months (the mother syphilitic), from the birth fed first with cow's milk mixtures and then with milk powder.

Records, belonging to Part IV, Chapter II.

Extracts.

Series XXIV.

Animals 97—103, 183, control animals on complete dietary. Weight charts, Fig. 116. No. 97 died of an acute infection, the others were chloroformed after 105 days, July 3rd, and autopsied immediately. Histological examination as in Series V.

No. 97.

♀. Light brown—black.

Increased during 50 days normally, then decreased during 5, with symptoms of panting respiration. Died $\frac{11}{5}$ 23. Autopsied $\frac{12}{5}$. Histological examination as in Series V, and of lungs, shows an infection spleen, numerous foci in the lungs, where the alveoli are filled out with red blood-corpuscles, mono- and polynucleate cells.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Bronchopneumonia ac.

No. 98.

♂. White (albino).

Showed during some weeks in May a hairless spot on the back, big as a sixpenny piece, which healed spontaneously.

Liver 27.5 grams. Spleen 1.2 gram.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

Fig. 116. Series XXIV. Complete dietary.

No. 99.

♀. Brown—white—black.

Showed at the *post-mortem* 3 feti, 3 cm. from vertex to coccyx, two in the right uterine horn, one in the left.

Liver 28.2 grams, spleen 0.75 gram.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 100.

♀. Brown—white—black.

Liver 31.3 grams, spleen 1.1 gram.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 101.

♂. White—brown—black.

After an unsatisfactory increase in weight during a month, it was noted $23/5$, that the animal showed a tendency of sinistrotflexion of the head. This symptom disappeared again after two weeks. In the beginning of May the animal also had a hairless spot on one flank which healed spontaneously after a short time. Liver 25.1 grams, spleen 1 gram. Histologically normal picture. Kidneys not examined.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 102.

♂. Black—light brown—white.

Showed at the end of May during a short time a hairless spot on the trunk, healing spontaneously.

Liver 31.1 grams, spleen 1 gram.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 103.

♀. White—light brown—black.

Liver 27 grams, spleen 1.1 gram.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 183: see p. 232.

Conclusion for Series XXIV: Of 8 animals that were given complete dietary, one died of pneumonia, the others lived till they were killed at the conclusion of the experiment, or more than 3 months. Neither clinically, nor at the *post-mortem* or the histological examination any sign of scurvy could be discovered.

Series XXV.

Animals 104—111. Had complete dietary of oats and bran, unboiled milk, and swedes *ad lib.* from March 20. Infected March 29 with tubercle bacilli (see p. 151). Weight charts, Fig. 117.

No. 104.

♂. White—yellow.

Chloroformed $30/6$, autopsied the same day. Strong, fat animal. Hair firmly fixed. No sign of scurvy. In the adductors of the right thigh a cavity, less than almond-sized, with uneven, hard-rinded walls several mms. thick, containing a turbid liquid with necrotic strips. Lphgl. ing. dx., big as a brown bean, shows a miliary abscess cavity surrounded by a distinct capsule, $1/2$ mm. thick, with columns that penetrate into the cavity. In other lymphglands a homogeneous swelling. Spleen 1.7 gram. Liver 38.2 grams. Histological examination according to Series V shows no sign of scurvy. *Liver:* Foci and strands of granulation tissue, of epitheloid cells, fibroblasts, lymphocytes and other round cells, young liver cell columns. In this tissue there are seen Langhans' giant cells and tubercle bacilli at intervals. From some vessels strong strands of connective tissue. Hardly any fat. In the *spleen* large areas where only reticular cells are seen. Numerous giant cells of Langhans' type and others; fibroblasts very few. In the lphgl. submax. there are small foci of epitheloid cells and giant cells, some of Langhans' type, some more irregular, and tubercle bacilli. Section through the primary focus shows necroses farthest in. Outside these a wide layer of connective tissue, at intervals a Langhans' giant cell and numerous calcium lumps; also the protoplasm of the giant cells is calcified. This connective tissue is arranged as a capsule around necroses and shows strong collagen fibrils. In a lymphgland lying

next to the focus, the centre shows a necrotic focus where inside almost every cell-outline there is a dark grain (calcium); outside that a zone of large calcium lumps; around that a tissue of fibroblasts and a few epitheloid cells, and rests of lymphatic tissue. *Lungs*: In lymph nodules a few epitheloid cells and Langhans' giant cells.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. The prim., muscular., lmphgl. regional. et aliar., lienis, hepatis, pulmon.

Fig. 117. Series XXV. Complete dietary. All animals tubercular.

No. 105.

♂. White—black—brown.

Did not increase in weight during the last three weeks. Chloroformed and autopsied ³⁰/₆; muscular, fat animal. In the adductors of the right thigh an extensive focus, following the muscle interstices in different ducts, bordered by a rind formation, hard as cartilage, with caseous contents. Regional lymph-glands at both knees, the right groin and at the entrance to the pelvis, of the

same hardness, with miliary caseous foci. The largest of the lumbar glands, large as a brown bean, shows three such distinctly separate foci. *Liver* 39.0 grams, filled with miliary greyish white granulations. *Spleen* 4.1 grams, with prominent follicles. *Lungs* filled with miliary greyish white hard grains. Lymphglands in the lung hilus also fibrously changed; very hard. Histological examination as in No. 104 with similar pictures.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. The primar., muscultur., lmpagl. regional. et aliar., lienis, hepatis, pulmon.

No. 106.

♀. White—light brown—black.

Seemed vigorous till death. Through an accident broken both hind-legs ^{23/5}. Chloroformed and autopsied ^{30/6}. No sign of scurvy. In the adductors of the right thigh caseous abscesses following the intermuscular connective tissue upwards to the inguen and downwards below the knee, bordered by rind-like connective tissue. Tibiæ of both hindlegs broken, bone edges united by abundant callus. Lymphogl. ing. dx. miliary, wholly caseous, lmpagl. genu on both sides fibrously changed. *Liver* 34.3 grams, spleen 1.2 gram. In the middle lobe of the right lung a lentil-sized, grey gelatinous-looking round nodule, fibrous under the knife. Lymph-glands for the rest of ordinary consistence, except in the lung hilus, where they are also hard. Histological examination as in No. 104.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. The primar. muscultur., lmpagl. regional. et pulmon., lienis, hepatis et pulmon.

No. 107.

♀. Light brown—white.

Seemed well till the beginning of April. Increase in weight bad during the last two weeks. Died ^{18/4}. Autopsied ^{21/4}; hair does not come off. Teeth somewhat loose. Incisors chalky. Ribs normal. Joints without remark. General brittleness of bones. No hemorrhages. Claw-bed of the paw on the right fore-leg blue-violet. Hyperemia of the extremity. Right axillary lymph-gland strongly hyperemic. Tests of bacilli negative. Mucous membrane of larynx wrinkled, in trachea pale. *Lungs:* 0. *Liver* 10.6 grams, spleen 0.55 gram. No macroscopic signs of tuberculosis. Histological examination as in No. 104. Teeth show a totally normal picture, even of the odontoblast layer. Section of the right paw shows changes principally in connective-tissue and joint-cartilage. The connective-tissue has abundant thin-walled vessels. For the rest there is in some places the picture of an incipient necrosis. The joint-cartilage has an uneven surface, and some fibrous portions are seen in the joint which also contains a number of erythrocytes. In the musculature of the right thigh there is a small necrosis surrounded by fibrous connective-tissue, in which there are seen some few Langhans' giant cells. The arteries of the extremities not examined.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. The localis muscultur.

No. 108.

♂. Light brown—black.

Less satisfactory increase in weight during the last five weeks. Chloroformed and autopsied ^{30/6}: No sign of scurvy. The purulent local focus follows the interstices of the adductors to the connections. The boundary surface granulous, bright red. Lymph-glands in right knee small, fibrous, with calcium scrapings. In the inguen a pea-sized lymph-gland with three miliary abscesses. Other lymph-glands homogeneous, swollen. *Liver* 46.2 grams, spleen 29.2 grams, considerably increased in volume, the former filled with miliary grains, the latter mottled, very full of blood. The lungs show

numerous miliary granulations with hyperemic zone. Histological examination as in No. 104. Examination on amyloid in spleen negative. Spleen: large necroses with connective-tissue. For the rest as No. 104.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc primar.; lmpghl. regional., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon.

No. 109.

♀. White—black—light brown.

Decreased in weight during the last twelve days. Chloroformed ³⁰/₆ and autopsied ²/₇: Fat animal. No sign of scurvy. In the uterine horns 3 feti, 3.5 cm. from vertex to coccyx. Feti and placenta show no signs of tuberculosis. Local focus in the muscles of the right thigh very small, of 5 mm. diameter, very hard-rinded, with an abscess in the centre, big as a pin's head. Lymph-glands at right knee, inguen and pelvis enlarged, all through rind-like and fibrous, each with one to four small purulent foci, surrounded by a caseous demarcation zone. The connective-tissue so hard that it grates against the knife. *Spleen* very voluminous, 5 × 3.5 × 3.5 cm., 16.1 grams, shows yellow foci varying in size and surrounded by a hemorrhagic border zone. *Liver* granular on surface, very hard. *Lungs* filled with miliary and somewhat larger granulations, yellow or grey, surrounded by a hyperemic zone. Five lymph-glands in hilus rindlike and fibrous, one with a small abscess. Histological examination as in No. 104. *Liver:* the regenerative strands occupy the larger part of the liver, are of a markedly fibrous character, while liver columns, epitheloid cells, Langhans' giant cells and round cells are somewhat less conspicuous. Tuberculous granulation tissue in spleen, lymph-glands, lungs, shows fibroblasts dominating among epitheloid cells, Langhans' giant cells, lymphocytes, calcium grains and tubercle bacilli. Granulation foci in the marrow of two ribs.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc primar. lmpghl. regional.; lienis, hepatitis, pulmon.; lmpghl. hil. pulmon.; costar.

No. 110.

♂. Yellow—white.

Increased uninterruptedly in weight, till it was killed by chloroform ³⁰/₆. Autopsied ²/₇: Fat animal. No sign of scurvy. In the muscles of the right thigh there is an extensive rindlike connective-tissue, in which a miliary abscess is found. Lphgl. genu bilat. enlarged rind-like, with 0—5 small purulent foci. Lphgl. ing. not so hard; smaller. Lumbar lymph-glands like the knee glands. Some lymph-glands in the lung hilus are harder still. One of them has a small abscess. Lungs, spleen and liver sparingly filled with yellow-grey granulations, somewhat more than miliary in size, surrounded by a hyperemic zone. *Liver* 49.7 grams, spleen 4.1 grams. Histological examination shows pictures like those in No. 104.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc primar., lmpghl. regional., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon., lmpghl. hil. pulmon.

No. 111.

♂. Black—brown—white.

After a standstill in weight during a month, the animal died ²⁷/₅. Autopsied ³⁰/₅. Fat animal. No sign of scurvy or acute infection. In the musculature of the right thigh an almond-sized abscess, surrounded by very thick connective-tissue rinds. The lymph-gland of the right inguen miliary in size, caseously changed all through. All lymph-glands homogeneously swollen. Spleen 17.7 grams, liver 36 grams. In the spleen, small white submiliary foci. Histological examination like No. 104 gives similar pictures.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc primar., lmpghl. regional., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon., costar. duo.

Conclusion for Series XXV. The series shows that the stock of tubercle bacilli that has been used must be indicated as having rather small virulence for guinea-pigs. One died of an unascertained illness after 27 days and only at the microscopical examination the primary focus was found in the musculature. Six of the animals lived till they were killed after 102 days. The tuberculosis was then general. Common to all the cases is the fibrous character of the connective tissue which is seen in and around the tuberculous foci in muscle, lymph-glands and parenchymatous organs. The primary focus in the musculature is bordered by rinds of connective-tissue, more than a millimeter thick, which, however, often contain epithelioid cells and Langhans' giant cells. The regional lymph-glands are for the most part changed into hard fibrous tissue, in which there are often seen one or several small abscesses. Between them strong connective-tissue septa penetrate.

Series XXVI.

Animals 112—119. Of these No. 116—119 were infected $\frac{29}{3}$ with tuberculosis. All were kept on basal diet without addition from this date and died within 36 days. Weight charts, Fig. 118.

No. 112.

♂. White—light brown.

Died $\frac{26}{4}$, autopsied $\frac{27}{4}$. No sign of infection. Hemorrhages around knees, wrists and most ribs. The costochondral junctions enlarged, around almost all of them mouldings of connective-tissue swellings, such as described above. Teeth can easily be removed. Increased fragility of epiphyses not so much of diaphyses. Jaw brittle. Liver 12 grams, spleen 0.22 gram. Histological examination shows pictures like those in No. 5.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 113.

♂. White—yellow—black.

Died $\frac{17}{4}$. Autopsied $\frac{18}{4}$. Teeth loose. Epiphyses of the long bones easily breaking. Hemorrhages around the swollen costochondral junctions, which show the white line, and around the swollen knees. An ulceration on the left fore-paw, corresponding to metacarpus, with subcutis as bottom. Lmphgl. axillaris bright pink. Histological examination shows in different organs scorbutic changes as in No. 5. Kidney, Fig. 87. Heart, Fig. 67. In muscles, the ulceration on metacarpus, in spleen, liver, lung, tubercle bacilli were looked for with negative result.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 114.

♂. Black—white.

Dead after one day, on $\frac{30}{3}$. Autopsied $\frac{5}{4}$: body in state of decomposition.

Diagnosis: Infectio?

No. 115.

♂. Black—white—yellow.

Died, with picture of scurvy, $\frac{27}{4}$. *Post-mortem* examination on $\frac{29}{4}$ and histological examination show similar changes as in No. 112.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior.

No. 116.

♂. White (albino).

Died with scurvy symptoms $\frac{16}{4}$, autopsied $\frac{18}{4}$. Hair easily loosening.

Large hemorrhages around right knee and the six upper pairs of ribs on the right side. These costochondral junctions swollen on both sides. Teeth can easily be removed. Upper jaw brittle. Lmphgl. inguin. dx., paratracheal, and submaxillar, slightly homogeneously swollen. Liver 23.5 grams, spleen 0.6 gram. Histological examination of 10 ribs shows absence of ordered cartilage column layer and of ossification in the light-coloured frame-work marrow. In the *musculature of the right thigh* there is a necrotizing granulation tissue, and around that an extraordinarily vascular zone. In the vicinity there are numerous small necroses of muscular fibres with embedded calcium lumps. Nowhere any connective tissue is seen to bound or grow through the necrotic foci. In the *spleen* the lymphoid tissue is to a large extent replaced by epitheloid cells. Tubercle bacilli are very numerous. No amyloid. *Liver* shows abundant fat, and atrophy. Small foci of epitheloid cells, fibroblasts, giant cells of undecided type, tubercle bacilli. In lmphgl. submaxillar. hyperemia, epitheloid cells, tubercle bacilli. In the bronchi exudate. Adrenals, p. 102.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. Tbc. muscul. primar., lienis, hepatis, lmphgl. submaxillar. Bronchitis.

The lines with $\times\times$ represent tubercular animals.

Fig. 118. Series XXVI. No antiscorbutic.

No. 117.

♀. White—black.

Progress to death $\frac{1}{5}$. The findings at the *post-mortem* examination $\frac{3}{5}$ and at the histological examination resemble the cases of severest absolute scurvy, that are described above. Small quantity of liquid in abdomen. Peritoneum parietale et viscerale thickened, not glossy. Liver and spleen with deposits around lower edge or pole. In the descending part of duodenum,

a small irregular sore of the mucous membrane and to the bottom of this sore a white-gray lymph-gland adheres. Lymph-glands of right knee and groin wholly caseous. Lumbar glands show caseous formation of a miliary focus in one pole. Histological examination shows pictures similar to those in No. 116 concerning primary focus, spleen, liver, lung. In regional lymph-glands necroses, which show numerous lymphocyte shadows, and very numerous tubercle bacilli. No distinct newly-formed connective tissue. Duodenal gland with large necrotic foci without specific character, with numerous tubercle bacilli.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. The muscul. primar., lmphgl. regional., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon. Bronchitis. Ulcus duodeni. Peritonitis.

No. 118.

♀. White—black—yellow.

Eating and drinking with appetite to the last. Died and was autopsied $\frac{4}{5}$. Hair loosening, though not so easily as otherwise in scurvy. Teeth everywhere loose. In the lower jaw they are easily lifted out. Only certain of the costochondral junctions are enlarged in any considerable degree (3, 4 and 11 sin.). Hemorrhage around both knees. Upper tibia epiphyses extremely brittle. Upper jaw not brittle. Liver 15.4 grams. A bean-sized caseous lymph-gland in the liver hilus. Lungs filled with a large number of miliary, white-grey foci, caseous in the centre. In the right groin a bean-sized lymph-gland, in the pelvis lentil-sized glands, partially caseous. In the lymph-glands of the lung hilus, bean-sized, partially caseous foci. In lmphgl. submaxillar. small white foci. In the inner part of the musculature in the right thigh a hazelnut-sized, caseous abscess cavity, without macroscopical capsular formation. Histological examination as in No. 116.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. The primar. musculor., lmphgl. regional., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon. lphgl. divers.

No. 119.

♂. Light brown—white—black.

Progress to death $\frac{22}{4}$, findings at the *post-mortem* examination $\frac{23}{4}$ and histological examination shows picture of pronounced scurvy. Also with regard to the tubercular changes in muscle, regional lymph-glands, spleen and liver, No. 119 resembles No. 116 and 117.

Liver 19.5 grams, Spleen 2.2 grams.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus gravior. The primar. musculor., lmphgl. regional., lienis, hepatitis, lmphgl. hilus pulmon.

Conclusion for Series XXVI: Neither in the primary muscle-foci, in the regional glands, spleen or liver, nor in other affected organs there is any tendency seen of reactive connective-tissue, macro- or microscopically.

Series XXVII.

Animals 120—127. No. 124—127 were infected with tuberculosis. The animals were given basal diet and besides 0.3 ccm. of preserved orange juice (0.1 m. pr. d.). Weight charts, Fig. 119.

No. 120.

♀. White—light brown—black.

Died $\frac{13}{4}$ without having shown scurvy symptoms. Autopsied the same day. No certain changes to be observed at the *post-mortem* examination. Liver 18.6 grams. Spleen 0.7 gram. Histological examination as in No. 5.

Diagnosis: Scorbut latens extensus. Infectio?

No. 121. Black—white.

Was found lying with its head over the brim of the milk basin and its nose in the milk, $23/4$. Autopsied $25/4$. Hair easily loosening. Teeth firm; knees swollen, ribs slightly enlarged in costochondral junctions. No hemorrhages. Lymph-glands of upper jaw nearly as big as brown beans. Liver 8.0 grams, spleen 0.4 grams. Histological examination as in No. 5, and besides kidney and adrenal. Spleen, Fig. 84. Adrenal, Fig. 93.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior. Infectio.

No. 122. Yellow—grey.

Progress to death $10/5$; findings at *post-mortem* examination $12/5$ and histological examination similar to those in No. 5. Spleen 0.5 gram. Liver 13.7 grams. Tooth, Fig. 22.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior.

Fig. 119. Series XXVII. 0.1 m. pr. d.

No. 123. Black—white—brown.

Dead and autopsied $30/4$. Progress, findings at *post-mortem* and histological examinations similar to those in No. 5. Liver 10.7 grams, spleen 0.35 gram. Swelling and reddening of the mucous membrane in larynx and trachea.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior. Laryngo-tracheitis.

No. 124.

♂. Black—white.

Dead and autopsied $21/4$: Lean animal. Teeth loose, can be removed with some difficulty. The epiphyses of the long bones brittle. Upper jaw brittle. Costochondral junctions and knees swollen. Hemorrhages in the rib interstices and around right knee. Necrosis focus in thigh musculature without distinct capsule. Lymph-gland of the right groin shows small caseous foci. Spleen 0.9 gram, filled with granulations of the size of a pin's head. Liver 15.9 grams. Histological examination shows the primary focus in the musculature bordered by a wall of epitheloid cells, among which some tuberculous foci

of lymphoid cells. No connective tissue (Plate IV). Also with regard to lymph-glands, liver, spleen, the pictures are similar to those shown in No. 116 and 117.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior. Tbc primar. muscular., lmpagl. regional., lienis, hepatitis, lmpagl. divers.

No. 125. Black—white—brown.

Died $^{27/5}$, autopsied $^{30/5}$. In trachea and large bronchi mucous phlegm. No hemorrhage except in the musculature of the right thigh, where it is very extensive. Teeth in the lower jaw loose. Epiphyses brittle, diaphyses not. The costochondral junctions of the ribs enlarged; some (C 6, 7, 8 sin.) surrounded by connective-tissue formations. Lymph-glands everywhere homogeneously swollen. In both groins and at right knee they are pea-sized, caseous. In a pelvis gland a pre-caseous focus. Histological examination similar to that in No. 116 and 117.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior. Tbc primar. muscular., lmpagl. regional., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon., lmpagl. divers. Tracheobronchitis, pneumoniae.

No. 126. Light brown—white—black.

Dead and autopsied $^{11/5}$. Progress, *post-mortem* examination and histological pictures similar to those in No. 125. On $^{6/5}$ there was observed round the left eye a small region, hairless, covered with bloody crustæ, which remained till death. No certain hemorrhage for the rest. Spleen 3.2 grams. Liver 21.8 grams. In regional lymph-glands necroses which occupy the largest part of the gland, with small calcium lumps in the centre. No distinct new connective tissue. Hyperemia of periganglionic capsule. (Plate VI). In the mucous membrane of the bladder wall a necrosis, in the wall of which there are seen bacilli looking like tubercle bacilli.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior. Tbc primar. musc., lmpagl. regional., lienis, hepatitis, vesicae urinae.

No. 127. White—brown—black.

Dead $^{15/4}$, autopsied $^{16/4}$. Knees are somewhat swollen, are fractured spontaneously when taken out. Hemorrhages in muscles above right knee. The costochondral junctions slightly swollen. Teeth of lower jaw somewhat loose. Lymph-glands at right knee and tracheal lymph-glands homogeneously swollen. The middle lobe of left lung pneumonic in its upper region. Liver 20.4 grams, spleen 0.4 gram. Histological examination of 12 ribs, spleen, liver, focus in thigh musculature, gives pictures similar to those in No. 116. The alveoli of left lung in the above-mentioned region filled with red blood-corpuscles, fibrin and diplococci. In bronchi also exudate of different cells.

Diagnosis: Scorbut manifestus mitior. Tbc primar. muscul., lmpagl. regional., lienis, hepatitis. Broncho-pneumonia ac.

Conclusion for Series XXVII: Hardly in any place the tuberculous foci in different organs show a connective tissue, which appears as having to be considered reactive.

Series XXVIII.

Animals 128—134. No. 132—134 were infected with tuberculosis. The animals had basal diet and besides each 0.6 ccm. of preserved orange juice (0.2 m. pr. d.). Weight charts, Fig. 120.

No. 128.

♀. White—light brown—black.

Dead and autopsied $^{13/4}$. Hemorrhages in subcutis around both knees.

Otherwise no macroscopical signs of scurvy. The large intestine filled with thin liquid contents. Hyperemia and hemorrhage in its lymph nodules (Peyer's plaques). Corresponding lymph-glands in the mesentery bean-sized, hyperemic. Histological examination of the mentioned organs, 12 ribs, liver (18.9 grams, spleen (1.0 gram) shows pictures of early scurvy as in No. 127.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Colitis ac.

No. 129. Light brown—white—black.

Dead and autopsied $21/4$: Hair not loosening. No hemorrhage. Teeth firm? Upper jaw not brittle. Somewhat increased fragility of epiphyses, not of diaphyses; knees and costochondral junction slightly swollen. »White line» in the latter. Lively hyperemia of the mucous membrane of larynx, trachea, ventricle and duodenum. Liver 23.1 grams, spleen 1.0 gram. Histological examination similar to that in No. 127.

Diagnosis: Scorbut latens extensus. Laryngo-tracheitis ac. Gastro-duodenitis ac.

Fig. 120. Series XXVIII. 0.2 m. pr. d.

No. 130. Yellow—black—white.

Progress to death $29/4$, findings at the *post-mortem* examination $30/4$ and histological examination similar to those in No. 129. Spleen 1.8 gram. Tooth, Fig. 23.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Infectio.

No. 131. White—black—brown.

Dead $19/4$, autopsied $21/4$. Rather fat animal. Hair easily loosening. Knees swollen in the epiphyseal lines. Hemorrhages around several ribs. The costochondral junctions swollen, surrounded by pale grey enlargements (connective tissue). The teeth are removed with some difficulty from their alveoli. Liver 18.9 grams. Spleen 1.5 gram. Hyperemia of the upper part of the large intestine. Histological examination similar to No. 127.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior manifestus. Colitis ac.

No. 132.

♂. Brown—grey—white.

Dead and autopsied $11/5$: Hair easily loosening. Teeth somewhat loose, can not be lifted out. The costochondral junctions and knees somewhat

swollen. The epiphyses of the long bones brittle, diaphyses and upper jaw not. No hemorrhages. The primary tuberculous focus in the musculature of the right thigh consists of an almond-sized caseous mass, bordered by a capsule thin as a knife-edge. Lymph. genu et inguen. dx., lumbal., for the greater part occupied by caseous foci. Other lymph-glands slightly enlarged uniformly. Liver mottled, 18.5 grams. Spleen 1.4 gram. Histological examination of all ribs and of knees shows pronounced scurvy changes, *i. a.*, calcified necroses in the muscles. For the rest the same organs as in No. 104 are examined. Heart, Fig. 70. Heart and lungs also stained with cresylic violet, spleen on amyloid.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior manifestus. The prim. loc., lymph. region.; lienis; hepatitis; lymph. divers.; costar. duo.

No. 133.

♀. White—brown—black.

Dead and autopsied ²³/₆. Hair easily loosening. The molars somewhat loose. The upper incisors easily broken. The costochondral junctions show white line, somewhat swollen, as are also the knees. Fracture of left ankle, healed in a wrong position, with slight, soft callus. Increased fragility of the epiphyses of the long bones. Upper jaw brittle. No hemorrhage except in spleen, 20.1 grams, and liver 39.8 grams, which show a very mottled picture. Local focus smaller than a hazel-nut, caseously changed, surrounded by a thin capsule, which is glossily reflecting. Lymph-glands of right knee and groin pea-sized, caseously changed. The lumbar glands bean-sized, homogeneously grey, as are also the bronchioles. Histological examination as in No. 132, and besides of kidney, adrenal, lung.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior manifestus. The prim. loc., lymph. region., lienis, hepatitis, lymph. divers.

No. 134. Black—brown—white.

No sign of scurvy. The stitch in the musculature of the right thigh without reaction. Abdominal cavity filled by a turbid liquid, which is scentless and contains numerous fat-drops and tissue-fragments. In the place of the pancreas there are only seen some small strips of tissue left. Right lung pneumonic. Histological examination of spleen, liver, lung.

Diagnosis: Pneumonia ac. dx. Necrosis ac. pancreat. c. peritonit.

Conclusion for Series XXVIII: The two tubercularly infected animals that had lived more than a month, show a certain connective-tissue reaction, in the shape of a thin capsule around foci in muscles and regional lymph-glands.

Series XXIX.

Animals 135—142. Of these No. 139—142 were infected with tubercle bacilli. All had basal diet and besides 1 ccm. of the earlier described preserved orange juice (0.3 m. pr. d.). Weight charts, Fig. 121.

No. 135. Black—white.

Dead ¹⁹/₆ without having shown scurvy symptoms. Autopsied the same day: Incisors not glossy, break easily. Teeth firm. Upper jaw brittle. Bones for the rest firm. Joints not swollen. No hemorrhage. In the abdominal cavity a couple of tea-spoonfuls of bloody liquid. Spleen 2.5 × 2.5 × 4 cm., weight 13.4 grams, very much filled with blood and fragile. The upper pole adherent to the back abdominal wall, bounding an abscess which is outwardly bounded by the 11th and 12th ribs. An irregular rupture through the spleen, big as the tip of a little finger leads into this abscess. Liver 44.5 grams, large,

with swelling, muddy section surface. Histological examination as in No. 5, and besides of kidney. Tooth, Fig. 24.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Abscessus lienis rupturat.

No. 136. Black—white—brown.

Dead $\frac{1}{6}$, autopsied $\frac{3}{6}$. Progress, findings and histological examination (also adrenal) similar to those in No. 135. Teeth in lower jaw somewhat loose. The costochondral junction somewhat swollen, the knees not. Spleen 3.5 grams, liver 33.5 grams. Abscesses in spleen and liver, partly into the substance, partly outwardly bounded by abdominal wall and kidneys. No rupture of these abscesses.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Abscessus lienis et hepatis.

Fig. 121. Series XXIX. 0.3 m. pr. d.

No. 137. Brown—black—white.

Dead $\frac{5}{6}$, autopsied $\frac{6}{6}$. Coat rough, thin. Hair coming off in tufts. The diaphyses of the long bones are of an increased fragility. Teeth firm. Lymph-glands at the angle of the jaws bean-sized. Spleen 0.45 gram, liver 16.9 grams. Histological examination of organs as in No. 5 gives pictures similar to those in No. 135.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Infectio.

No. 138. Black—white—brown.

Dead $\frac{8}{6}$, autopsied $\frac{9}{6}$. Hair coming off in tufts. No hemorrhage. Teeth firm. Upper jaw brittle. The epiphyses of the long bones brittle. Larynx filled with glassy phlegm. Liver 26.6 grams, spleen 1.7 gram. Histological examination as in No. 135. Spleen, Fig. 85, also stained on amyloid, iron, with Giemsa.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Laryngitis ac.

No. 139.

♀. Grey—white.

Dead and autopsied ¹⁴/₅. Fat animal. Hair easily loosening. No hemorrhages except in the subcutis of right thigh, which is edematous. Walnut-sized, caseous focus in the musculature, surrounded by a connective-tissue capsule, 1 mm. thick. Lymph-gland of right knee not macroscopically changed. In the right groin two pea-sized, yellowish white glands, one of them caseous. Lymph-glands for the rest homogeneously swollen. Teeth firm, except incisors, which are rather loose and brittle. Upper jaw brittle. The epiphyses show increased fragility, the diaphyses not. The costochondral junctions somewhat swollen, distinctly in C 2 dx. and C 3 sin., there an enclosing connective-tissue formation is seen. Knees and other joints not swollen. Liver and spleen considerably enlarged; liver grey-yellow, adipose, fairly firm, 44.2 grams; spleen 2 × 4 × 6 ccm., 15.2 grams, profusely filled with blood, penetrated by white, firmer foci, big as a pin's head and more. In its upper pole a rupture, reaching almost across the organ. In the abdomen some tea-spoonfuls of bloody liquid. Histological examination as in No. 136. Rib, Fig. 38, also stained on iron and on fibrin according to Weigert.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Tbc prim. muscul., lymphgl. region., lienis, hepatitis, lymphgl. divers. Hemorrhagia e ruptura lienis.

No. 140. All white (albino).

Dead ¹⁴/₅, autopsied ¹⁶/₅. Hair somewhat loose. No hemorrhage. Teeth somewhat loose, incisors chalky. Slightly increased fragility of epiphyses, but not of diaphyses. Upper jaw brittle. In the costochondral junctions the white line of Fraenkel. In the adductors of right thigh a bean-sized dry caseous focus, with a thin but distinct membrane-like capsule. The inguinal lymph-glands lentil-sized, white, hard as calcium, grate against the knife. Other lymph-glands homogeneously swollen. Liver 26.5 grams. Spleen 21.2 grams, profusely filled with blood, with large white soft portions of irregular form. Histological examination as in No. 104. Rib, Fig. 35. Spleen also stained on amyloid.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Tbc prim. muscul., lymphgl. region., lienis, hepatitis, lymphgl. divers.

No. 141. Brown—white.

Dead ²²/₅, autopsied ²⁴/₅. Teeth somewhat loose, brittle. Upper jaw rather brittle. Pairs of ribs 3—5 have enlarged costochondral junctions. Knees slightly swollen in the epiphyseal regions. Hemorrhage in subcutis around the left elbow. From the inside of right knee the subcutis, upwards over the abdomen and forwards against both axillæ, is changed into caseous tissue, a couple of mms. thick. The pelvic lymph-glands are bean-sized and occupied to about half their volume by caseously purulent foci. Spleen 2.2 grams, liver 27.5 grams. Histological examinations as in No. 105.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Tbc subcutis, lymphgl. region., lienis, hepatitis.

No. 142.

♂. Brown—black—white.

Dead and autopsied ¹³/₅; lean animal. Teeth firm. Incisors very brittle. No hemorrhage. No swelling of the epiphyses of the extremities, nor of the costochondral junctions. Epiphyses easily broken, diaphyses not. Primary focus in the thigh musculature big as a brown bean, with thin, translucent capsule. Of some rice-shaped inguinal glands, one shows a small caseous focus, another a similar focus which is partially calcified and surrounded by a distinct connective-tissue capsule. Other lymph-glands homogeneously

glassily swollen. Larynx reddened. Mucous membrane wrinkled and swollen, on its surface a slight quantity of phlegmy, turbid, bubbly fluid. Mucous membrane in trachea reddened. Liver 19.6 grams. Spleen 2.4 grams. Histological examination as in No. 105, and besides of heart, lung. Kidney, Fig. 88.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. The prim. musc., lymphgl. region. et aliar., lienis, hepatis. Laryngo-tracheit. ac.

Conclusion for Series XXIX: Distinct, but slight connective-tissue reaction around tuberculous foci.

Series XXX.

Animals 143—150. Of them No. 147—150 were infected with tuberculosis. All the animals had basal diet and with that each 1.5 ccm. of preserved orange juice (0.5 m. pr. d.). Weight charts, Fig. 122.

Fig. 122. Series XXX. 0.5 m. pr. d.

No. 143. White—black—brown.

Dead $26/5$, autopsied $30/5$; very lean. No macroscopical sign of scurvy. Liver (11 grams) shows, like spleen (0.3 gram), lung, lymph-gland above the right adrenal, foci of irregular form and varying sizes up to the size of a bean, peripherally hard, in the centre often purulent, of white-yellow colour. Histological examination shows them to consist of a non-specific granulation tissue. Scorbutic changes in 13 ribs, spleen.

Diagnosis: Scorbut latens extensus. Infectio.

No. 144.

♂. Brown—grey—white.

Chloroformed and autopsied $29/6$. No macroscopical sign of scurvy or infection. Liver 29.2 grams. Spleen 1.9 gram. At the histological examination of 11 ribs, normal junction pictures are shown. Teeth, Fig. 25. Spleen also stained with Giemsa, heart, kidney, adrenal, muscle.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior.

No. 145. Grey—white—black.

Dead and autopsied ¹⁸/₄. Incisors of lower jaw chalky, somewhat loose. For the rest, no sign that might indicate scurvy. Liver 18.8 grams. Spleen 0.8 gram. The right foot shows pathological changes. The claw-bed is injected, the claws partly gone. The lymph-glands at the knees to some degree swollen. Injection of their arteries. The lungs have diminished air contents. The bronchi show purulent contents. Histological examination as in No. 97, and besides of heart (Fig. 68, 69) and right paw. Heart and lung also stained with cresylic violet.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Gangrena extremitat. Bronchitis purulenta.

No. 146.

♂. White—black—brown.

Chloroformed and autopsied ²⁹/₆ 1923. Incisors of the lower jaw possibly not quite firm. For the rest no pathological symptoms. Histological examination as in No. 97.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior.

No. 147. Black—white.

Dead and autopsied ³⁰/₄; no macroscopical sign of scurvy or acute infection. The right inguinal lymph-gland pea-sized, some partially changed into a dry caseous mass, others fibrous. Submaxillary lymph-glands pale, homogeneously swollen. Liver 24.8 grams with numerous foci, partly caseating but otherwise hard, up to the size of beans. Spleen 2.1 grams. The large intestine in two places adherent through the mesentery round a caseous lymph-gland. Histological examination as in No. 104, and besides of colon.

Diagnosis: Scorbut latens levior. Tbc prim. musc., lmpzgl. region., lienis, hepatis, pulmon., coli; lmpzgl. divers.

No. 148. Black—brown—white.

Dead and autopsied ²⁴/₆. Upper jaw brittle. Diaphyses somewhat easily broken. Epiphyses not. No sign of scurvy. The caseated, a little more than hazelnut-sized primary focus does not lie in the musculature but subcutaneously, surrounded by a very thin, reflecting membrane. Lymph-glands at the right knee and in the inguen pea-sized and a little larger, with small caseous foci, otherwise rather hard. Small quantity of turbid liquid in abdominal cavity and left pleura. Lower part of the lower lobe of left lung pneumonic. Peritoneum parietale rose-coloured, downy, with fibrin films on left lobe of the liver and on spleen. Liver 21.5 grams. Spleen 1.2 gram. Histological examination as in No. 116.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Tbc prim. musc., lmpzgl. region., lienis, hepatis, lmpzgl. divers. Bronchopneumonia ac. c. pleurit. et peritonit. ac.

No. 149.

♂. Grey—brown.

Chloroformed and autopsied ²⁹/₆. No macroscopical sign of scurvy or acute infection. The primary focus in the thigh musculature bean-sized, caseating though not yet homogeneous, outwardly bordered by a homogeneous granulating muscle surface. Lymph-glands everywhere homogeneously swollen, without distinct foci. Spleen 11.2 grams. In the lower pole a pea-sized whitish yellow focus. Liver 43.8 grams, traversed by strands of what looks like connective-tissue. Lungs filled with a large number of small foci, miliary in trefoil

or horseshoe arrangement. Histological examination as in No. 116. Spleen also stained on amyloid.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. The prim. muscul., lymphog. region., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon., lymphog. divers.

No. 150. Grey—yellow.

Dead $26/4$, autopsied $17/4$: No macroscopic sign of scurvy. In the bend of the right knee between the tendons of the adductors, a great focus of fibrous tissue. Lymph-glands at knees, groins and in pelvis caseating, not purulent, hardly more than pea-sized, enclosed by a capsule, from which they are easily loosened. In the mesentery some pea-sized hard lymph-glands. Spleen 0.8 gram, liver 11.8 grams. Histological examination as in No. 117.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. The prim. muscul., lymphog. region. lienis, hepatitis, pulm., lymphog. divers.

Conclusion for Series XXX: The reaction of the connective-tissue stronger than in preceding series, but not of normal strength.

Series XXXI.

Animals 151—158. Of these No. 155—158 were infected with tuberculosis. All animals had together with the basal diet 2 ccm. of preserved orange juice (0.7 m. pr. d.). Weight charts, Fig. 123.

No. 151.

♂. White—brown.

Killed and autopsied $29/6$. No macroscopical sign of scurvy or acute infection. Rather fat animal. Liver 29.9 grams. Spleen 1.1 gram. Histological examination as in No. 5.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior.

No. 152. Grey—white.

Dead $20/4$, autopsied $21/4$. The long bones generally brittle (diaphyses). No sign of scurvy. In lungs, liver, right kidney, different muscles and two ribs, there are foci up to the size of a hazel-nut, yellow, which at incision are found to contain a creamy mass in the centre. Histological examination as in No. 5. Tooth, Fig. 26.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Infectio.

No. 153.

♀. Black—brown—white.

Died and was autopsied $27/6$. Rather fat animal. Upper jaw brittle. Incisors of lower jaw somewhat loose. Otherwise no sign of scurvy. In both uterine horns lively injection around an elevated area 5—6 mm. long, on the inside showing a cavity with a small irregular elevation (graviditas). Mucous membrane in larynx, trachea and bronchi reddened. All left lung pneumonic, over a large extent fastened through light red adhesences to pleura parietalis. Between the adhesences abundant bloody-serous liquid. Liver 23.2 grams, spleen 1.2 gram. Histological examination as in No. 5.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior.

No. 154. Yellow—black—white.

Dead $4/4$, autopsied $5/4$. Nowhere any pathological conditions. Microscopical examination not undertaken.

Diagnosis incerta.

No. 155. White—black—brown.

No macroscopical sign of scurvy. Strong injection of duodenum, in the descending part of which there is a small callous ulcer. Towards the intestine there are two lymph-glands attached together, large as the half of an almond. In one of them a large abscess with thin pus. Liver 22.5 grams. Spleen 1 gram. Histological examination as in No. 104. In the thigh musculature only degeneration and increased connective-tissue are found, but no necrosis, no specific granulation tissue, no tubercle bacilli.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Ulcus duodeni.

Fig. 123. Series XXXI. 0.7 m. pr. d.

No. 156.

♂. White—black.

Chloroformed and autopsied ²⁹/₆. Rather fat animal. Macroscopically no sign of scurvy. In the adductors of the right thigh two pea-sized foci with a connective-tissue capsule, a little above 1 mm. thick. Knee lymph-glands on both sides bean-sized, with small caseous foci, surrounded by a calcium-grating capsule. Calcified, partially liquified foci are also found in several submaxillary lymph-glands. In lung hilus small hard lymph-glands without distinct calcium scrapings. Numerous miliary, not quite round grey-white foci in lungs and liver (38.4 grams) some few in spleen (4.8 grams). A bean-sized focus, calcified and caseating, is seen at the back in the middle part of the liver. Histological examination as in No. 104. Tooth, Fig. 27.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens extensus. Tbc prim. musc., lmphgl. regional. et divers.; lienis, hepatis, pulmon.

No. 157. Brown—white—black.

Died ²⁰/₄, autopsied ²³/₄. Teeth somewhat loose. Upper jaw not brittle. Costrochondral junctions and knees slightly swollen. Hemorrhage around

right knee-joints. Increased fragility of the epiphyses of the long bones. Spleen 0.4 gram. Liver 12 grams. Local focus in the musculature of right thigh has the shape of an elongated narrow abscess, without capsule. Lymph-glands in groin and in pelvis somewhat enlarged, without foci. A piece of the small intestine, a few cm. long, shows lively hyperemia with blood-imbibed faeces. Histological examination as in No. 116. The epiphyses of knees and elbows show no certain scorbutic changes.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Tbc prim. muscul., lymphgl. region. Enteritis hemorrhagica.

No. 158.

♀. Black—brown—white.

Died $\frac{8}{5}$ and was autopsied $\frac{9}{5}$. No macroscopical sign of scurvy. On the right side of the nose a region which is partly hairless, partly covered by short, broken hairs. In the base of the plantar side of the little toe on the right hind-leg a small hyperemic blain. In the nostril milky liquid. Trachea filled with frothy liquid, a little thinner than milk. In the muscles of the right thigh several pea-sized abscesses, enclosed by connective-tissue capsules. Regional glands pea-sized, at the most, with miliary foci of caseous tissue in one pole. Lung hilus glands similar, but fibrous. Spleen 6.3 grams. Liver 17.3 grams. Histological examination as in No. 116. Spleen also stained on amyloid.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Tbc prim. muscul., lymphgl. region., lienis, hepatis, pulmon.

Conclusion for Series XXXI: The strength of the connective-tissue reaction varies in the different cases — from fairly strong to rather weak.

Series XXXII.

Animals 159—166. Of these No. 163—166 were infected with tubercle bacilli. The animals had basal diet and in addition each 2.5 ccm. (0.8 m. pr. d.) of preserved orange juice. Weight charts, Fig. 124.

No. 159. Black—white.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{27}{4}$. No macroscopic sign of scurvy. A deep reddening of the mucous membrane in the digestory canal from stomach to anus, increasing downwards. In the mesentery of the large intestine a purulent lymph-gland. Liver 19.5 grams. Spleen 0.5 gram. Histological examination of 12 ribs, spleen and liver. Tooth Fig. 28.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Gastro-enterocolitis. ac. c. lymphadenit. supp.

No. 160.

♀. White—black—brown.

Chloroformed and autopsied $\frac{29}{6}$. Fat animal. Hair somewhat loose. No sign of scurvy or acute infection. Liver 31.2 grams. Spleen 1.3 gram. Histological examination of 12 ribs, muscles, jaw, liver, spleen; heart and lungs, also stained with cresylic violet.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior.

No. 161.

♀. Black—white—brown.

Chloroformed and autopsied $\frac{29}{6}$. Hair somewhat loose. No macroscopical sign of scurvy or acute infection. Liver 31.5 grams, spleen 1.5 gram. Histological examination as in No. 160 (spleen also stained according to Giemsa, tooth, Fig. 29, and besides of heart, Fig. 66, kidney, Fig. 89, adrenal.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior.

No. 162.

♀. Grey—brown—white.

Progress, macroscopical and microscopical examinations and findings as in No. 161. Liver 28.5 grams, spleen 1.5 gram.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior.

Fig. 124. Series XXXII. 0.8 m. pr. d.

No. 163. Grey.

Died $9/4$, autopsied $10/4$. No macroscopical sign of scurvy or tuberculosis. On the front side of the lower part of sternum an enlargement of the periosteum, 1×1 cm., homogeneous, grey, soft, with an abscess in the centre. In the left pleura and in the pericardium some ccm. of bloodily turbid liquid. On visceral pleura and pericardium thin fibrinous membranes. Left lung filled with miliary, greyish white nodules. Cor nearly ballshaped. In the left auricle a thrombus, which fills the whole space and is adherent to the wall. Histological examination of the mentioned organs, 24 ribs, knees, spleen, liver, teeth, thigh focus and lymph-glands.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. The prim. musc., Impagl. region., lienis, Impagl. hil. pulm. Pneumoniæ, pleuritis, pancarditis. Periostit. sternal.

No. 164. Black—white.

Died $12/5$, autopsied $13/5$. In the larynx glassy phlegm and a small quantity of a thin turbid liquid. Mucous membrane in trachea and bronchi reddened. Lungs have diminished air content. No sign of scurvy. In thigh musculature

on the right side scattered caseous foci, peasized, with distinct, though thin, connective-tissue capsule. In lympho-gland. genu et inguen. dx. and in the regional pelvic glands, which all are smaller than a pea, there is found in one pole miliary foci, one in each, looking like yellow cheese, but under the knife like hard cicatrizized fibrous tissue. Liver 23.7 grams, mottled. Spleen $0.6 \times 1.3 \times 3.7$ cm., weight 3.5 grams, of similar, mottled appearance. Histological examination as in No. 116.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Tbc prim. muscul., lymphogl. region., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon., lymphogl. divers., costar. duo, condyl. femoris. Laryngo-tracheo-bronchitis and bronchopneumonia ac.

No. 165.

♀. Black—brown—white.

Died and was autopsied ²⁷/₆: Hair loosening. The epiphyses of the long bones somewhat more easily broken than normally, diaphyses not. For the rest no sign of scurvy. Right lung to pleura parietalis with soft, red adherences. Lungs filled with foci in sizes from a pin's head to a pea, greyish white in the periphery, yellow white in the centre, not purulent. In superficial parts towards pleura a number of conical foci. Spleen 11.5 grams, large, mottled, filled with a large number of calcium-hard foci, big as a pin-point. Liver 68.0 grams, paler, granulated, like spleen very firm with hard pale regions up to the size of a hazel-nut, in which there are caseous foci. In lymph-glands of right knee and groin, and in the regional pelvic glands, all of them at the most pea-sized, fibrous, very hard foci with small, miliary, caseous abscesses in the centre. In some of them the caseous focus is not a uniform cavity but is divided by connective-tissue septa into different rooms. Glands of lung hilus similar, a little larger, but without abscesses. Instead the focus is felt to be calcium-hard. Histological examination as in No. 116, except of adrenal.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Tbc prim. muscul., lymphogl. region., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon., lymphogl. divers.

No. 166. White—yellow.

Showed from the start a bad appetite. A couple of weeks after the weight curve had turned downwards, the animal began persistingly to twist its head and wheel round to the right. Showed this symptom afterwards, only the twisting was during the last week to the left, till death ²⁶/₆. Autopsied ²⁷/₆. General brittleness of bone. Extreme emaciation. No sign of scurvy. The terminations of all the four extremities mutilated, the tips of the toes being gone on the fore-paws, the distal part of the foot as far as half the metatarsus on the hind-paws. Remaining stumps dry, brittle, easily broken. Lymph-glands in axilla and inguen strongly hyperemic. Cultures are made on the juice from these glands on aërobical and anaërobical substrata; no growth. In the thigh musculature on the right side a small necrotic focus, enclosed by a distinct capsule. In the right knee, groin and regional pelvic glands small whitish yellow foci. In the centres of these there is a minimal abscess in one pelvic lymph-gland as well as in one lung hilus gland. Spleen 2.8 grams, liver 18.8 grams. In the lower part of right lung a couple of small miliary, gelatinous granulations. Histological examination of the mentioned organs and of 10 ribs, muscles, jaw.

Diagnosis: Scorbut mitior latens levior. Tbc prim. muscul., lymphogl. region., lienis, hepatitis, pulmon., lymphogl. divers. Gangrena extremitat.

Conclusion for Series XXXII: Connective-tissue reaction of moderate strength round tuberculous foci.

Series XXXIII.

Animals 167—174. Of these No. 171—174 were infected with tubercle bacilli. All animals had from March 29 basal diet and besides each 3.5 cm. of preserved orange juice. They were completely protected. Weight charts, Fig. 125.

No. 167. Whitish grey.

Died $10/4$, autopsied $13/4$. No sign of scurvy. Strong hyperemia of colon. Lymph-glands in the mesentery enlarged. Spleen 0.1 gram. Liver 17.7 grams. The eighth rib on the right shows in the costochondral junction a heavy local enlargement. Histological examination of 2 ribs, jaw, liver, spleen.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Colitis ac. Osteochondrit. ac.

Fig. 125. Series XXXIII. 1.2 m. pr. d.

No. 168.

♀. White—black—brown.

Killed and autopsied $30/6$. No pathological conditions could be observed. Histological examination of teeth, liver (29.2 grams), spleen (1.0 gram), kidney, Fig. 86; heart, also stained with cresylic violet.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 169.

♀. Brown—black—white.

Progress and findings as in No. 168. } Liver 13.3 grams, spleen 0.8 gram.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 170.

♀. Brown—black—white.

Progress and findings as in No. 168. } Liver 23.1 grams, spleen 0.9 gram.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 171.

♀. All white (albino).

Killed and autopsied ³⁰/₆. Fat animal. No sign of scurvy. No macroscopical sign of tuberculosis. Liver 20.0 grams. Spleen 1.0 gram. At histological examination of the thigh musculature in series of sections, a submiliary focus was found, consisting of epithelioid cells, lymphocytes and fibroblasts. No tubercle bacilli found in it. Nothing remarkable noted in liver, spleen, jaw. Heart and lungs also stained with cresylic violet.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc prim. musc. peracta.

No. 172. White—brown—black.

Dead ²²/₄, autopsied ²³/₄. Fat animal. Hair not coming off. No sign of scurvy. Primary focus in thigh musculature rather more than pea-sized, hard-rinded with a miliary abscess in the centre. In the regional lymph-glands, which are pea-sized, there are miliary, yellow, very hard foci. Spleen weighs more than 1 gram. Right lung in its upper part pneumonic, adherent to pleura parietale. In the pleura bloody liquid. Histological examination as in No. 165, and besides of jaw. Region. lymph-gland, Plate V.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc prim. musc., lmphgl. region., lienis, hepatitis. Pneumonia ac. dx.

No. 173. White—black.

Fat animal. Hair not loosening. No sign of scurvy. Teeth firm. Incisors of lower jaw brittle, easily broken. In the musculature of the right thigh a more than almond-sized, caseous focus with a smooth capsule more than a millimeter thick. One lymph-gland in knee and one in groin, pea-sized with a miliary abscess, enclosed by rind-like connective-tissue. Other lymph-glands homogeneously swollen. Abdomen distended. In the abdominal cavity a tea-spoonful of liquid blood. The large intestine considerably distended by gases. A rupture a centimeter long in the lower pole of the spleen, which is swollen, congested, around a pea-sized greyish yellow focus. Under slight pressure blood percolates from the rupture. Spleen 10.2 grams. Liver 35.5 grams. Histological examination of jaw, thigh focus, different lymph-glands, liver, spleen.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc prim. musc., lmphgl. region., lienis, hepatitis, lmphgl. divers. Ruptura lienis c. peritonitide.

No. 174.

♀. Brown—black—white.

Died and was autopsied ¹¹/₅. No sign of scurvy. Between the tendons of the adductors in the bend of the right knee an almond-sized caseous focus, surrounded by connective-tissue rinds, a millimeter thick. Gland in the bend of knee pea-sized, white, hard. Other lymph-glands homogeneously swollen. Spleen 0.9 gram. A somewhat more than pea-sized spleneculus at the spleen hilus, largely caseous. Liver 18.0 grams, mottled, with differently sized, irregular white foci. Histological examination as in No. 172.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc prim. musc., lmphgl. region., lienis, hepatitis, lmphgl. divers, costar. duo.

Conclusion for Series XXXIII: Strong reaction of a well developed connective-tissue in and about tuberculous foci.

Series XXXIV.

Animals 175—182. Of these No. 180—182 were infected with tubercle bacilli. All the animals had basal diet and besides 5 ccm. of preserved orange juice. The dose proved to be fully protective. Weight charts, Fig. 126.

No. 175. White—black—brown.

No sign of scurvy. All claws partially gone. A metatarsal joint opened. Upper lobes of both lungs pneumonic. Histological examination as in No. 172.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Pneumonia ac. bilat. Gangrena extremitat.

×× tubercular animals.

Fig. 126. Series XXXIV. 1.7 m. pr. d.

No. 176. Brown—white—black.

Died and was autopsied $12/6$. No sign of scurvy. The epiphyses of the long bones are more easily broken than normally. Upper incisors somewhat loose. The right pleura is reduced to slits between thick fibrin coats, through which the pneumonic lower part of the lung adheres to chest wall and diaphragm. In the peritoneal cavity a moderate quantity of frothy, turbid scentless liquid. Peritoneum rose-coloured. Liver 15.5 grams, spleen 0.8 gram. Histological examination as in No. 172. Tooth, Fig. 30.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Pleuropneumonia ac. dx. et peritonitis ac.

No. 177. Brown—white.

Died $26/4$, autopsied $27/4$. No sign of scurvy. Mucous membrane in larynx wrinkled. Under the left mandible a pea-sized, half purulent lymph-

gland. In both lungs miliary pneumonic foci. Liver 12.4 grams, spleen 0.5 gram. Histological examination of spleen, liver, jaw.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Laryngotracheit. ac. Bronchopneumonïe ac.

No. 178.

♂. Black—brown—white.

Chloroformed and autopsied ³⁰/₆. Fat animal without remark. Liver 39.9 grams. Spleen 1.0 gram. Histological examination of spleen, liver, jaw, kidney. Adrenal, Fig. 92.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 179.

♂. Greyish yellow.

Chloroformed and autopsied ³⁰/₆. No sign of scurvy. Hair loosening rather easily. Upper lobe of right lung pneumonic. Lymph-glands in hilus homogeneously swollen. Liver 25.6 grams, spleen 0.7 gram. Histological examination of liver, spleen, jaw.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Pneumonia ac.

No. 180. Grey—brown—white.

Dead and autopsied ⁶/₅. No signs of scurvy. In the musculature on the inside of the right thigh very strong rind formation with a number of small caseous miliary foci. Lymph-glands in the right groin and in pelvis pea-sized, hard, with miliary, strongly white foci of great hardness, without cheese. Spleen (2.2 grams) shows a large number of larger and smaller soft parts of different red colour. Liver 21.6 grams, with a large number of conical whitish yellow parts localized at the border with hyperemia in the edges (septic infarcts). All the left lung and central parts of the two upper lobes in the right lung pneumonic, with turbid black fluid. Two Peyer's plaques hyperemic, swollen. Histological examination as in No. 104.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc prim. musc., lmpghl. region., lienis, hepatis. Bronchitis ac. Pneumonia ac.

No. 181.

♂. Black—yellow—white.

Dead and autopsied ³⁰/₆. No sign of scurvy. In the right thigh musculature an irregular cavity reaching a good distance towards inguen, filled by a thin liquid with strips of tissue and bordered by thick rinds of connective tissue. Lymph-glands lying at right knee and groin, in left musculus quadriceps and at left knee, and in pelvis, pea-sized, with miliary and smaller caseous abscesses, enclosed by thick connective tissue. A similar gland under the jaw. In one of the pelvic glands a similar small focus with calcium in the capsule. Liver large, 37.9 grams, congested, with some miliary granulations, greyish white. Spleen 2.8 grams, likewise. Histological examination as in No. 104.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. Tbc prim. musc., lmpghl. region., lienis, hepatis, lmpghl. divers.

No. 182.

♂. Black—brown.

Killed and autopsied ³⁰/₆. No sign of scurvy. Not much hair loosening. The diaphyses of the long bones and upper jaw somewhat more brittle than normally. In the adductors of the right thigh a narrow, less than almond-sized focus of dry cheese, bordered by a distinct capsule. In the left thigh, in the adductors, a lymph-gland, with an abscess in the centre, and in the outer parts changed into a thick connective-tissue membrane. Lymph-glands at both knees pea-sized, white, fibrous, no foci. Other lymph-glands generally

swollen, grey, homogeneous. Liver 44.8 grams, mottled, filled with submiliary, somewhat irregularly formed grey foci with hyperemic zone. Lungs likewise. Also in the spleen some similar foci. Histological examination as in No. 104.

Diagnosis: No scurvy. The prim. musc., lymphgl. region.; lienis, hepatitis, pulmon., lymphgl. divers.

Conclusion for Series XXXIV: Strong reaction of well developed connective tissue in and around tuberculous foci.

No. 183.

♂. Brown—white—black.

From the day of arrival, $\frac{19}{3}$ (weight 310 grams), the animal persistingly twisted its head to the left and would run round. It was put on complete dietary as Series 2. Standstill in weight till $\frac{19}{4}$, when increase in weight followed. In the middle of May the above-mentioned symptom disappeared and the animal seemed afterwards to be well. Chloroformed and autopsied $\frac{8}{7}$. Liver 33.0 grams. Spleen 0.6 gram.

Histological examination as in No. 5 shows normal pictures in most organs. Kidney, p. 99. The nerves in the bend of the knees show considerable changes: axis-cylinders irregularly swollen, myelinic sheath irregularly segmented; here and there small hyperchromatic, spool — starshaped cells with rounded nuclei.

Diagnosis: Beriberi (?) peracta.

Series XXXV.

Animals 184—187. These were put on relative general inanition with full dose of antiscorbutic from Oct. 1, 1923. Each animal had its own cage and got a daily ration of 40 grams of chickweed and besides a dose of preserved orange juice. This was given to each animal with a pipet in a dose of 3 ccm., and besides 10 ccm. were put into the cage, which were not always consumed. Weight charts, Fig. 127. The animals retained their liveliness of movement almost to the last day.

No. 184. Black—brown—white.

Dead and autopsied $\frac{8}{10}$. Hair not coming off. Almost no fat. No sign of scurvy. Bones not brittle, teeth firm. Liver 11.0 grams, spleen 0.2 gram. Histological examination of 12 ribs, jaw, muscles, heart, liver, lung, shows no changes like those described for the scorbutic animals. Kidney, adrenal, salivary gland, spleen, show slight atrophic changes of the parenchymatous cells.

Diagnosis: Inanitio.

No. 185. White—brown.

Died and was autopsied $\frac{14}{10}$. Lean animal. No sign of scurvy. Histological examination as in No. 184. Also liver (nuclei) and heart (elastic membranes) show slight atrophic changes. Hemorrhage in the marrow of the adrenal.

Diagnosis: Inanitio.

No. 186.

♀. White—brown.

Died and was autopsied $\frac{10}{11}$. Findings and histological examination as in No. 185. Adrenal, Fig. 94.

Diagnosis: Inanitio.

No. 187.

♀. White—brown.

Died and was autopsied $7/10$. Hair easily loosening. Lean animal. The diaphyses of the long bones are somewhat too easily broken. No sign of scurvy. Two lymph-glands in the lower jaw with miliary abscesses. Histological examination as in No. 184. Only kidney and adrenal show slight atrophic changes of the parenchymatous cells.

Diagnosis: Inanition. Lymphadenit. ac. supp.

Conclusion for Series XXXV: With a dietary of about a third of that required for normal increase in weight, the animals lost in one to two weeks 29—36% of their initial weight. The lymphoid tissue of the spleen, the elastic membranes of the large vessels, the parenchymata of kidney, adrenal and liver showed slight atrophic changes.

Fig. 127. Series XXXV. Relative inanition.

Additional animals.

No. 188.

♂. Light brown—white.

Had from $1/10$ chickweed *ad lib.*, and was besides given 5 ccm. of preserved orange juice with pipet. Killed and autopsied $10/10$. Everywhere normal conditions, also at the histological examination as in No. 5. Tooth, Fig. 3.

Diagnosis: No scurvy.

No. 189. Black—brown.

From birth it has been fed on complete dietary by the breeder and seemed healthy when bought; weight 300 grams. Was killed immediately $1/10$ with chloroform and was autopsied. Examination as in No. 5 showed everywhere normal conditions. Radiograms of the ribs, Fig. 42 b.

Records belonging to Part IV, Chapter III.

Terms and abbreviations.

D 1, D 1—2, D 2, D 2—3, D 3, Dulness in five degrees.

Resp. respiration; *ves.* vesicular; *br.* bronchial.

R Râles.

Scl. fossa supraclavicularis; *I, II, III* etc. first, second, third etc. costal interstice; *ssp* fossa suprascapularis; *sp.* spina; *A* angulus scapulae; *1/2 A* halfway between *sp* and *A*.

Pat. 2/13 patient second among thirteen children.

Expect. expectoration.

Infl. ep. influenza epidemica.

Couple a.

1. Or.

Ernst Bernhard L-n, born 1890. Farmer. Odensala.

Anamnesis. Pat. $\frac{1}{13}$. Two brothers died of tbc. Was well till 1916, when he had pleuritis exsud. bilat. Afterwards subjectively well till the autumn of 1922; then cough, expectoration, breathlessness. The physician suspected the pulm. in December 1922. No night-sweat; appetite fairly bad, during the last few months no emaciation. Never hemoptysis, never pneumonia.

Admitted $\frac{3}{2}$ 1923. *Status* $\frac{6}{2}$: Constitution fairly good. Spare flesh. Moderate cough with moderate amount of expect. Stitching and stabbing pain. Appetite fairly good. Digestion and sleep good. Feels well. Pulse; about 100. Temperature: sub-febrile till $\frac{29}{4}$, afterwards 38—39° C. Stomach, nose, pharynx, larynx 0.

Local status: D 3 over both lungs with bronchial respiration. Diffuse R over both lungs. In the lower left side lobe an orange-sized cavity, in the upper right side lobe a smaller cavity. Tbc of Stage III. all over the lungs.

Extracts from records. $\frac{3}{3}$ orange. $\frac{20}{3}$: R lessened in the bases. The rest as before. $\frac{1}{5}$: as before, yet the left side cavity increased anteriorly. $\frac{29}{5}$: since three weeks the patient has constant headache with vomiting. Babinsky +, Oppenheim +, stomach reflex 0, foot clonus, dull pupillar reflexes. Kernig +. During the last weeks temporarily wandering in mind, during last days periods of sopor. † $\frac{29}{5}$. Meningitis tbc.

The bacilli always +. Examined every fortnight.

Summary: Tbc of Stage III. with cavities, which increase during the orange period (after 6 weeks). After 2 months meningitis tbc. Cyanotic from the first; dissuaded from sanatorium treatment, being considered a hopeless case.

Weight chart:

$\frac{4}{2}$ — 69 kg.	$\frac{1}{3}$ — 71 kg.	$\frac{31}{3}$ — 71.5 kg.	$\frac{1}{5}$ — 69.5 kg.
$\frac{15}{2}$ — 71 »	$\frac{14}{3}$ — 71.5 »	$\frac{14}{4}$ — 69.5 »	$\frac{29}{5}$ — †

2.

Erik Fridolf A-n, born $\frac{25}{6}$ 1891. Building carpenter. Ed.

Anamnesis: Pat. $\frac{2}{3}$. A maternal aunt died of tbc. pulm. One of the patient's 3 children died of tbc. mening. Well till the autumn of 1918, then infl. ep. with pneum. sin. After that periods of coughing. After January

1920 constant cough with expect. Nursed in the Väsby Hospital $16/3-20/4$ 1920 with the diagnosis of bronchitis. On $14/1$ 1923 acutely ill, fever, shiverings. Stabbing pain in left side, dyspnea. Admitted to the Väsby Hospital $16/1$. Diagnosis: tbc. bas. pulm. dx. with fever, gradually lowered.

Admitted to the Sanatorium $5/2$. Status: Deviatio septi nasi, hypertroph. concaë med. sin. For the rest 0.

Local status: D 3 over both lungs, except in lower front part of right side. Submetallic R over both lungs, except in the above-mentioned place. Respiration of slightly bronchial character in the upper halves of both lungs. Constitution good, flesh spare. Slight cough with rather inconsiderable expect. Stabbing pain, breathlessness. Appetite, sleep and digestion good. For the rest subjectively well.

Extracts from records. $26/3$ R fewer. Otherwise as before. $7/5$: Right lung, no R anteriorly; D and respiration as before; left lung, fewer R anteriorly. $2/6$: Feels well, out of bed without fever from this day.

Summary: Case of Stage III. without definite cavities (neither in clinical examination nor with Roentgen rays) and without fever; steadily improving.

Weight chart.	Quantity of sputum.
$7/2$ — 66.5 kg.	$6/2$ — 40 ccm.
$15/2$ — 67.5 "	$15/2$ — 30 "
$1/3$ — 68.5 "	$2/3$ — 40 "
$14/3$ — 69.5 "	$16/3$ — 50 "
$31/3$ — 70 "	$1/4$ — 30 "
$14/4$ — 72 "	$15/4$ — 30 "
$1/5$ — 72.5 "	$1/5$ — 45 "
$13/5$ — 73 "	$13/5$ — 30 "
$1/6$ — 73 "	$1/6$ — 15 "
$15/6$ — 73 "	$15/6$ — 25 "
$30/6$ — 74.5 "	$1/7$ — 25 "

Conclusion for Couple a: The case with orange treatment has had the less favourable progress.

Couple b.

3. Or.

Albert Nicolaus B-g, born $20/9$ 1887.

Anamnesis. Pat. $4/7$. No. 1 died of tbc. pulm. at the age of 19 in 1900. No. 3 died of tbc. osteomyelit. at the age of 16 in 1901. — In 1913 period of coughing for some months. Otherwise well till the autumn of 1918, then infl. ep. with relapse. Cough with expect. at least since March 1921. Since beginning of November 1921 constant cough. No hemoptysis? Was then taken ill, with stabbing pain in left side, fever. Not continuously in bed. Appetite bad; night-sweat. Tbc. pulm. stated in March 1921. Abusus aethylicus going on for a long time past.

Admitted $25/11$ 1921. Status $25/11$: Constitution good. Flesh somewhat spare. Moderate cough with moderate expect. No breathlessness. Appetite good. Right lung, D 3 scl-II, resp. there br. — br. ves.; hard R, a few—several, partly submetallic. Behind, ssp D 3, ssp to A, D 2—D 1, resp. weak, unclear and br. ves. R, same as in front. Left lung, corresponding parts D 1, resp. harsh, unclear, no R.

Weight:	Bacilli:
$25/11$ 1921 — 69.5 kg.	$11/12$ 1921 +
$28/2$ 1923 — 56.5 "	$6/8$ 1922 +

Pat. not weighed during the orange period.

Extracts from records. Progressing steadily downwards till $\frac{9}{2}$ 1923. Cough about the same as before. Expect. at times increased (more than 200 cem.), almost purulent. Continuous pain on both sides anteriorly. General condition worse. Status of lungs: over the greater part of both lungs resp. br., D 3 and metallic R. On $\frac{2}{3}$ orange. $\frac{27}{3}$: During last weeks diarrhea, abdominal pains. Attacks of dyspnea, weak pulse. Obj.: metallic R diffusely over both lungs. The last two days abdomen continuously distended, violent abdominal pain; vomiting, not faecal. Excessive tenderness diffusely all over the abdomen. Pulse very slight, quick; cold extremities. $\dagger \frac{27}{3}$.

Temper. about 38° till Jan. 1922, afterwards $38-40,4^\circ$; from $\frac{11}{2}$ — $\frac{25}{3}$ again about 38° .

Summary: Case in Stage III. with destruction of both lungs. Continually declining before the orange diet was begun. A week afterwards symptoms of tuberculous enterocolitis with supervening peritonitis.

4.

Bror Jakob Harry M-n, born $\frac{25}{9}$ 1900. Upholsterer, Vaxholm.

Anamnesis. Pat. $\frac{3}{4}$. No. 4 has had pleuritis. An uncle tbc pulm. 1919 the pat. had infl. ep. without complications. Enrolled for conscription in the spring of 1919, allowed respite on account of feeble constitution. Began military service in 1921. Well till beginning of April 1922, then cough and expect., since continued. Hemoptysis (about a table-spoonful) in July and Sept. 1922. In bed with fever up to 40° C. during April—May 1922. A physician stated bronchopneumonia. Afterwards about and in work again till Aug. 1922; in July a physician stated tbc. pulm. Temperature not taken for some time. Earlier night-sweat. Appetite generally good. Slight loss of flesh. Never pleuritis.

Admitted $\frac{11}{12}$ 22. *Status* $\frac{15}{12}$: Constitution somewhat feeble. Flesh spare. Coughs slightly with moderate expect. Appetite good. Digestion and sleep good. Feels well. Pulse: 96.

Local status: Upper halves of both lungs D 3, resp. on right side feeble, unclear, on left side br. ves. R on the right some—a few, medium—finer, posteriorly submetallic, anteriorly hard; R on the left some—a few, medium, submetallic. Both lower halves D 1—D 2, more on the right side, resp. there not quite clear, on left side ves. No R.

Extracts from records. $\frac{8}{1}$ 23: Resp. everywhere as before. D increased posteriorly in the bases. Slight cough with perhaps increased expect. Hemoptysis once since last examination (about 90 gr.). $\frac{26}{1}$: Since $\frac{15}{1}$ sensation of stabbing pain on the right side with rising temperature. Much increasing D over the right side base with hardly audible resp. Test puncture $\frac{22}{1}$. Result a somewhat turbid exudate. The bacilli $\frac{14}{12}$ +. *Local status* $\frac{26}{1}$: Left lung, R. audible all the way down both anteriorly and posteriorly, some—a few, medium, hard, in the upper half partly metallic; below A mixed with friction sounds. Resp. and D = $\frac{8}{1}$. Right lung, below A D 2 increasing downwards to absolute; three fingers' breadth below A to the limit of the lung resp. almost 0. Just above, occasional friction sounds. The rest = $\frac{8}{1}$. Cough during the last 24 hours trying, with inconsiderable expect. Feels fairly well. General condition as before. $\frac{9}{3}$: R in left lung and in upper half of right lung more metallic. In lower halves of both lungs friction sounds here and there (remains after ex. pleurit.). Cough and expect. as before. Feels well. Continuously in bed with fever. Condition of health declining. (Prognosis: mala.) $\frac{12}{4}$ status of lungs: 3 big cavities, one in the upper, one in the lower part of right lung; one cavity in the middle of the left lung. Cough and expectoration as before. General condition worse. Feels better than before! $\frac{1}{5}$: Since the last examination the general condition has declined steadily. During the

last days coarse partly metallic R diffusely over both lungs. All the right anterior side sibilant br. resp., metallic in the lower half. Since a few days intensely fetid, abundant sputa. In the last days pulse quick. Very slight dyspnea. † $1/5$.

Weight $11/12$ 1922 55 kg. Since then not weighed. Occasional traces of alb. During the last 4 months or more, remittent fever from $37-39^{\circ}$ C: the last fortnight with more than 3 degrees' variation a day.

Summary: Case in Stage III. with great virulence. In upper halves of both lungs incipient destruction. Quick progress towards death with large destruction setting in.

Conclusion for Couple b: In Case 3, the lessening of the power of resistance through aethylysm seems to have been conducive to the progress of the disease. In Case 4, similar progress.

Couple c.^a

5. Or.

Karl Erik B-g, born $18/5$ 1902. Farm-owner's son. Vaddö.

Anamnesis. Pat. $5/6$. One brother died of tbc. pulm. In 1918, after infl. ep. periods of cough, constant fatigue. Cough and expect. after Oct. 1920; stabbing pain in left side. Physician diagnosed pleurit. sicca sin. and tbc. pulm. in Dec. 1920. Nursed in the Serafimerlasarettet, Dec. 1920. Attempts at Forlanini. Nursed in the Hälshult Sanatorium $14/2$ 1921— $18/6$ 1922. Was out of bed there, without fever, all the time. Forlanini attempts with negative result. Hemoptysis $1/2$ litre in Aug., the same in Oct. 1921. Appetite bad, almost continual loss of flesh; since 1920 in all 10 kg.

Admitted $15/12$. *Status* $18/12$: Constitution fairly good, flesh spare, moderate cough with moderate expectoration. Appetite fairly good. Other organs 0. Status of lungs: Chiefly affected on the left side. Right lung D 1 and D 2 in the apex, resp. unclear, interscapular R anteriorly and posteriorly. Left lung, all D 3, R metallic covering the resp. sounds.

Extracts from records. $27/1$ 23: On the whole the same status of lungs. R possibly somewhat lessened. Feels well. Less cough with less expect. $1/3$ an orange a day. $10/3$: No R anteriorly on right side, appetite better (subj.), been out of bed without fever since then. Pleuropericarditis (slight symptoms) as when admitted. $20/4$: Local status unchanged. Cough inconsiderable, feels much better, but has not put on flesh. Bacilli all the time. Temperature afebrile all the time. Forlanini attempts without any marked effect on $26/5$. Afterwards status quo in the lungs.

Weight chart:

$1/3$ — 70 kg.	$15/4$ — 70 kg.	$1/6$ — 68.5 kg.
$15/3$ — 70 "	$1/5$ — 70 "	$15/6$ — 67.5 "
$1/4$ — 70 "	$15/5$ — 68.5 "	$30/6$ — 68 "

Quantity of sputum:

$1/3$ — $15/5$ — 90 ccm.
$1/6$ — $15/6$ — 50 "

Summary: Case in Stage III., practically one-sided, with cavities on the left side. After orange diet, local status improved on both sides, also appetite improved.

6.

Nils Bertil B-n, born $16/11$ 1906. Errand-boy. Spånga.

Anamnesis. Pat. $3/5$. No tbc. in the family. Well till 1919, when infl. ep. Coughing in wintertime for a couple of years. Constant cough with expect.

in the autumn of 1922. Never hemoptysis. Last week night-sweat. Tbc. pulm. diagnosed in Jan. In the Mörby Hospital $17/1-18/2$. Two Forlanini attempts there, 100 and 160 ccm. Thin, but not losing flesh.

Admitted $22/2$ 23. Status: Constitution lank. Habitus phthisicus. Flesh spare. Coughs slightly with inconsiderable expect. Appetite, digestion, sleep good. Local status: Right lung, D 1 and D 2 in the apex, resp. unclear. No R. Chiefly affected on the left side. Left lung, upper half D 3, the rest D 2. Resp. of slightly bronchial character in the apex. Otherwise enfeebled and unclear. R metallic in the apex. Smaller changes than Case 4, but on the whole similar. Other organs 0. Roentgen $27/2$: All the left lung completely filled with foci. Small cavities at the top. Pneumo-thorax treatment continued (up to 500 ccm.). Apex adherent.

Extracts from records. $1/7$: Continued decline. Appetite lessened. R occurring in right lung — gradually progressing. Temp. afebrile. Bacilli found before admittance, but not at Väsby till $27/5$.

Weight chart:

$22/2$ — 63 kg.	$14/4$ — 66.5 kg.	$1/6$ — 65.5 kg.
$1/3$ — 63.5 »	$1/5$ — 67.5 »	$15/6$ — 66.5 »
$14/3$ — 64 »	$15/5$ — 66.5 »	$30/6$ — 66 »
$31/3$ — 66 »		

Quantity of sputum:

$23/2$ — 5 ccm.	$4/3$ — 30 ccm.	$1/5$ — 5 ccm.
$24/2$ — 10 »	$16/3$ — 15 »	$15/5$ — 15 »
$25/2$ — 15 »	$1/4$ — 10 »	$1/6$ — 30 »
$26/2$ — 15 »	$15/4$ — 10 »	$15/6$ — 30 »
$2/3$ — 30 »		

Summary: Case of Stage III., practically unilateral, with cavities on the left side. Grown worse during the stay in the hospital.

Conclusion for Couple c: The orange case has progressed more favourably.

Couple d.

7. Or.

Frans August H-g, born $14/10$ 1870. Married, joiner. Spånga.

Anamnesis. Pat. $2/2$. Sister died of tbc pulm., 40 years ago. Stepmother died of tbc pulm. Has 7 half-brothers and -sisters; 2 of them died of tbc pulm. Married since 1898. Five children, one of them died with sequelae of pertussis. Always well till 1918, then infl. ep.; in bed with high fever for a week, did not summon a physician. Cough and expect. Sept. 1921. Underwent operation in the middle of March 1922 for abdominal tumour (not ca.). Shortly before, tbc. pulm. has been stated. After this nursed in the Serafimerlasarettet for pneumonia bilat. $21/2-24/5$ 1922. Appetite bad since 4 to 5 years back. Losing flesh. Fever from the middle of March to July 1922.

Admitted $12/12$ 22. Status $20/12$: Constitution perhaps somewhat weak. Flesh spare. Inconsiderable cough and hardly any expect. No stabbing pain; breathlessness when moving. Appetite now fairly good. Digestion and sleep fairly good. Feels rather well. Cor: dull sounds. Syst. accompaniments over aorta? For the rest 0. Right lung, Sc-I and Ssp D 1, resp. not quite clear. IV—VI D 3, resp. weak, unclear. R laterally from the mammailla and downwards, isolated to a few medium hard. Below A D 3, resp. enfeebled, unclear, slightly bronchial in the depth. Left lung, upper part to III and rather more than $1/2$ A D 3—2, diminishing downwards, resp. br.-ves. R in these

areas some—a few, medium—finer, hard. In the lower part resp. very harsh, unclear. Bacilli not examined, as 0 exp. $^{22/12}$ 22 and $^{14/5}$ 23.

Extracts from records. $^{1/2}$: In the left apex only occasional R. Otherwise 0. Right lung, accompaniments diminished. Otherwise as before. Hardly any cough, feels fairly well. $^{2/3}$: an orange a day. $^{15/3}$: Resp. and D everywhere as before. R in toto considerably diminished, in extension as well as in number and degree. $^{27/4}$: Accompaniments are heard only in the right lung below A isolated — a few, finer, and in the left lung I—II. Almost no cough at all. No expect. Feels well. Appetite about as before. $^{14/5}$: Status of lungs = $^{27/4}$. Coughs occasionally with hardly any expect. Feels well. Appetite the whole time, and especially of late, excellent. Has been afebrile. Discharged on $^{15/5}$.

Summary: Case in Stage II. to III., which locally and generally has considerably improved.

Weight chart:

$^{16/12}$ — 57 kg.	$^{15/2}$ — 61 kg.	$^{15/4}$ — 63.5 kg.
$^{30/12}$ — 57 "	$^{1/3}$ — 62 "	$^{1/5}$ — 64 "
$^{15/1}$ — 59 "	$^{15/3}$ — 62.5 "	$^{15/5}$ — 64.2 "
$^{1/2}$ — 60 "	$^{1/4}$ — 62.5 "	

8.

Sven N-n, born $^{15/6}$ 1875. Night-watchman. Huvudsta.

Anamnesis. Pat. $^{3/3}$. 4 children. Generally well till the spring of 1919, then infl. ep. followed by bronchitis; in bed for two weeks. Since then sometimes cough with inconsiderable expect. $^{15/9}$ 21 hemoptysis (about $^{1/2}$ litre). Physician diagnosed tbc. pulm. Appetite fairly good. No loss of flesh.

Admitted $^{21/2}$ 23. *Status* $^{24/2}$: Constitution fairly good. Flesh spare. Height 180 cm. Weight 72 kg. Slight cough in the morning. No stabbing pain, no breathlessness. Appetite good, bowel sluggish. Sleep fairly good; feels well.

Local status: Right lung, scl-II and ssp-A D 1. Resp. weak, unclear. In the base resp. unclear; a few finer hard R. Left lung, scl—IV D 2, ssp—A D 2. Resp. weak, unclear; isolated — a few fine hard R; in the base resp. not quite clear. Pharynx and larynx show diffuse redness.

Extracts from records. $^{7/4}$: Nowhere R or accompaniments. Coughs unfrequently, almost without expectoration. Feels well. $^{19/5}$: Nowhere R or accompaniments. Never coughs, no expect. Feels well. Bacilli looked for $^{27/2}$, $^{13/3}$, and $^{10/4}$, without being found. Temperature afebrile.

Weight chart:

$^{21/2}$ — 72.5 kg.	$^{1/4}$ — 77 kg.	$^{15/5}$ — 80 kg.
$^{1/3}$ — 74.5 "	$^{15/4}$ — 78.5 "	$^{22/5}$ — 82.2 "
$^{15/3}$ — 76 "	$^{1/5}$ — 78 "	

Summary: Case in Stage I.—II. Locally and generally improved.

Conclusion for Couple d: Both considerably improved, the orange case most.

Couple e.

9. Or.

Josefina A-k, born $^{5/9}$ 1879. Wife of a filer.

Anamnesis. Pat. $^{1/1}$. Well till 1905, when diphtheria. In 1919 pneumonia sin. after infl. ep. Nursed 3 months in the Serafimerlasarettet. Con-

tinuous cough and expect. since May 22. In July the same year hemoptysis (about 1 table-spoonful). Physician stated tbc. pulm. Then 1 month in bed with fever up to 39° C. In September another period of heightened temperature up to 38° C. No night-sweat. Appetite generally good. Lost 4 kg. since last July.

Admitted ¹⁸/₁ 23. *Status* ²¹/₁ 23: Constitution and flesh fairly good. Coughs moderately with inconsiderable expect. Occasionally stabbing pain in left side. Breathlessness when moving. Appetite, digestion, sleep, fairly good. Feels rather well.

Right lung: D 2 in scl-III, ssp—A. Resp in upper parts harsh, unclear, below III. and A harsh, prolonged expirium. R scl—II and ssp—A, a few finer hard R, mixed with rhonchi. *Left lung*: D 1—D 2 in the apex with resp. harsh, unclear, D 3 from ¹/₂ A and downwards anteriorly; here resp. enfeebled, unclear, posteriorly br.-ves. Lower half of left lung, R hard, medium, some—a few.

²/₃: an orange daily.

Weight chart:

¹⁸ / ₁ — 70 kg.	¹⁵ / ₃ — 73.5 kg.	¹ / ₅ — 76.5 kg.
¹ / ₂ — 72 »	³¹ / ₈ — 74 »	¹⁵ / ₅ — 77 »
¹⁵ / ₂ — 72 »	¹⁴ / ₄ — 75 »	²⁰ / ₅ — 79 »
¹ / ₃ — 73.5 »		

Extracts from records. ⁴/₃ Right lung, no R. Left lung as before. Cough and expect. about as before. Feels well. ¹⁵/₄ Right lung, no R. Left lung anteriorly no R. Laterally to the left and ¹/₂ A all the way down a few hard R. Dry cough sometimes. Feels well. Temp. afebrile. ²⁹/₅ Resp. and D everywhere as before. Left lung, anteriorly no R, posteriorly to the right isolated R in different places interscapularly. Right lung, ssp and downwards isolated hard R; anteriorly Scl—II = posteriorly. Coughs sometimes, without expect. Feeling well. No Roentgen ex. ³⁰/₅. Discharged.

No tbc bacilli found ²⁰/₁, ³⁰/₁, ¹⁴/₂, ³/₅, ¹⁵/₅.

Summary: Case in Stage III. Left lung more gravely attacked, without sure destruction. Locally and generally, considerable improvement.

10.

Maria Valborg L-n, born ²⁹/₁₂ 1889. Wife of game-keeper, Nacka.

Anamnesis. Pat. ³/₁₀. Married since 1905. A cousin tbc. Three children ¹/₂—7 years. Nervous debility when growing up. In 1913 nursed in the Sabbatsberg Hospital for renal hemorrhage during 19 days. Tired in the mornings, but otherwise well, till 1921, when bronchial catarrh. Afterwards periods of cough and expect., at times blood-imbibed sputa. Temp. during the last months on the verge of subfebrile. Appetite fairly good. Hardly any losing of flesh. After partus in July 1922 affection of apex was suspected by physician. Sanatorium treatment was advised in October.

Admitted ²/₂ 23. *Status*: ⁶/₃ Constitution and flesh good. Coughs occasionally with hardly any expect. No stabbing pain. No breathlessness. Appetite, digestion, sleep good. Feels well. Pharynx and larynx: inconsiderable diffuse redness, mucous coating.

Local status: Right, scl sunk, resp. enfeebled, unclear, in both apices scl—II, D 1—D 2, more on left side. No R. Left, below II. anteriorly and posteriorly resp. everywhere weaker than in the right lung.

Extracts from records. ²⁰/₂ Roentgen ex. shows slight changes, peribronchitic shadows possibly too dark on left side. ²⁰/₃: Nowhere R or accompaniments. Coughs sometimes with inconsiderable expect. ⁴/₅: Lung status as

before. Never coughs. No expect. Feels well. Temp. afebrile. No bacilli found in examinations $^{14/2}$, $^{13/3}$, $^{10/4}$, and $^{3/4}$.

Weight chart:

$^{2/2}$ — 66 kg.	$^{15/3}$ — 71 kg.	$^{15/4}$ — 73 kg.
$^{15/2}$ — 68 »	$^{1/4}$ — 71 »	$^{1/5}$ — 73.5 »
$^{1/3}$ — 70 »		

Summary: Case in Stage I.—II., with good general condition. Lung-status not changed; general condition, good on arrival, still somewhat improved.

Conclusion for Couple e: Case 9 has larger extent than Case 10, but virulence and conditions seem to be similar. Greater improvement of the orange case.

Couple f.

11. Or.

Elsa Elis. S-m, born $^{17/9}$ 1894. Bookbinder, Sundbyberg.

Anamnesis. Pat. $^{1/5}$. No tbc in the family. Morbilli at the age of 5 with bronchitis and eye complications. Since that time often suffering from colds. Otherwise well till Oct. 1919. Afterwards weakly, tired, sometimes febrile. Cough and expect. after this time. No hemoptysis, periodically fever since Nov. 1920, night-sweat, emaciation, appetite constantly bad since a year back. During alternate periods sluggish bowels and diarrhea. No menses since 2 months back. Physician stated tbc. in Nov. 1920. Nursed in the Sundbyberg almshouse in May 1922. There thrombophlebitis.

Admitted $^{30/9}$ 22. *Status:* Constitution fairly good, flesh beneath the average, moderate cough with abundant expect. Breathlessness. Appetite fairly good.

Lung status: The upper halves of both lungs D 3, br. resp. and metallic R, the lower parts resp. harsh, unclear, no R. Right lung posteriorly with weak D 1. Larynx: the right vocal chord and ventricular ligament slightly reddened. Other organs 0. Pulse 100.

Weight chart:

$^{1/3}$ — 53.5 kg.	$^{14/4}$ — 54 kg.	$^{1/6}$ — 55 kg.
$^{15/3}$ — 53.5 »	$^{1/5}$ — 54.5 »	$^{15/6}$ — 54.5 »
$^{31/3}$ — 53 »	$^{15/5}$ — 54.5 »	$^{30/6}$ — 54 »

Quantity of sputum:

$^{1/3}$ — $^{1/6}$ — 100 ccm.	$^{15/6}$ — 80 ccm.	$^{30/6}$ — 80 ccm.
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Extracts from records. $^{15/12}$: Lung status idem. $^{26/1}$: diffuse bronchitis. $^{3/3}$: An orange daily. $^{9/3}$: Lung status idem. Bacilli $^{2/11}$ +. No bacilli found $^{10/4}$ and $^{20/4}$. $^{20/4}$: R somewhat lessened, everything else idem. Larynx: the right vocal chord and ventricular ligament infiltrated, a small granulation on the back wall. Appetite relatively good. Bowels irregular, sometimes diarrhea. $^{2/6}$: R in toto somewhat lessened, especially anteriorly on the right side. Otherwise as $^{20/4}$. General condition improved in spite of symptoms from the bowels the whole time; larynx the same. Temp. constantly subfebrile. Cough minimal.

Summary: Case in Stage III. Cavity symptoms in the upper halves of both lungs; when admitted inconsiderable symptoms from larynx and the bowels, thrombophlebitis not quite gone. Much improved during the orange diet.

12.

Axelina Maria L-n, born $^{14}/_{12}$ 1895. Servant girl. Lidingön.

Anamnesis. Pat. $^1/_8$. Tbc. in the family. Served, when 17 years old, in a family where there was a case of manifest tbc. Has a healthy, 3 years old child. In 1919 after infl. ep. weakly. Coughed, had expect., sometimes blood-imbibed. Partus in April. Nursed in St. Erik's Hospital in June 1919, in the Söderby Hospital Oct. 1919—Febr. 20. Out of bed without fever till May 22. Nursed for ileus in the Serafimerlasarettet in May 22. Afterwards again cough, expect. and fever up to 39° C. After op. the whole time bad appetite and night-sweat. Tbc. stated in April 1919.

Admitted $^{20}/_{10}$ 22. *Status*: General condition without remark, flesh spare. Troublesome cough with abundant expect. Breathlessness. Appetite rather bad. Bowels often irregular; pain and often nausea, sometimes diarrhea. Pulse 100. Other organs 0.

Local status: In the upper right and lower left parts D 3, br. resp. and metallic R. Otherwise on the right below, feeble, unclear resp. In the upper left part, D 2 and hard, not metallic R.

Extracts from records. $^{11}/_{12}$: R slightly lessened, cough troublesome as before. $^{22}/_{1}$: Resp. br. also in the upper left parts with a few metallic R. $^6/_3$: Status idem. Cough troublesome, increased expect. Feels tired. Loss in weight. $^{18}/_{4}$: Status quo. Increased expect. No symptoms from the bowels. General condition less satisfactory. $^{31}/_{5}$: R on right lung somewhat increased. R also below A. R metallic all over the left lung. General condition worse.

Weight chart:

$^1/_3$ — 47.5 kg. $^5/_3$ — 47 kg. $^{31}/_3$ — 45.5 kg.

Quantity of sputum:

$^1/_3$ — 100 ccm. $^{15}/_4$ — 300 ccm. $^{15}/_5$ — 350 ccm.
 $^{15}/_3$ — 250 " $^1/_5$ — 300 " $^{30}/_6$ — 300 "
 $^1/_4$ — 300 "

Summary: Case in Stage III. with complications from larynx and bowels. Cavity symptoms in all the left lung and in upper parts of the right lung. Generally and locally declining.

Conclusion for Couple f: The orange case shows the more satisfactory progress.

Couple g.

13. Or.

Emilia Josefina K-n, born $^{11}/_8$ 1896. Housekeeper. Tureberg.

Anamnesis: Pat. $^7/_10$. No tbc. in family. Well till 7 years ago when fatigue set in. Examined and nursed for a few weeks in the Väsby Hospital for catarrh in the left apex. Cough and expect. in periods since Jan. 1922. Once blood-imbibed sputa. Appetite generally good. Lost flesh during the last 2 years. Fever since 3 weeks back, $38-40^{\circ}$ C. Night-sweat.

Status $^{24}/_9$: General constitution without remark. Flesh spare, moderate cough with moderate expect. No stabbing pain, no obvious breathlessness. Appetite, sleep, digestion good, feels a little tired; frequent and abundant menses. Pulse 92.

Right lung: D 1—D 2 in the upper half, resp. unclear, harsh, R isolated, finer. *Left lung*: D 3 in rather more than the upper half, to III and near A, with br. resp. and metallic R. Below D 1—D 2, resp. anteriorly enfeebled,

posteriorly unclear. R in the first-mentioned area some—several, medium—coarse, submetallic—metallic; about A and laterally R isolated finer, hard.

Extracts from records. ⁵/₁₀: Roentgen. Left lung almost filled with small indurations (tbc.—looking foci). Right lung: from hilus laterally, mostly downwards, similar foci, but not so close together. In the left apex a few small cavities. ¹⁸/₁₀: Attempts at pneumothorax on left lung, without effect. ⁴/₁₁: Right lung, upper half, irregular accompaniments. Left lung, about the same as before. The first successful insufflation (I) on the left side. ⁷/₁₁: II insufflation. ⁸/₁₁: III insufflation. ¹¹/₁₁: IV. ¹⁵/₁₁: V. ²⁰/₁₁: VI.

Bacilli: ²⁵/₉ ++. ⁵/₁₂ +. ²⁷/₄ +. ²⁷/₅ +.

Weight chart:

²¹ / ₉ — 55.5 kg.	¹ / ₁₂ — 56 kg.	¹⁵ / ₂ — 58 kg.	¹⁴ / ₄ — 58 kg.
³⁰ / ₉ — 56.5 »	¹⁵ / ₁₂ — 57 »	¹ / ₃ — 57.5 »	¹ / ₅ — 58 »
¹⁴ / ₁₀ — 56.5 »	³⁰ / ₁₂ — 56 »	¹⁵ / ₃ — 57 »	¹⁵ / ₅ — 58 »
¹ / ₁₁ — 57.5 »	¹ / ₂ — 57 »	³¹ / ₃ — 57 »	¹ / ₆ — 57.5 »

²⁰/₁₁: laterally in the upper part of right lung a large tbc focus (Roentgen rays), not compressed.

²⁴/₁₁: VII.; physical signs as before. ²⁷/₁₁: VIII. ⁴/₁₂: IX. ⁹/₁₂: X.

Roentgen: »Left lung: laterally in lower half pneumothorax rather large. No exudate. Right lung: tbc foci as before.» Physically the lower half flat. No resp., no R. For the rest everywhere resp. audible and a few medium R. Right lung: in some places isolated accompaniments.

¹⁸/₁₂: owing to the delicate state of the patient no insufflations have been undertaken. The temperature has risen to 39—40° C. R audible all over the right side anteriorly, in the upper half posteriorly. R extended over right lung, in spite of partial pneumothorax. ⁸/₁ 23: over the upper part of both lungs D 3 down to IV on the right, VI on the left and A posteriorly, resp. more or less br. over the scapulae with bronchophony. R metallic. Cough somewhat lessened but with increased expect. General condition as before. ²¹/₂: right lung anteriorly I—III resp. almost br. Left lung anteriorly I—III resp. amphoric, posteriorly R metallic all the way down. Lung status otherwise as on ⁸/₁. Purulent, somewhat increased expect. Since ¹³/₂ rising temperature up to nearly 40° C, now again sinking. General condition improved. ²/₃: an orange a day. ⁵/₄: right lung, R, some, medium, are heard over the whole anterior area and ssp to near A. Left lung, R in toto somewhat diminished. Otherwise as on ⁸/₁. Feels very much better than before. Temp. subfebrile, more steady. Somewhat less cough with less expect. ¹⁸/₅: Right lung below IV no R. Otherwise as before, yet resp. I—III with br. touch. Posteriorly as before; iscp resp. with br. touch. Left lung, R in toto lessened. Otherwise same as on ⁸/₁. Cough somewhat easier with plenty of expect. Feels fairly well. General condition as before. In bed during the greater part of the day with subfebrile temp. ¹/₆: on some places anteriorly a few R I—III, almost metallic. Posteriorly iscp some few, medium, hard R, partly submetallic. Otherwise nothing abnormal. Left lung: R in toto somewhat lessened, especially anteriorly. Otherwise as on ⁸/₁. Cough troublesome with plenty of expect. Temp. during the last month 37.5—38.5. Pulse 84. Sent home at her own request.

Summary: Case in Stage III., with the gravest changes in the upper part of the left lung. Clinical cavity symptoms confirmed by Roentgen examination. Large foci also in the right lung, yet Roentgen rays show no cavity. Partial pneumothorax in the beginning of November, followed by an aggravation especially of local manifestations in the less affected lung; improvement from February, before the orange cure was begun, and onwards during this cure, the patient growing much better, both locally and generally.

14.

Vivi Margit Constance G-t., born $^{25}/_{10}$ 03. Dressmaker. Nynäshamn.
Anamnesis: Pat. $^{1}/_{3}$. No tbc in the family. Often tired and infirm since childhood. Easily catching colds. At the age of 10 operated upon for adenoid. The pulm. bilat. stated in 1917. Autumn 1918 infl. ep. Later on periods of coughing and increased expect. No hemoptysis. Never night-sweat, fever. Appetite generally fairly good. Nursed at the Hälshult Sanatorium $^{28}/_{5}$ 21— $^{23}/_{9}$ 22. Forlanini for 9 months; during this time loss of flesh. Afterwards at home.

Admitted $^{16}/_{12}$ 22. *Status:* general constitution fairly good. Flesh below the average. Coughs moderately with inconsiderable expect. Breathlessness. Appetite, digestion, sleep good. Feels well. Everything else all right.

Local status: the upper halves of both lungs D 3. Resp. br., metallic R. On the left, posteriorly and downwards D 1 with occasional finer R.

Extracts from records. $^{2}/_{2}$: status idem. $^{15}/_{3}$: lung status idem. Feeling well. $^{27}/_{4}$: idem. $^{10}/_{5}$: idem. $^{9}/_{6}$: lung status as on $^{15}/_{3}$. Coughs a little with slight expect. Appetite bad during last month. Temp. afebrile. Tbc bacilli: $^{17}/_{12}$ —; $^{5}/_{1}$ +; $^{3}/_{5}$ — and $^{16}/_{5}$ +.

Weight chart:

$^{1}/_{3}$	—	48.5	kg.
$^{15}/_{3}$	—	49.5	»
$^{31}/_{3}$	—	49	»
$^{14}/_{4}$	—	49.3	»
$^{1}/_{5}$	—	49	»
$^{15}/_{5}$	—	48	»
$^{1}/_{6}$	—	48	»
$^{15}/_{6}$	—	47.5	»
$^{30}/_{6}$	—	47.5	»

Quantity of sputum:

$^{1}/_{3}$	—	15	cem.
$^{15}/_{3}$	—	15	»
$^{1}/_{4}$	—	5	»
$^{15}/_{4}$	—	5	»
$^{1}/_{5}$	—	15	»
$^{15}/_{5}$	—	15	»
$^{1}/_{6}$	—	15	»
$^{15}/_{6}$	—	15	»
$^{30}/_{6}$	—	25	»

Summary: Case in Stage III. Cavities in all the left and in the upper right lung. General condition inconsiderably improved. Lung status the same. All the time without fever, has been out of bed.

Conclusion for Couple g: Case 14 is more stationary and has less virulence than Case 13, which shows a greater improvement.

Couple h.

15. Or.

Elin Hildegard S-I: born $^{4}/_{10}$ 1880. Wife of a labourer. Täby.

Anamnesis: No tbc in the family. At the age of 19 servant in a house, where there was tbc in infectious stage. Married at 20. Husband alcoholic. 5 children, $2^{1}/_{2}$ —9 years. At 21 erythema nodosum.

Hemoptysis, after a year's coughing, early in 1916. Two periods of nursing in the Väsbj Hospital, July 1916—Jan. 1917, Dec. 1917—May 1918. The first period: right lung scl D 1—D 2, ssp—A, D 3—D 2; left lung scl—III, D 3—D 2, ssp—A D 1. In these areas numerous small—medium, hard R. The second period: signs of destruction in the upper halves of both lungs.

When dismissed the second time, $^{4}/_{5}$ 18, weight 64.3, sputum + tbc. Since then she has been working continuously and felt fairly well, but with periods of fever, 38—39° C, which has disappeared after a few days in bed. Cough at periods troublesome, sputa often tinged with blood. Lately bad appetite, gripes and nausea. A tbc swelling on the sternum. Operated. Advised renewed sanatorium treatment in May 1922.

Admitted $21/12$ 22. Constitution weakly, very thin. Coughs slightly with inconsiderable expect. No breathlessness; appetite fairly bad. Digestion troublesome, often gripes and nausea. Sleep good, but sweating at night.

Local status: The upper halves of both lungs D 3; br. resp. and metallic R. Pulse 88.

Extracts from records. $6/2$: R rather decreased. $1/3$: one orange a day. $21/3$: left lung considerably improved, less R. Right lung as before. Cough lessened with expect. as before. Digestion now all right. $22/5$: right lung, R only in I—II. The same as before posteriorly. Left lung, anteriorly lessened R, posteriorly the same. Cough, expect. somewhat decreased. Feeling fairly well. Open-air resting, walks. Bacilli $22/12$ and in later examinations +.

Weight chart:

$1/3$ — 54 kg.
$15/3$ — 54.5 »
$31/3$ — 54.5 »
$14/4$ — 55 »
$1/5$ — 55 »
$15/5$ — 55 »
$1/6$ — 55.5 »
$15/6$ — 56 »
$31/6$ — 55.5 »

Quantity of sputum:

$1/3$ — 75 cem.
$15/3$ — 75 »
$1/4$ — 50 »
$15/4$ — 125 »
$1/5$ — 100 »
$15/5$ — 100 »
$1/6$ — 100 »
$15/6$ — 80 »
$30/7$ — 80 »

Summary: Case in Stage III. Cavity symptoms in the upper halves of both lungs. Generally and locally improved (generally already before having the orange).

16.

Brita Märta G-n, born $17/12$ 89. Wife of an engine-driver.

Anamnesis: Pat. $1/1$. No tbc in family. Two healthy children. Ulcus ventriculi three times, last time in 1919, nursed in St. Maria's Hospital. Autumn 1918 infl. ep. Nursed in the Sabbatsberg Hospital for salpingitis. Two abortions, in 1919 and Nov. 1922. Pertussis March—April 1920. In May hemoptysis (150 gr.). Slight hemoptysis in May 1922. During a year continuous cough with expect. Breathless, tired. Appetite good all the time. Inconsiderable losing of flesh. No night-sweat. Tbc stated in July 1922.

Admitted $9/1$ 23. *Status:* constitution fairly good. Flesh somewhat spare. Coughs slightly with inconsiderable expect. Slight breathlessness when moving. Digestion troublesome, can not support food; digestion difficult. Sleep good; feeling well. Pulse 90. Other organs without remark (inconsiderable resistance on the left side of the pelvis [salpingitis] + fluor). *Local status:* slight changes diffusely over both lungs, D 1—D 2, changed, nowhere br. resp., in some places isolated hard R.

Extracts from records. $23/2$: At the beginning of the month in bed, temp. risen, stabbing pain in right iscp. Increased cough and expect. Obj. D 3, br. resp. and metallic R in the upper part of the right lung anteriorly and posteriorly. In other places fewer R, otherwise the same. $7/4$: Right iscp, accompaniments not so hard. Coughs occasionally, now without expect. Feeling well. $19/5$: right lung posteriorly again as $23/2$. Left lung, nothing. Coughs hardly ever. No expect. Feeling well. $2/6$: lung status the same, except that laterally on the right there are now numerous fine, medium R. No cough, no expect. Feeling well. Afebrile. Roentgen $12/2$ 22: three cavities in I, II and III, respectively, the largest in III. Pronounced peribronchitic changes. Left lung: from hilus outwards peribronchitis. Bacilli $20/3$ +, $10/4$ and $8/5$ —, $14/5$ +. Temp. afebrile.

Weight chart:

$\frac{1}{3}$	— 65 kg.
$\frac{15}{3}$	— 65 »
$\frac{21}{3}$	— 66 »
$\frac{14}{4}$	— 66.5 »
$\frac{1}{5}$	— 67 »
$\frac{15}{5}$	— 65.5 »
$\frac{1}{6}$	— 68 »

Quantity of sputum:

$\frac{1}{3}$	— 15 ccm.
$\frac{15}{3}$	— 65 »
$\frac{1}{4}$	— 5 »
$\frac{15}{4}$	— 10 »
$\frac{1}{5}$	— 5 »
$\frac{15}{5}$	— 0 »

Summary: Case in Stage II. and soon (before the beginning of the experiment) III. Cough, expectoration, weight and subjective condition improved during this time. Lung status aggravated.

Conclusion for Couple h: Case 16 shows a less good result than Case 15.

Couple i.

17. Or.

Hilda L-m, born $\frac{28}{8}$ 98. House-maid. Danderyd.

Anamnesis: Pat. $\frac{1}{10}$. One brother, No. 5, dead of meningitis. No tbc in family otherwise. Always well till Jan. 22. Caught cold, got fever, in bed for two weeks. Since then continuous cough and expect. Aug.—Oct. 22 slight hemoptyses, 1 tea-spoonful—1 table-spoonful. Physician stated tbc pulm. in Aug. 22. No emaciation. Hoarse since childhood.

Admitted $\frac{21}{2}$ 23. *Status:* $\frac{25}{2}$: constitution and flesh fairly good. Coughs slightly with inconsiderable expect. Appetite, digestion, sleep fairly good. Feels rather well. Cor: systolic accompaniment all over, the max. in the base. Pulm. II acc. Inconsiderable diffuse reddening in the larynx. Vocal cords, nothing. *Lung status:* right lung, scl and ssp D 3, below to II and A D 2. Resp. anteriorly harsh, unclear; posteriorly br. ves.-br. tinge. Below II resp. not quite clear. Isolated accompaniments. In ssp some few sub-metallic R. Anteriorly in scl—II and posteriorly below sp some few fine hard R. Left lung: scl—II and ssp—well above $\frac{1}{2}$ A D 1—D 2, resp. unclear, harsh. Around sp a number of finer, hard R. In scl isolated fine, hard R. Below II and A resp. harsh.

Extract from records: $\frac{8}{4}$: right lung anteriorly as before. Posteriorly, R are heard not quite as far as A. Otherwise as before. Left lung idem. Coughs occasionally with inconsiderable, lessened expect. $\frac{28}{5}$: lungs, status quo. Coughs occasionally without expect. $\frac{4}{6}$: R are only heard on the right $\frac{1}{2}$ A—A and on the left in ssp. Otherwise nothing. Resp. and D as before. Coughs occasionally. Hardly any expect. Suspicious of lighter clothing. Strange mind. Eats plenty, good appetite. Wishing to leave. Has got a bed in another sanatorium. Temp. afebrile. Sputum examined $\frac{27}{2}$ + and $\frac{27}{5}$ —.

Weight chart:

$\frac{21}{1}$	— 67 kg.	$\frac{31}{3}$	— 65.5 kg.	$\frac{15}{5}$	— 65 kg.
$\frac{1}{3}$	— 67 »	$\frac{14}{4}$	— 66 »	$\frac{1}{6}$	— 63.5 »
$\frac{15}{3}$	— 66 »	$\frac{1}{5}$	— 65 »		

Summary: Case in Stage III with changes in both apices, trace of destruction on the left. Open tbc. Distinct improvement all the time in spite of decreasing weight. Pharyngolaryngitis chron.

18.

Knut L-g, born $\frac{13}{1}$ 02. Farm labourer. Adelsö.

Anamnesis: Pat. $\frac{5}{5}$. A sister dead of tbc in 1915. Otherwise no tbc in family. Well till Jan. 21, then cough, expect., breathlessness, emaciation

and night-sweat. Temp. not taken. Never hemoptysis. The pulm. stated in May 21. Nursed at Hamra $^{29}/_8$ 21— $^{22}/_7$ 22. Sometimes in bed with a temperature, generally without fever and about.

Admitted $^{10}/_{10}$ 22. Status $^{12}/_{10}$: constitution fairly good, flesh below the average. Sometimes stabbing pain in the right side posteriorly. Breathlessness when moving. Appetite, digestion, sleep good. Feeling well.

Local status: The upper half of right lung and the lower third of left lung D 3, resp. br. ves., harsh, unclear; a moderate number of medium, hard, partly metallic R. Other parts, isolated fine R (catarrhal).

Extracts from records. $^{23}/_{11}$: R in toto diminished. Cough diminished. Expect. as before. $^{5}/_1$: left lung posteriorly no R, anteriorly as before. Right lung anteriorly scl—II, resp. pronouncedly br. + bronchophony, posteriorly as before. Cough troublesome. Feeling well. $^{17}/_2$: status idem. Cough as before. Expect. somewhat lessened. Feeling well. $^{4}/_4$: in bed since some weeks with fever up to 40° C, stabbing pain in right side anteriorly and downward, increased cough. Status: right lung anteriorly D 3, br. resp., especially distinct in I—II, and some medium partly metallic R. Otherwise such R diffusely over the whole lung, mingled with coarse rhonchi. R posteriorly metallic $^{1}/_2$ A—A. Left lung: R anteriorly and downwards more metallic than before. Ssp—ang., isolated to some few, medium hard R. Below ang. isolated coarse rhonchi. Cough still troublesome with fairly abundant expect. Feeling tired. $^{17}/_5$: nowhere rhonchi. Left lung, some to some few R $^{1}/_2$ A all the way down; hard but without distinct consonance. Right lung, generally less consonance of R. Otherwise status idem. Temp. all the time febrile—subfebrile, constantly sinking. Cough and expect. lessened. General condition worse.

Summary: Case in Stage III. with a great change for the worse in lung status and general condition. Subfebrile.

Weight chart:

$^{1}/_3$	—	77.5	kg.
$^{14}/_3$	—	77.5	»
$^{15}/_5$	—	68.5	»
$^{1}/_6$	—	70	»
$^{15}/_6$	—	70	»
$^{30}/_6$	—	70	»

Quantity of sputum:

$^{2}/_3$	—	75	ccm.
$^{16}/_3$	—	75	»
$^{1}/_4$	—	150	»
$^{15}/_4$	—	100	»
$^{1}/_5$	—	75	»
$^{15}/_5$	—	100	»
$^{1}/_6$	—	75	»
$^{15}/_6$	—	100	»

Conclusion for Couple i: The orange case has progressed better.

Couple k.

19. Or.

Augusta Karolina S-r, born $^{2}/_6$ 91. Wife of timber-yard labourer. Ingarö.

Anamnesis: Pat. $^{2}/_7$. No tbc in family. One child, 15 years, healthy. Since childhood periodically evil-smelling secretion from right ear. Three partus arte prematuri owing to albuminuria. Since 1914 after the last confinement she has felt weakly. Infl. ep. autumn 1918. Afterwards cough and expect. Tbc stated in June 1919. Four small hemoptyses, last time midsummer 1921, a couple of table-spoonfuls. Pneumothorax treatment in the Serafimerlasarettet Oct. 1919—June 1921, interrupted on account of progression in the less affected lung. Nursed in the Serafimerlasarettet June 1922 for hemoptysis. Appetite during the last months bad, emaciation, temp. up to 39° C.

Admitted $18/1$ 23. *Status* $22/1$: Constitution weak; pale, flesh very spare. Cyanosis; breathlessness. Appetite bad; feeling tired. Refuses to eat bread, bread and butter, fruit. Takes much milk and some meat. Otitis med. chron. supp. dx. et sin. c. granulation. Hemoglobin 45 % (Tallquist).

Local status: rather more than half of both lungs from above D 3, resp. br., metallic R.

Extracts from records. $5/3$: R in toto considerably diminished. Feeling very tired. Coughs less, expect. diminished. $2/3$: an orange a day. $11/4$: R considerably diminished, scl—II and ssp— $1/2$ A. Left lung, posteriorly at the base catarrhal accompaniments. Cough lessened, expect. likewise. Feeling considerably better, but the increase in weight is still unsatisfactory. 55 % hgbl. (Tallquist). $30/5$: catarrhal accompaniments have disappeared, otherwise as before. Cough and expect. still less. »Appetite much better since two months». Consumed earlier almost exclusively liquid food. 65 % hgb. without Fe treatment. $20/1$ no bacilli, after $30/1$ +.

Weight chart:

$18/1$ — 48 kg.	$1/3$ — 48.5 kg.	$14/4$ — 48.5 kg.	$1/6$ — 51 kg.
$1/2$ — 48 »	$15/3$ — 48 »	$1/5$ — 49.5 »	$15/6$ — 51.5 »
$15/2$ — 48 »	$31/3$ — 48 »	$15/5$ — 50.5 »	

Summary: Case in Stage III. with cavity symptoms, which have receded. General and local improvement, to some degree already before the orange was given. Considerably better result than had been expected.

20.

Anna Lovisa A-n, born $9/6$ 1860. Vada.

Anamnesis: Married since 1884. 9 children, one dead at the age of 23 in the pulm. 1918. No. 9 has tbc pulm. A granddaughter has the pulm. Has had »gastric catarrh» for a long time. Since at least 10 years back constant breathlessness when moving. 1904 pneumonia, nursed in the hospital of this place. Afterwards cough and expect. in periods; constantly since 1918 when she had infl. ep. Nursed here in another department in the spring of 1922 for bronchitis: no tbc bacilli in sputum. Taken violently ill in Oct. 1922 with high fever and bad cough. Blood-imbibed sputa. Afterwards in bed with fever till admitted into the hospital $18/1$. The pulm. then stated.

Admitted into the sanatorium $29/1$. *Status* $4/2$ 23: Constitution fairly good. Flesh spare. Cough moderate with moderate expect. No stabbing pain. Breathlessness when moving. Appetite, digestion, sleep fairly good. Feeling tired. *Right lung*: scl—III D 3, resp. br., some—several medium—coarser metallic R. Likewise in ssp—A. Below anteriorly and posteriorly D 2, resp. unclear, harsh; posteriorly almost br. ves. *Left lung*: Scl—III and ssp— $1/2$ A D 2, resp. of slightly bronchial character. R I—III and sp— $1/2$ A some few, fine—medium, hard. Below resp. harsh and unclear. Cor: hypertrophy? Weak systolic accompaniment all over the heart. Pulm. II acc. Pulse 100, somewhat soft.

Extracts from records. $19/1$: Right lung anteriorly only isolated R I—II. Otherwise nothing, posteriorly as before. Left lung, no certain R. Coughs less with less expect. Feeling fairly well. Complaining of breathlessness. Cor: no distinct accompaniment. $1/3$ and $14/4$: examinations with same result. $1/5$: left lung posteriorly no R. Otherwise lung status about the same as on $4/2$. Cough rather troublesome with somewhat increased expect. Feels tired, breathless. Appetite bad. $8/5$: resp. and D everywhere as before; left lung, no R. Right lung posteriorly, resp. br., bronchophony interscapularly. D with

metallic R. Below A resp. br.-ves. with some few hard R intermingled with rhonchi and friction sounds. Right lung anteriorly isolated fine hard R, intermingled with rhonchi. No increase of weight during the last month. Complaints of pain in the pit of the stomach, obj. tenderness. Leaves the sanatorium contrary to advice.

Temp. afebrile during the first month, afterwards subfebrile. Last week towards 39°, remittingly. Bacilli examined $^{30/1}$ +, and $^{3/5}$ —. 100—150 ccm. of mucopur. sputum daily.

Weight chart:

$^{1/2}$ — 56.5 kg.	$^{15/3}$ — 60 kg.	$^{14/4}$ — 60 kg.
$^{15/2}$ — 58 »	$^{31/3}$ — 60 »	$^{1/5}$ — 59.5 »
$^{1/3}$ — 59 »		

Summary: Case in Stage III. with beginning destruction in the upper half of the right lung, proceeding to a large cavity. Local aggravation. At first general improvement, afterwards getting worse. (After leaving the sanatorium her condition grew still worse at home, where she had about the same treatment.)

Conclusion for Couple k: The orange case has had the better progress.

Couple l.

21. Or.

Maria Elisabet (Betty) E-n, born $^{19/11}$ 02. Skipper's daughter. Vätö. *Anamnesis:* Pat. $^{6/9}$. Father tbc, youngest child tbc of slight degree. Always delicate. In the autumn 1918 infl. ep. Spring 1919 lymphomata colli, treated with Roentgen in St. Maria's Hospital; now disappeared. Mid-summer 1922 hemoptysis, about a coffee-cup. Only after that continuous cough with some expect. Tbc stated in June 1922.

Admitted $^{19/2}$ 23. *Status* $^{23/2}$: constitution and flesh without remark. Coughs slightly, almost without expect. Appetite good. *Local status:* both apices D 2. Resp. changed, a number of rather fine R. $^{3/3}$: an orange a day. $^{6/4}$: R diminished everywhere. D and resp. as before. Bacilli $^{27/2}$: none. $^{10/4}$: no expect. $^{16/5}$: local status idem. Never coughs. No expect.

Summary: Case in Stage II in a stout person with good general condition, which has improved with lung status. Progress better than was expected.

Weight chart:

$^{10/2}$ — 64 kg.	$^{1/5}$ — 66.5 kg.
$^{1/3}$ — 65.5 »	$^{15/3}$ — 65.5 »
$^{15/3}$ — 65 »	$^{1/6}$ — 65.5 »
$^{1/4}$ — 65.5 »	$^{15/6}$ — 66 »
$^{15/4}$ — 66 »	$^{30/6}$ — 65.5 »

22.

Svea Viktoria Elvira A-t, born $^{17/5}$ 07. Daughter of farm labourer. Mar-kims.

Anamnesis: Pat. $^{5/5}$. 9 half-brothers and sisters. No tbc in family. Autumn 1918 infl. ep. Two years later pneumonia. Cough in autumn and spring. Since autumn 1922 increased cough, bad appetite, emaciation. Never hemoptysis. Tbc stated in Jan. 1923.

Admitted $31/1$ 23. *Status*: Constitution somewhat weakly. Flesh spare. Coughs slightly, almost without expect. Appetite not so good. Otherwise without remark. Other organs, nothing abnormal. *Lung status*: in both bases D 2—D 3, resp. in the right base br. ves.; enfeebled on the left, R rather hard and large (rest of pneumonia with bronchial catarrh) D 1—D 2 in both apices, more pronounced on the right. In the right interscap. and scl—I sin. some small hard R.

Extracts from records. $25/3$: R considerably lessened. Status otherwise the same. No expect. Since a fortnight in bed with fever. Obj. posteriorly on the right below A friction sounds = dry pleuritis. Since a week erythema nodosum on both legs and left arm. Temp. sinking. Feels well. No pain. No bacilli $14/2$, $2/3$ and $3/3$. $7/5$: nowhere certain R or accompaniments. Never coughs; no expect. Feels well.

Summary: Starved girl with slight tbc. (Stage I—II). After passing aggravation (pleuritis) pronounced improvement. Temperature afebrile.

Weight chart:

$15/2$ — 48 kg.	$1/5$ — 51 kg.
$1/3$ — 49 »	$10/5$ — 52 »
$15/3$ — 48.5 »	$1/6$ — 54 »
$31/3$ — 47.5 »	$15/6$ — 52.5 »
$14/4$ — 49.5 »	$30/6$ — 53.5 »

$1/2$ and $15/6$ no sputa.

Conclusion for Couple I: The orange case has had the better progress.

Couple m.

23. Or.

Ida Margit Johanna H-n, born $24/8$ 05. Daughter of an engine-foreman. Hammarby.

Anamnesis: Par. $2/3$. Father has healed tbc. Otherwise no tbc in family. Felt tired and weak since the spring of 1922. Bad appetite, losing of flesh, breathlessness when moving. No cough or expect. Never hemoptysis. The stated in June 1922 through Roentgen examination in the Serafimerlasarettet.

Admitted $5/2$ 23. *Status* $11/2$: constitution fairly good. Flesh somewhat below the average. Never coughs, no expect. Breathlessness when going upstairs. Appetite, digestion, sleep good. Feeling well. *Local status*: D 1 in apices of both lungs, resp. changed. I dx., br. ves. resp. and isolated fine R. Other organs, nothing.

Extracts from records. $3/3$: an orange a day. $25/3$: nowhere certain R or accompaniments. Coughs occasionally without expect. Feels well. $7/5$: lung status idem = only D 1. Coughs occasionally without expect. Feels well. (Roentgen: small foci in left apex and confluent on the right.) Film on the right apex. Temp. the whole time afebrile. No bacilli $1/3$. $15/6$: no sputa. Dismissed $30/6$.

Weight chart:

$1/3$ — 56 kg.	$15/4$ — 57 kg.	$1/6$ — 58 kg.
$15/3$ — 56 »	$1/5$ — 58 »	$15/6$ — 57.5 »
$1/4$ — 56.5 »	$15/5$ — 58 »	$30/6$ — 58 »

Summary: Case in Stage I., which has progressed to healing.

24.

Hulda Katarina B-y, born $^{30/1}$ 99. Housemaid. Danderyd.

Anamnesis: Pat. $^{3/6}$, twin. Mother has had repeated lung hemorrhages. Always well till Febr. 22; since then constantly tired, coughed up phlegm in the mornings. Hemoptysis, about 100 gr., June 22. Afterwards subfebrile temperature the whole summer. Appetite good all the time. No emaciation. Tbc stated in Sept. 22.

Admitted $^{3/3}$ 23. *Status* $^{6/3}$: constitution and flesh ordinary. Sometimes hawks up a little phlegm in the morning. No cough. Sometimes breathlessness when moving, and palpitation of the heart. Appetite, digestion, sleep good. Feels well. Other organs, nothing. Pharynx, diffuse reddening, mucous coating. Right lung: D I—D 2 scl—II, ssp—rather more than A, harsh, unclear resp. No R. Otherwise resp. everywhere unclear, in places harsh or enfeebled.

Extracts from records. $^{18/3}$: nowhere R or accompaniments. Never coughs. »Still slight amount of phlegm from the throat.» Feels well. $^{31/5}$: status idem. $^{6/6}$: lungs the same. Departs at her own request. No cough, slight phlegm from throat. Temp afebrile. No extra treatment. No tbc bac. found at examination $^{13/3}$, $^{23/3}$ and $^{26/4}$.

Weight chart:

$^{3/3}$ — 64.5 kg.	$^{14/4}$ — 67.2 kg.	$^{15/5}$ — 67.5 kg.
$^{15/3}$ — 66.5 »	$^{1/5}$ — 67 »	$^{1/6}$ — 68 »
$^{31/3}$ — 67.5 »		

Summary: Case in Stage I—II without R. Lung status unchanged. General condition improved. Pharyngit. chron.

Conclusion for Couple m: Both cases show a favourable progress.

Couple n.

25. Or.

Agda Sylvia E-n, born $^{20/9}$ 10. Skipper's daughter. Vätö.

Sister of Maria Elisabet (No. 21). Always well till the autumn of 1918, then light infl. ep. After that reduced hearing. Otherwise felt well. Tbc pulm. stated by physician when her sister fell ill. She had constantly felt tired, however, since a year back. No fever and no night-sweat. No hemoptysis. Appetite good, no emaciation. Had a good home.

Admitted $^{19/2}$ 23. *Status* $^{23/2}$ 23: constitution fairly good. Flesh a little below the average. No cough or expect. No stabbing pain. No breathlessness. Appetite, digestion, sleep good. Feels well. No heart hypertrophy. Systolic accompaniment over the base. II pulm. acc. Pulse 100, normal. *Lung status*: D I scl—I on both sides, and on both sides interscap. Likewise D I on left side IV—VI anteriorly and at the base posteriorly. Resp. in these parts harsh, unclear. Scl—II on both sides, interscap., and laterally on the left isolated — some few fine, hard R.

Extracts from records. $^{1/3}$: an orange daily. $^{6/4}$: resp. and D everywhere as before. No R. Never coughs. No expect. Feels well. $^{16/5}$: nowhere R or accompaniments. Never coughs. General condition about the same as on admission to the sanatorium. Feels well. Temp. the whole time afebrile. Dismissed $^{17/5}$.

Weight chart:

$\frac{19}{2}$ — 47.5 kg.	$\frac{1}{4}$ — 47.5 kg.	$\frac{1}{5}$ — 47.5 kg.
$\frac{1}{3}$ — 48 »	$\frac{15}{4}$ — 47.5 »	$\frac{15}{5}$ — 47 »
$\frac{15}{3}$ — 48 »		

Summary: Bilateral hilus tbc with objectively distinct improvement. General condition about the same as when admitted to the sanatorium.

26.

Elsa Sofia M-m, born $\frac{13}{7}$ 07. Daughter of a plumber. Södertälje.

Anamnesis: Pat. $\frac{2}{7}$. Both parents have had tbc, mother died at Väsby, father nursed in sanatorium. Brother, No. 1, dead in unknown disease, other brothers and sisters healthy. Otherwise no tbc in family. At the age of 3 in bed for a month, severely ill with fever; since then always easily catching cold and getting cough. Otherwise well till the age of 11; then lymphomata colli, operated at the Södertälje Hospital. Afterwards treated with Roentgen and quartz lamp. Cough without expect. since at least a year. Never hemoptysis. Appetite good, no emaciation. No fever or night-sweat. The pulm. stated in Oct. 22. Home conditions bad.

Admitted $\frac{28}{2}$ 23. *Status* $\frac{4}{3}$: constitution fairly ordinary, rather thin. Coughs slightly without expect. Appetite, digestion, sleep good. Feels well. Lymphomata on both sides of neck and lower jaw. Hypertrophia tonsillar. *Lung status:* Hilus affection, with D 1—D 2 in both interscap. and I—II with small fine R. Resp. harsh and unclear.

Extracts from records. Nowhere R or accompaniments. Never coughs. No expect. Feels well. Incision of purulent lymphoma under the chin. Large quantities of yellowish green, thick pus discharging. Tamponade. An open fistula from lymphoma on the left side of the neck is also secerning. $\frac{17}{4}$: quartz lamp. $\frac{29}{5}$: nowhere R or accompaniments. Never coughs. No expect. Feels well. Still secretion from fistulæ. Temp. afebrile. Sputa: $\frac{27}{2}$ no bacilli; $\frac{16}{6}$ no sputa.

Weight chart:

$\frac{26}{2}$ — 48 kg.	$\frac{15}{4}$ — 48.5 kg.	$\frac{1}{6}$ — 50.5 kg.
$\frac{15}{3}$ — 49.5 »	$\frac{1}{5}$ — 48 »	$\frac{15}{6}$ — 51 »
$\frac{1}{4}$ — 48.5 »	$\frac{15}{5}$ — 49 »	$\frac{30}{6}$ — 51.5 »

Summary: Hilus affection with purulent lymphomata under the chin, which has improved locally in the lungs and possibly also with regard to the general condition.

Conclusion for Couple n: The orange case has progressed somewhat more favourably (?).

Couple o.

27. Or.

Ingrid Karolina R-m, born $\frac{1}{3}$ 99. Wife of shoe-factory workman. Nacka.

Anamnesis: Pat. $\frac{8}{8}$. No tbc in family. Married in May 1921. Nullipara. Healthy till the age of 14, then operated upon for appendicitis. Afterwards feeling weakly. 1919 nursed in hospital for cystitis with inflammation of the kidneys. Well till Dec. 1921, then pain in her throat, difficulty of swallowing, treated with serum by physician supposing diphtheria. The attack passed. Since then well till Aug. 1922, then the same kind of pain in her throat. In the Serafimerlasarettet the physician stated the laryngis et pulm. Operated

in larynx $8/9$. Afterwards nursed for a week in the Sabbatsberg Hospital. Cough and expect. since Dec. 21. Often blood-imbibed sputa. Often fever, up to 38° C. Night-sweat. Appetite less good since 1919; emaciation since then.

Admitted $5/2$ 23. Status $8/2$: Constitution fairly good. Flesh spare. Pale; coughs slightly with inconsiderable expect. Very breathless when moving. Often palpitation of heart. No longer any pain in throat. Feeling somewhat tired. Cor: slight hypertrophy towards the left. Slight systolic accompaniment all over the heart, strongest over the base. Lung status: D I—D 2 in both scl—II. On the right side posteriorly well down to A, the same D; on the left down to $1/2$ A. In the same areas resp. unclear. Resp. everywhere in the lungs slightly changed (enfeebled, not quite clear, harsh, prolonged expiration). R sparse, small, fine in both I—II and on the left posteriorly about $1/2$ A and at A. In larynx on the back wall some infiltration, and epiglottis a little swollen, especially in the left part.

Extracts of records. $21/2$: since a few days periodically palpitation of heart, general restlessness; slight rise of temperature (up to 38), nasal catarrh, headache. No pain in chest. Cor: accompaniments more distinct. Pulm. II more acc., sometimes a grating systolic accompaniment over Pulm. II (superficially?). Lungstatus idem. $3/3$: an orange a day. In the beginning of March in bed with alveolar abscess which was opened and scraped out, tamponade. Looked like the pus. Pat. has earlier had some such abscesses. Healing slowly, secretion stopped only in June. $23/3$: nowhere R or accompaniments. Cough lessened with less expect. Feels well. No longer any symptoms from heart. Objectively, no certain accompaniment. Larynx, status idem, but no swelling of the epiglottis. $4/5$: nowhere distinct R, but resp. everywhere unclear. Otherwise as on $8/2$. Cough for the moment somewhat irritating with inconsiderable expect. Last weeks occasional headaches. Last days slight rise of temp. (acute infection of throat).

Weight chart:

$1/3$	— 50 kg.
$15/3$	— 50 »
$21/3$	— 51 »
$14/4$	— 50.5 »
$1/5$	— 53 »
$15/5$	— 23 »
$1/6$	— 52.5 »
$15/6$	— 52 »

Quantity of sputum:

$1/3$	— 20 ccm.
$15/3$	— 15 »
$1/4$	— 15 »
$15/4$	— 5 »
$1/5$	— 10 »
$15/5$	— 10 »
$1/6$	— 10 »
$15/6$	— 10 »

$1/6$: local status, no R, otherwise as before. General condition improved, feeling well. Temp. afebrile. Bacilli examined $14/2$ and $14/4$ = 0.

Summary: Case in Stage II. with diffuse lighter changes over both lungs, bone abscess and larynx affection (pericarditis?). In the anamnesis affliction of kidneys.

Considerable improvement with disappearing of R and larynx symptoms; bone affliction healed. General condition considerably improved.

28.

Maria Charlotta Viveka R-ä, born $9/7$ 95. Telephonist 09. Ljusterö.

Anamnesis: Pat. $4/4$. Mother dead of the ren. Otherwise no tbc in family. As a child often coughing. Of infantile diseases only morbilli, slight form. Spring 1919 pain in the left renal area and urinary strain. In 1917 pain at urination. Frequent urinations at night. Extirpation of tuberculous left kidney in the Serafimerlasarettet 1918. Autumn 1918 slight infl. ep.

Afterwards fatigue and rise of temp. autumn and spring. Since autumn 1921, slight continuous cough, almost without expect. At one occasion, 8—9 years ago, slight spitting of blood. Temp. during last year with a tendency of rising to 38° when moving. Periodically night-sweat. Appetite at the end of last year bad, now again good. Decreased in weight 3 kg. during the last months. The pulm. stated in Dec. 1921.

Admitted $^{23}/_2$ 23. *Status* $^{26}/_2$: constitution and flesh good. Coughs occasionally with inconsiderable expect. Appetite good. Gets diarrhea easily. Feels tired at times, but generally well. Larynx slightly reddened diffusely, somewhat hypertrophic tonsilli with a few polyp. nasi sin. *Lung status*: anteriorly scl—III on the right, scl—II on the left, posteriorly ssp on the right, ssp— $^{1}/_2$ A on the left D 1—D 2, resp very harsh, unclear. In the lower parts of the lungs resp. harsh. Right lung, I—II and sp— $^{1}/_2$ A isolated to a few fine to hard R. Left lung, no R. $^{15}/_4$ nowhere R or accompaniments. Coughs occasionally without expect. Generally feels well except at the periods of the menses, when there is often a pain in the right renal region and just above the symphysis on the left side. Urine sometimes a little turbid. $^{6}/_5$: no sediment in urine. $^{17}/_5$: nowhere R or accompaniment. Resp. less harsh and unclear. D as before. Never coughs. No expect. Feels well. Temp. afebrile. No tbc bacilli.

Weight chart:

$^{23}/_2$ — 64 kg.	$^{31}/_3$ — 65.5 kg.	$^{1}/_5$ — 65.5 kg.
$^{1}/_3$ — 65 "	$^{14}/_4$ — 65.5 "	$^{15}/_5$ — 66 "
$^{15}/_3$ — 65,5 "		

Summary: Case in Stage I—II locally and generally improved. Has had kidney complications.

Conclusion for Couple o: The orange case has progressed somewhat more favourably.

Couple p.

29. Or.

Maria Linnea Josefina O-n, born $^{20}/_{10}$ 97. Wife of electrician. Sundbyberg.

Anamnesis: Pat. $^2/_4$. Two of the other children dead in the pulm. Married since 1920. One child, two years old. Always well till April 1922, then pneumonia sin. Afterwards cough and expect. Subfebrile temp. since the same time. Sometimes night-sweat. The pulm. stated in April 1922, when sanatorium treatment was advised. Appetite generally good. No emaciation.

Admitted to the Väsby Hospital $^3/_4$ 23. Moved to the Sanatorium $^{19}/_4$. An orange daily from $^3/_4$.

Status $^{20}/_4$: constitution fairly good. Rather thin. Coughs moderately with moderate expect. Breathlessness when moving. Appetite good. Digestion troublesome, often diarrhea. Sleep bad. Other organs, nothing. *Local status*: all the left lung D 3, upper half resp. br. and submetallic—metallic R, some—some few. Lower part, resp. harsh, unclear, a few hard, medium R. intermingled with friction sounds. Right lung: scl, ssp, D 3: I—II and sp—more than $^{1}/_2$ A, D 1—D 2. Resp. over all this area of br. character. Then all the way down resp. harsh, unclear. Scl—II and ssp—more $^{1}/_2$ A some few partly submetallic R. Laterally and below A isolated dry accompaniments.

Extracts from records. $^2/_6$: R in toto diminished. Otherwise equal. Cough and expect. as before. Temp. sinking. General condition improved. Feels well. $^{15}/_6$: very much the same.

Bacilli $^{20}/_4$ +.

Dismissed home ¹⁵/₉. On ¹¹/₁₉ 23 condition good, subjectively better than when leaving the sanatorium.

Weight chart:

⁵ / ₄ — 66.2 kg.	¹ / ₆ — 68.5 kg.	¹ / ₈ — 69 kg.
¹⁹ / ₄ — 66.5 »	¹⁵ / ₆ — 68.5 »	¹⁵ / ₈ — 69.5 »
¹ / ₅ — 67.5 »	¹ / ₇ — 69 »	¹ / ₉ — 69.5 »
¹⁵ / ₅ — 68 »	¹⁵ / ₇ — 68.5 »	

Summary: Case in Stage II. praec. sin. with destruction over the upper half of the left lung. Subjectively and objectively improvement.

30.

Ida Albertina Birgitta K-n, born ¹⁴/₁₀ 98. Bookbinder. Sollentuna.

Anamnesis: Pat. ²/₉. Well till Nov. 22, then began to feel tired and weak. Afterwards cough and expect. Hemoptysis a couple of tea-spoonfuls on ⁵/₁₂ 22. Appetite generally good. Losing flesh the last months. Since six weeks fever up to 39.5° in the evening, and night-sweat. Tbc stated ⁸/₁₂ 22.

Admitted to the Väsby Hospital ³/₄, removed to the Sanatorium ¹⁸/₄. *Status* ²⁰/₄: Constitution fairly good. Flesh spare. Coughs moderately with moderate expect. Appetite bad. Digestion troublesome. Diarrhea frequently. Sleep generally good. Feels well. Larynx inconsiderable diffuse reddening. Right ventricular ligament somewhat swollen, reddened. Obj. nothing from abdomen. *Lung status:* right lung scl—II and ssp— not quite A D 3 + br. ves. resp. + some few submetallic R. For the rest all the way down D 1 and resp. very harsh, not quite clear. Left lung: scl D 2—D 3. I—II D 1—D 2. Posteriorly D 3 to 1/2 A. Resp. very harsh, not quite clear. Sp to 1/2 A a few fine hard R.

Extracts from records. ¹/₆: right lung, R heard scl—III and ssp—more than ¹/₂ A. Left lung: no certain R. Coughs hardly ever. Expect. as before. ¹⁶/₆. Status quo. Periodically diarrhea and vomiting. Temp.: febrile—subfebrile. Sputa + tbc all the time.

Weight chart:

¹⁰ / ₄ — 58.5 kg.	¹⁵ / ₅ — 59 kg.	¹⁵ / ₆ — 59.5 kg.
¹ / ₅ — 58.5 »	¹ / ₆ — 60.5 »	¹ / ₇ — 60 »

Summary: Case in Stage III., bilateral with the gravest changes in the upper half of right lung. There trace of destruction. Lung status about the same. General condition somewhat improved. (Yet temp. all the time on the verge of febrile.)

Conclusion for Couple p: The orange case more improved.

Couple q.

31. Or.

Judit Ingeborg Paulina L-v, born ²⁵/₈ 96. Cook. Järfälla.

Anamnesis: Pat. ⁵/₉. A brother, No. 6, tbc pulm. 1916 at the age of 18. Otherwise no tbc in family. Always well till 1916, then pneumonia ac. sin. Otherwise well till the autumn of 1918, then infl. ep. without complications. Well till April 1922, then infl. Afterwards felt weak without appetite; emaciation, lost 7 kg. last month. Sometimes afebrile temp. No night-sweat. In beginning of May 22 slight hemoptysis. Afterwards sometimes blood-imbibed sputa. Tbc pulm. May 1922.

Admitted $^4/_{10}$ 22. Status $^6/_{10}$: constitution and flesh fairly good. Slight cough with inconsiderable expect. Appetite bad. Feels physically well but is very depressed and cares for nothing. Other organs, no remark.

Local status: right lung, apex scl—II and ssp—A br. ves. resp. and a moderate number of R, hard in scl and submetallic in ssp D 2—D 3 in scl and ssp, D 1—D 2 to II and A. Left lung: D 1—D 2 scl—I and ssp— $1/2$ A, harsh and unclear resp., sparse, fine, hard R.

Extracts from records. $^{17}/_{11}$: right lung anteriorly increased R, scl—III, otherwise as before. Posteriorly distinct R only to $1/2$ A. Left lung no R. Coughs hardly ever. Diminished expect. Feels fairly well. Sometimes blood-imbibed sputa. Roentgen: indicating pneumothorax? Chiefly right-sided affection with beginning purulence in right apex. $^7/_{12}$: peribronchites starting from hilus on both sides, more numerous and closer together on right side, with small consolidations scl—II on the right. $^{30}/_{12}$: right lung anteriorly R scl—II, posteriorly as before. Left lung, no R. Coughs less with rather increased expect. Feels tired, psychially depressed. Since last examination running away during psychosis. No increase in weight. Bacilli: $^{17}/_{10}$ none, $^2/_{11}$ +, $^3/_{4}$ and $^{20}/_{4}$ none. $^{17}/_{2}$: right lung, R heard only scl—I and ssp— $1/2$ A. Otherwise as before. Coughs occasionally without expect. Still tired. No increase in weight. $^3/_{3}$: an orange a day. $^{23}/_{3}$: status idem, but resp. more br. on the right and submetallic R as before. Roentgen shows in the right lung small distinct cavity. Coughs occasionally with inconsiderable expect. Feels fairly well, but continually without increase in weight. $^7/_{5}$: local status, isolated R scl—III in right lung, posteriorly to $1/2$ A. Left lung, nothing. Coughs slightly with slight expect. Feels well. Lately some increase in weight. Temp. afebrile. $^3/_{6}$ Regained her spirits. Mind changed. No cough.

Weight chart:

$1/3$ — 63 kg.
$^{15}/_3$ — 63 »
$1/4$ — 63 »
$^{15}/_4$ — 61.5 »
$1/5$ — 63 »
$^{15}/_5$ — 63.5 »
$1/6$ — 63.8 »
$^{15}/_6$ — 63 »
$^{30}/_6$ — 62.5 »

Quantity of sputum:

$1/3$ — 10 ccm.
$1/4$ — 10 »
$^{15}/_4$ — 10 »
$1/5$ — 10 »
$^{15}/_5$ — 0 »
$1/6$ — 0 »
$^{15}/_6$ — 0 »

Summary: A restricted case in Stage III. with half of the right lung affected and with light changes in the left apex. Aggravating at first, cavity formation, psychosis. After starting with the orange experiment locally improved and also general condition considerably better.

32.

Oskar Robert B-n, born $^2/6$ 03. Farm labourer. Spånga.

Anamnesis: Pat. $^3/6$. Father tbc 3 years ago. Otherwise no tbc in family. As a rule catching cold easily and getting cough. Otherwise always well till the end of Aug.; then fell ill with stabbing pain in his left side. Temp. up to nearly 39° C. Is said to have had pleuritis exsud. sin. in Aug. 22. After that mostly out of bed, but has not been able to work much. Tbc pulm. stated in Sept. 22. Cough and expect. since Aug. 22, bad appetite and emaciation. Never hemoptysis.

Admitted $^5/3$. Status $^7/3$: constitution frail. Flesh spare. Coughs slightly with inconsiderable expect. No breathlessness, appetite fairly good. Feels well. Slight hypertrophy of heart? Systolic accompaniment, strongest

over the apex. Pulm. II acc. Other organs, nothing. *Local status*: left lung all over D 3, upper half resp. of slightly br. character, and hard, partly metallic R; lower half enfeebled resp. and laterally isolated friction sounds. Right lung: scl—II and ssp—A, D 3—D 2 diminishing downwards and br. ves. resp. Anteriorly isolated hard R.

Extracts from records. ¹⁸/₂: right lung, no certain R. Left lung, status idem. Hardly ever coughs. Sometimes inconsiderable expect. Feels well. ³¹/₅: R as on ⁷/₃. Slight cough with inconsiderable expect. Feels well.

Weight chart:

⁵ / ₃	—	52.5	kg.
¹⁴ / ₃	—	53.5	»
³¹ / ₃	—	56	»
¹⁴ / ₄	—	57.5	»
¹ / ₅	—	59	»
¹⁵ / ₅	—	59.5	»
¹ / ₆	—	60	»
¹⁵ / ₆	—	58	»
³⁰ / ₆	—	60	»

Quantity of sputum:

⁶ / ₃	—	15	ccm.
¹⁷ / ₃	—	10	»
¹ / ₄	—	10	»
¹ / ₅	—	10	»
¹⁵ / ₅	—	10	»
¹ / ₆	—	10	»
¹⁵ / ₆	—	15	»

Summary: Case in Stage III. All the left lung with symptoms of cavities in the upper half and pleuritic symptoms in the lower; lighter changes in the apex of right lung. General condition considerably improved. Locally no improvement.

Conclusion for Couple q: Case 32 more extended but less virulent. Case 31 improved more.

Couple r.

33. Or.

Asta Vilfrida K-a, born ¹⁸/₆ 16. Labourer's daughter. Solna.

Anamnesis: Maternal grandmother tbc pulm. Parents healthy. During several years relapsing bronchitis. Pertussis at the age of 3. Afterwards weakly. Cough since the summer of 1922, when tbc pulm. was stated, in July. Since then bad appetite, emaciation.

Status on admission ²⁷/₁₀ 22: general condition exceedingly bad. Pale and thin. Vomited all food. Left lung: D 3 almost everywhere. Tymp: in ssp, below A, and I—III. In these areas br. resp.; amphoric and coarse metallic and grating R. Resp. for the rest unclear, br. ves., numerous hard R. Right lung: ¹/₂ A—A some few hard R. Resp. everywhere harsh, not quite clear. Roentgen: all the left lung strong consolidation with three large cavities from base to apex.

Extracts from records. ¹⁸/₁₁: left lung, amphoric resp. nowhere quite pronounced. Anteriorly resp. only softly br. R in toto considerably lessened, less metallic. Right lung, D ssp—beyond ¹/₂ A resp. of br. character with isolated hard accompaniments. ³⁰/₁₀: D as before. Pronouncedly br. resp. only on left side posteriorly, ¹/₂ A—A with hard metallic R. For the rest resp. harsh, of slightly br. character with isolated hard accompaniments in some places. Laterally on the left resp. almost extinguished. Right lung as on ¹⁸/₁₁. ¹⁰/₁ 23: right lung scl resp. very unclear. Otherwise as on ¹⁸/₁₁. Left lung as on ³⁰/₁₁. At Christmas cough somewhat increased, especially when moving. Somewhat hoarse. General condition slightly improved. Larynx diffusely reddened. ⁷/₂: D and resp. as before. R only in right lung I—II and at sp hard without metallic ring, finer. Left lung I—II and ssp—A, some few to several, metallic R, rather coarse, most numerous posteriorly. For

the rest no R. Cough increased of late, trying at the slightest movement. Temp. running higher. General condition improved. Roentgen ²⁷/₂, as before. ¹/₃ an orange a day. ⁷/₃: pneumothorax starting, always standing partial but pressing the cavities together. Expect., up till now abundant, has disappeared. (Narrow lateral pneumothorax, wide adherence in the middle of lung to chest wall, above the clavicle total adherence.) Periodically only slight pneumothorax. ¹⁹/₃: anteriorly on the left no resp., no R: posteriorly ssp—A resp. br. with some medium metallic accompaniments. Then resp. feeble, of bronchial character. No certain R. Right lung: II—III and isc resp. br. ves. with suspicion of accompaniment. Cough diminished during last week. Expect. about as before. Pneumothorax continued 50—at highest 100 (generally 80) ccm. under high pressure. At first every other day, in June once a fortnight. ¹⁸/₄: left lung anteriorly scl—II resp. feebly audible (pneumothorax partially). For the rest all the way down almost no resp., the same laterally. Posteriorly = ¹⁹/₃, but no R. Right lung, no R. Otherwise as before. Cough considerably less with hardly any expect. General condition greatly improved. ²⁴/₅: status quo. Hardly ever coughs. No expect. General condition considerably improved. ¹⁶/₆: nowhere R. Resp. in the upper half of left lung br.; then no resp. Right lung: resp. everywhere harsh. Otherwise no remark. General condition improved. Temp. some time afebrile, mostly febrile with high points, especially after insufflations, yet less after March. At the end temp. a — subfebrile (like that of the others).

Weight chart:

²⁶ / ₁₀ — 17 kg.	¹⁵ / ₁ — 18.7 kg.	¹⁵ / ₄ — 19.5 kg.
³¹ / ₁₀ — 17 »	¹ / ₂ — 19.3 »	¹ / ₅ — 19.5 »
¹⁵ / ₁₁ — 17 »	¹⁵ / ₂ — 19.5 »	¹⁵ / ₅ — 20 »
¹ / ₁₃ — 18,5 »	¹⁵ / ₃ — 18.5 »	¹ / ₆ — 20.5 »
¹⁵ / ₁₂ — 18,7 »	¹ / ₄ — 18.5 »	¹⁵ / ₆ — 20 »
¹ / ₁ — 18.7 »		

Summary: Case in Stage III., left lung totally attacked with large cavities. Right lung, hilus process with peribronchites. Favourably influenced by pneumothorax treatment (sputa disappeared). General condition greatly improved. Improvement in general condition is regarded as surpassing what might have been expected as a consequence of and during the pneumothorax treatment.

34.

Ernst Napoleon L-n, born ¹⁷/₁₁ 97. Täby.

Anamnesis: Pat. ³/₃. (One brother suspected for the pulm.) Fell ill with fever and stabbing pain in the left side ¹¹/₁₂ 1922. In bed two weeks with fever. Then cough and expect since Jan. 1923. Never hemoptysis. Advised hospital nursing by physician Febr. 1922. Admitted to the Väsby Hospital ²²/₂ 23. Removed to the tbc department ³¹/₃ 23 as tbc pulm. and pleurit. exsud. sin. were stated. Appetite since beginning of the year bad. Emaciation.

Extracts from records. ⁵/₄: right lung scl—II and ssp—¹/₂ A, D 3—D 2 with enlarged unclear resp. No R. Below no D, but resp. harsh, isolated R. Left lung below II and ¹/₂ A D 3 with hardly audible resp., and feeble br. resp. at the bottom. Some few submetallic R, intermingled with friction sounds. Other organs, nothing. ¹⁹/₅: appetite good as before. D and resp. the same. R are only heard in left lung about A and in right lung at the top in the axilla. Hardly ever coughs. Practically no expect. Feels well. Temp. afebrile.

Tests for bacilli in the hospital $26/2$ positive; in the tbc department on $3/4$, $10/4$ and $20/4$: No bacilli.

Weight chart:	Quantity of sputum:
$31/3$ — 63.5 kg.	$1/4$ — 5 cem.
$14/4$ — 66.5 »	$1/5$ — 0 »
$1/5$ — 68.5 »	$15/5$ — 15 »
$15/5$ — 68.5 »	$1/6$ — 10 »
$1/6$ — 69.5 »	$15/6$ — 10 »
$15/6$ — 71.5 »	
$30/6$ — 71 »	

Summary: Case in Stage III. with light affection of right apex and graver of the lower half of left lung. Locally and generally considerably improved.

Conclusion for Couple r: Similar progress.

Couple s.

35. Or.

Karin Elisabet J-n, born $9/3$ 1913. Labourer's daughter.

Anamnesis: Nursed here since $5/12$ 1917 to $20/3$ 1918 for bronchitis and in the tbc department. Since then periodically weakly, has not been able to go to school. Occasionally rising temp. Last days fever to 40° C.

Admitted $5/12$. Pale, thin, feeble. *Status* $6/12$: right lung, isc D 1—D 2, harsh, unclear resp. No certain R. Left lung: parasternal D 1; D 2—D 3 I—II. No certain R. Roentgen examination $5/12$; enlarged hilus with peribronchites on both sides, most on the right.

Extracts from records. $10/1$: lungs status quo. $7/2$: right laterally II—IV isolated accompaniments. Never coughs. Poor increase in weight. $2/3$: an orange a day. $7/3$ D and resp. = $6/12$. No certain accompaniments. Tonsillectomy bilat., healed $19/2$. $18/4$: laterally on the left, suspicion of accompaniments. For the rest no R. Resp. and D as before. Never coughs. General condition as before. $24/5$: nowhere R or accompaniments. Never coughs. General condition considerably improved. $15/6$: status idem. General condition still more improved. Getting stout, temp. subfebrile with points. Appetite began to grow a little better at Christmas-time. Distinct improvement from the middle of March.

Weight chart:

$5/12$ — 27.5 kg.	$15/2$ — 28.3 kg.	$1/5$ — 31.5 kg.
$15/12$ — 27.5 »	$1/3$ — 29 »	$15/5$ — 32.3 »
$1/1$ — 28.2 »	$15/3$ — 30 »	$1/6$ — 33 »
$15/1$ — 28.6 »	$1/4$ — 31 »	$15/6$ — 32.8 »
$1/2$ — 28.5 »	$15/4$ — 31 »	

Summary: Case in Stage I. of hilus tbc without certain R. Considerably improved general condition.

36.

Irma Kristina L-m, born $24/9$ 1911. Mason's daughter. Solna.

Anamnesis: Mother tbc pulm. 5-para. Nursed here for 4 months 1921. Since then, according to dispensary, process at standstill. Pat. born 6 weeks too early. Always weak and frail. Disposition for colds and sore throat. Began coughing about a year ago. The pulm. stated in summer 1922.

Admitted $^{16/1}$ 23. Status: Pale, thin, weakly, exceedingly bad appetite. Lung status: right lung D 1—D 2, sc—III and ssp—A and in a small area around A on the left. Right lung I—II and interscap. slightly br., as also in left isc. For the rest harsh and unclear resp. Isolated — some few fine R in the right isc and in the indicated area posteriorly on the left. Roentgen: bilateral enlargement of the hilus shadow, more on the right. Shadow on the left apex. $^{7/2}$: right lung posteriorly ssp—A resp. less pronouncedly bronchial. For the rest, idem. $^{7/3}$: never coughs; general condition as before. Left lung very harsh resp. $^{1/2}$ A—downwards. Right lung unclear resp. No R. Somewhat shorter tone in isc, but less pronounced than before. $^{18/4}$: right lung isc resp. harsh, unclear. At the base posteriorly and laterally, isolated fairly loose R. For the rest nothing. Left lung: $^{1/2}$ A—A isolated inconsiderable dry accompaniments. For the rest as before. $^{24/5}$: nowhere certain accompaniments (suspicion of such around A on the left). Never coughs. General condition improved. $^{16/6}$: left lung around A sometimes isolated accompaniments. Right isc at deep resp. br. character. General condition as before. Never coughs. Feels well. Temp. sometimes subfebrile (points, like Case 35). Appetite not so good, until last month. $^{4/6}$: like the other children moved into new premises.

Summary: Case of hilus tbc with R in right isc and around left ang., which on the whole have disappeared. For the rest, locally idem. General improvement less than the parallel case.]

Weight chart:

$^{16/1}$ — 30 kg.	$^{15/3}$ — 31 kg.	$^{15/5}$ — 32 kg.
$^{1/2}$ — 30 »	$^{1/4}$ — 31.3 »	$^{1/6}$ — 32.5 »
$^{15/2}$ — 30 »	$^{15/4}$ — 31.5 »	$^{15/6}$ — 32 »
$^{1/3}$ — 31 »	$^{1/5}$ — 32 »	

Conclusion for Couple s: Greater improvement for the orange case.

Couple t.

37. Or.

Ivar M-n, born $^{24/8}$ 1915. Labourer's son. Huvudsta.

Anamnesis. Mother suffering from chest affliction, a maternal aunt nursed in sanatorium. Pat. twin. Had pertussis as an infant. Three years ago severe lung catarrh. Always weak and easily catching cold. Last year breathlessness, easily perspiring, even at night. Was to begin school in the autumn 1922, at examination hypertrophy of hilus. Advised hospital treatment. Temp. subfebrile all through the autumn and winter.

Admitted. $^{16/1}$ 23. Status: appetite indifferent. Local status: both lungs anteriorly sc—II, D 1—D 2; posteriorly right lung, ssp— $^{1/2}$ A and a small area around A, D 1. D to the fifth dorsal vertebra. No R. Resp. harsh, enfeebled, unclear diffusely over both lungs. Both isc, suspicion of accompaniments. Roentgen $^{16/1}$: considerably enlarged hilus shadows on both sides.

Extracts from records. $^{7/4}$ signs of diffuse bronchitis, more in the left lung. Otherwise as before. $^{2/3}$: an orange a day. $^{19/5}$: bronchitis better. Otherwise as before. General condition better. $^{15/4}$: both isc D with resp. unclear. For the rest nothing. Never coughs. Temp. still subfebrile. General condition as before. Dismissed $^{22/4}$ 23.

Weight chart:

$^{16/1}$ — 26.5 kg.	$^{1/3}$ — 27 kg.	$^{1/4}$ — 27.9 kg.
$^{1/2}$ — 26.5 »	$^{15/3}$ — 27.5 »	$^{15/4}$ — 27.8 »
$^{15/2}$ — 26.5 »		

Summary: Bilateral hilus-gland tbc with peribronchites, without certain R. General condition somewhat improved already before starting the orange cure; after that considerable improvement of general condition and marked improvement of lung status.

38.

Ingrid Linnea K-n, born $9/10$, 1911. Labourer's daughter. Hagalund. *Anammes.* Pat. $1/5$. No tbc in family. Morbilli, pertussis at the age of $2\frac{1}{2}$. At the age of 3 peritonitis. Since then weakly and thin. Easily catching cold. In the beginning of Dec. 1922 she fell into the water, after that cough and fever. Nursed in the Allmänna Barnhuset $7/12$ 22— $24/2$ 23 for the pulm. (Roentgen).

Admitted $24/2$ 23. Roentgen: both hilus greatly enlarged with peribronchites downwards. *Status* $7/3$: left lung isc short tone and dry R all the way down. Right lung: isc somewhat short tone and buzzing resp. with accompaniments. Rather pale and thin. Appetite fairly good.

Extracts from records. $18/4$: left lung I—II and isc. isolated dry accompaniments. For the rest nothing. Right lung, everywhere unclear resp., but no accompaniments. Still coughs a great deal. General condition improved. $24/5$: right lung, around mamill. isolated dry accompaniments. Left lung: $1/2$ A—downwards in places isolated — some few dry R. Otherwise nothing. Coughs less. Generally improved. $15/6$: lung status idem.

Temp. generally subfebrile, sometimes a little above 38° C.

Weight chart:

$27/2$ — 27 kg.	$1/4$ — 27.4 kg.	$15/5$ — 29 kg.
$1/3$ — 26 »	$15/4$ — 28 »	$1/6$ — 29.5 »
$15/3$ — 26.5 »	$1/5$ — 28.3 »	$15/6$ — 29.5 »

Summary: Bilateral hilus tbc with peribronchites. Generally improved, locally sooner aggravated, like the cough. Less improved than might have been expected.

Conclusion for Couple t: Greater improvement of the orange case.

Couple u.

39. Or.

Carl Evert L-n, born $3/3$ 1919. Farmer's son. Össebygarn.

Admitted $1/2$ 23. Has tbc genu sin.; a year ago nursed in the Väsby Hospital. Capsular changes with small effusion (nothing in the bone). *Local status* $1/2$: both isc, more on the right, resp. very harsh, not quite clear. Isolated rhoncus in right isc. Otherwise nothing. Roentgen $3/2$: bilaterally enlarged hilus, more on the right.

Extracts from records. $2/3$: an orange a day. $7/3$: right isc resp. harsh. Otherwise nothing. $18/4$: sometimes in both isc isolated creaking accompaniments. Never coughs. General condition considerably improved. $24/5$: status idem. General condition improved. $29/6$: resp. still harsh in both isc. Otherwise nothing. Never coughs. General condition greatly improved.

Weight chart:

$1/2$ — 16.5 kg.	$1/3$ — 17.5 kg.	$1/4$ — 18.2 kg.
$15/2$ — 16.5 »	$15/3$ — 17.9 »	$15/6$ — 18.7 »

Not weighed during the time $1/4$ — $15/6$ on account of a large plaster-bandage.

Summary: Bilateral hilus-gland tbc, more in right lung, with complications in left knee. Local symptoms unchanged. General condition improving the whole time. Appetite good all through.

40.

Carl Thore Lennart J-n, born $14/9$ 1919, Labourer's son. Solna.

Anamnesis: Pat. $1/1$. Father tbc in 1921, now well. Pat. always weakly, pale, easily catching cold. Bad appetite. $2/1$ 23: Pirquet pos.

Admitted $8/1$ 23. *Status:* Left side, both isc short tone, resp. very harsh, unclear. Suspicion of accompaniments. Temp. mostly subfebrile with isolated higher points.

Extracts from records. $7/2$: bronchitic symptoms. Rhonchi over both lungs. Right lung below A and laterally to the left half-hard accompaniments. Left lung in toto shorter tone. Last days increased cough. General condition improved. $7/3$: left lung, shorter tone nearly over the whole lung, increasing downwards. Resp. harsh. Right lung, resp. harsh, especially in isc. Now no accompaniments.

Roentgen $19/4$: enlarged hilus fields on both sides. $28/4$: scraping at the back of nose. Dismissed $30/3$ 23.

Weight chart:

$8/1$ — 15.2 kg.	$15/2$ — 17.2 kg.	$15/3$ — 17.8 kg.
$15/1$ — 15.5 »	$1/3$ — 17.8 »	$30/3$ — 18.2 »
$1/2$ — 16.5 »		

Summary: Bilateral hilus-gland tbc. General condition [improved. Possibly also some local improvement.

Conclusion for Couple u: Similar improvement.

Couple v.

41. Or.

Evald Torgny V-n, born $8/6$ 19. Carters' son. Lövö.

Anamnesis: No tbc in family. Well till last spring, then began growing thin and getting delicate. Pertussis at midsummer, afterwards bad general condition. Cough considerably lessened.

Admitted $8/9$ 22. *Status:* general condition bad, appetite bad. *Local status:* upper half of left lung short tone. Lower half softened tympanism, specially distinct below A. Resp. everywhere very harsh, isc almost bronchial. Diffusely over the whole lung rhonchi and hard, almost creaking R. Right lung: nowhere quit clear lung tone, resp. everywhere harsh, not quite clear. In some places isolated rhonchi and R (partly from elsewhere?).

Extracts from records. $5/11$: changes in right lung possibly increased. General condition improved. $1/11$: only below A on both sides isolated mostly dry accompaniments. For the rest no accompaniments or R. $3/11$: Roentgen. Left lung, distinct shadow from hilus upwards, also a little downwards. Right lung, distinct enlargement of hilus. $24/11$: rhonchi and R as on admission diffusely over both lungs. $8/12$: diffusely over both lungs rather coarse R, especially posteriorly below A bilaterally. Short tone on the right laterally and in isc. $10/1$ 23: left lung, numerous dry coarse R over the whole lung, mostly over the base. Right lung, isolated rhonchi diffusely over the whole lung. Resp. and D everywhere as before. Still coughing as before. General condition improved. $7/2$: D 1 all over the right lung, D 2 over the left, stronger posteriorly. Resp. as before. Rhonchi diffusely over both. Still fits of cough-

ing, but considerably less than before. General condition improved. Roentgen $2^{1/2}$: enlarged hilus shadows with peribronchites, mostly in left lung downwards. Appearance suggests tbc. $2^{2/3}$: an orange a day. $1^9/3$: right lung below III, isolated — some few fairly hard accompaniments. For the rest no R or accompaniments. D and resp. as before. Last week bad appetite. General condition as before. $1^8/4$: right lung accompaniments as before. Left lung below A isolated rhonchi. For the rest no R or accompaniments. Hardly ever coughs. General condition improved. $2^4/5$: nowhere R. For the rest as on $7/2$. Never coughs. $1^6/5$: resp. everywhere very harsh. D inconsiderable in left scl and base. Right lung no D or R, but harsh resp. Nowhere R. Coughs hardly ever. Dismissed $2^8/6$.

Summary: Bilateral hilus tbc with diffusely spread peribronchites. Before giving the orange general condition improved, but no local improvement. After the orange considerable improvement of local status and also of general condition, specially of appetite (flesh and weight were good when the orange was first given). Greater improvement than might have been expected.

Weight chart:

$8/9$ — 13 kg.	$1^5/12$ — 15.5 kg.	$1/4$ — 16.7 kg.
$1^5/9$ — 14.3 »	$1/1$ — 16.5 »	$1^5/4$ — 17.3 »
$1/10$ — 15.3 »	$1^5/1$ — 16.5 »	$1/5$ — 17.3 »
$1^5/10$ — 15.3 »	$1/2$ — 16.5 »	$1^5/5$ — 17.3 »
$1/11$ — 16.2 »	$1^5/2$ — 17.5 »	$1/6$ — 17.3 »
$1^5/11$ — 16.2 »	$1/3$ — 17.5 »	$1^5/6$ — 17 »
$1/12$ — 15.5 »	$1^5/3$ — 17.5 »	

Couple w.

43. Or.

Gustaf Ruben T-n, born $8/1$ 11. Carter's son. Hagalund.

Anamnesis: No tbc in family. Always been weak and thin. Has had morbilli, pertussis and pneumonia when three years old. Bronchial catarrh every year since two years old. Is said to have had attacks of asthma every year since he was 7. During the last years more frequent attacks. Admitted $1^6/2$. Bad appetite, thin. Both isc and I—III D 2. Besides, D 1—D 2 in right lung below A. Resp. in both isc of br. character with isolated inconstant mostly dry accompaniments. Right lung below A and anteriorly laterally isolated fairly coarse dry R. Resp. for the rest in both lungs harsh, unclear. No constant accompaniments. Roentgen $1^6/2$: both hilus considerably enlarged, the right more, with consolidation towards the base.

Extracts from records. $2^{2/3}$: an orange a day. $9/3$: R only right isc, D and resp. as before. Never coughs. $1/4$: D as before. No R. Resp. harsh, br. ves. as before. No cough. Dismissed $2^5/4 = 1/4$. Appetite considerably improved after orange; general condition also. Breathlessness gone.

Weight chart:

$1^6/2$ — 25.3 kg.	$1^5/3$ — 27.5 kg.	$1^5/4$ — 29 kg.
$1/3$ — 25.7 »	$1/4$ — 29 »	

Summary: Bilateral hilus affection with slight consolidation in base of right lung. Both locally and generally improved after the orange.

44.

Inga Maj Elisabet P-t, 4 years old.

Nursed in the Allmänna Barnhuset for pertussis + pneum. ac. dx. + tbc lphgl. bronch. June—Aug. 1922. Apparently well in the middle of Aug.

Afterwards nursed in the Serafimerlasarettet till admitted into the Sanatorium $^{21/10}$ 22.

Status $^{21/10}$: right lung, lower half D with tymp. accompaniments and unclear respiration verging on br. ves. Uncertain accompaniments. Left lung below A, D + resp. harsh. Inconstant accompaniments in some places laterally. $^{3/11}$ Roentgen: enlarged hilus shadows on both sides, most on the right. Shadow of the left base. $^{30/11}$: Left lung, laterally fairly certain fine accompaniments. For the rest status quo. $^{10/1}$ 23: right lung $^{1/2}$ A—A isolated accompaniments. Left lung: isolated rather dry accompaniments laterally. For the rest as before. Coughs slightly at times. General condition improved. $^{7/2}$: right lung, nowhere certain accompaniments. Left lung, below A and laterally some slight coarse accompaniments. Otherwise as before. Hardly ever coughs. General condition improved. $^{19/4}$: right lung below A sometimes suspicion of dry accompaniments. Left lung: no certain accompaniments. General condition as before. Last week bad appetite. $^{18/4}$: right lung I—III and isc resp. unclear, harsh, of almost br. character. On the right laterally resp. enfeebled. Nowhere certain accompaniments. Never coughs. No expect. Appetite better. General condition as before. $^{24/5}$: Nowhere R or accompaniments. For the rest status quo. Bad appetite. Never coughs.

Weight chart:

$^{15/2}$ — 15.5 kg.	$^{15/4}$ — 15.4 kg.	$^{1/6}$ — 15 kg.
$^{1/3}$ — 16 »	$^{1/5}$ — 15 »	$^{15/6}$ — 15.5 »
$^{15/8}$ — 15 »	$^{15/5}$ — 15.3 »	$^{1/7}$ — 15.5 »
$^{1/4}$ — 15.3 »		

Summary: Bilateral hilus tbc, most on right side. Before $^{1/3}$ improved, afterwards aggravation with regard to general condition (appetite!) and also locally.

Conclusion for Couple w: The orange case has improved more.